

Report on Assessment Methods and Results

WP6 Y3Q4

Task leader: Chalmers University of Technology

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Executive Summary

- Literature review on ICT applications to elderly with Mild dementia or Alzheimer disease concluded that technology can improve patients' quality of life, their cognitive performance, independence and other aspects, also can reduce caregiver's burden. However, new strategies to improve care are necessary (such as to improve communication and the organization of services). Through DECI, an IT-enabled integrated care approach that is implemented within multidisciplinary intervention for a considerable number of patients, is expected to produce new knowledge.
- A mixed-method study approach was applied combining quantitative (using standard questionnaires and IT log data) and qualitative methods (semi-structured interviews).
- Results from two different intervention groups and a control group were assessed to a limited sample of patients, and not the full sample of the recruited patients, due to time constraints.
- Clinical outcomes analysis suggests that patients participating in the complete intervention group (Group 2) present more stability in Basic activity of daily living (BADL) over time. This result could be interpreted as a benefit from physical activity program. No effect on global cognition has been found at this stage, due to relatively too short duration of intervention (six months) to observe changes in cognition. Hence, DECI could be a promising approach to delay BADL worsening in elderly people at the first stages of cognitive impairment.
- Quality of Life analysis when data from all pilots are combined into a single sample suggested that the partial intervention group (Group 1) has improved the perceived overall health state, in comparison to the Control group. The same result has been observed in Italy.
- Patient satisfaction analysis revealed that eHealth solutions of DECI were seen as complementary tools to the care system, but not eliminating the human contact. New roles – IT helpdesk for patients is found to be necessary to reduce burden of IT stability and usability from the healthcare professionals. A case manager role should be a part of MCI and MD care system.
- The healthcare professionals' perception analysis indicated that eHealth solutions of DECI were seen as complementary tools to the care system, appreciating all the ICT modules of the DECI solution, and a possibility to monitor patient's performance through these tools. Also, they believed that due to DECI they can keep the current or increase their job performance.

- Caregiver’s burden analysis indicated that with the studied sample, only the Spanish site demonstrated statistical significance in reduction of the total Zarit score.
- A good level of ICT penetration was achieved or a digital solution in the intervention groups, though with an overall sense of slow progression.
- From safety perspective, physical training program and activity monitoring sensor (a watch) raised concerns. Physical training program might need extra supervision for older population. Activity monitoring sensor caused some allergies through a skin contact.
- From ethical perspective, patients were concerned that the activity monitoring sensor, with its current design, can create an image of a sick person.
- DECI solution can increase process effectiveness: responsiveness to patient contact improved for the Group 2 patients. However, Group 2 patients needed more assistance resulting in increased consumption of healthcare resources.
- Although patients and caregivers were positive about DECI, most of them were not willing to pay for it.

1 Introduction

Dementia is one of the most common and serious disorders in later life. It causes irreversible decline in global intellectual and physical functioning, and has a significant personal, social, health and economic impact on people with dementia, their family carers, and health and social services (Alzheimer Association, 2016). Mild cognitive impairment (hereinafter – MCI) and Dementia are complex diseases and affect several fields of a patient’s life: cognitive functioning, social interaction (family and friends), activities of daily life and autonomy, general clinical condition, emotion and affectivity, quality of life (patient and informal caregiver), personal and family income. This disease also changes and creates new needs the people have.

It is quite clear today that assessment of cognition and functional ability is insufficient for clinical decision-making and policy development, and that importance of additional measures such as Quality of Life (QoL) and carer outcomes are crucial. Moreover, there is a need to improve the quality and consistency of care for older people with dementia. This includes increasing not only the appropriate prescription of anti-dementia drugs, but also the use of psychological and social management strategies for people with dementia and their caregivers. This points to the need to develop and evaluate different models of service provision for people with dementia and their family carers so that potentially beneficial interventions can be offered (Smith et al. 2005).

Given this complexity and given that DECI project will not only provide a new organisational model but also a multidisciplinary intervention (with possible impact on patient, caregiver and care providers), the evaluation process should be multi-componential and considering several aspects of affected stakeholders.

This document outlines the assessment methodology and results of the project. The methodology and results described in this document have been built on previous deliverables developed in DECI:

- D1.1 “State-of-the-art of clinical and assistance management models and practices of elderly patients with MCI”
- D1.3 “Patient, caregivers; and support and clinical organisational needs”
- D1.4 “Key performance indicators to be monitored”
- D2.2 “Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments”
- D2.3 “Change management and introduction processes of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments”
- D3.1 “Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions”
- D3.2 “Document of ICT solution requirements analysis”
- D3.3 “Definition of overall application (ICT solution and processes) in each country”
- D4.1 “Living and home automation”

- D5.1 "Pilot settings, organizational and technological model tuning in each country"
- D8.5 "Data management plan"

D6.1 also provided the informational basis for deliverables "D6.2 – A business case" and "D6.3 – Exploitation plan" that discusses transferability and exploitation potential of results and lessons learned.

2 Overview of existing evidence of ICT usage by elderly

Several works can be found in the scientific literature that assess the new technologies for patients with Alzheimer Disease and Mild Cognitive Impairment. In most cases, it has been concluded that the technologies under study improve patients' quality of life, their cognitive performance and their empowerment, but new strategies are necessary.

M. Yasini et al. (2016) evaluated the acceptance of new technologies in elderly patients. They assessed during 6 months a set of fifteen older adults that play serious games with a tablet. The authors obtained promising results and concluded that the acceptance of the technology was good and useful to improve the wellbeing of the users.

Lisa D. Van Mierlo et al. (2015) evaluated a platform that provided information on health and care services, tailored to the needs of people with dementia and their caregivers. The platform was easy accessible, anywhere and anytime. They designed a pilot in which patients with dementia and informal caregivers participated; the control group did not use the platform while the intervention group did. Authors concluded that the informal caregivers in intervention group improved their confidence; they also reported that the patients had more needs than they thought, in other words, the platform helped them to approach the actual problems of the patients.

G. Ben-Sadoun et al. (2016) tested the usability and effects of serious games targeting cognitive functions and physical activity. They included in the experiment 8 healthy elderly controls and 10 patients with Alzheimer disease or Mild-Moderate Cognitive Impairment; both groups were compared. The study concluded that the adherence was good in both groups; usability results suggested that the serious games represented a usable tool for both groups. However, in order to reach moderate or high intensity of aerobic activity, the games should be adapted to become more stimulating.

G. Sacco et al. (2012) objectified functional impairment in Alzheimer disease and Mild Cognitive Impairment through a video monitoring system for instrumental activities of the daily living. They also proposed a score able to predict the development of dementia, that would be very helpful for early intervention.

A. Astell et al. (2010) in their research, where 100 patients with mild cognitive impairment, participated, objectified that elderly people with cognitive impairment can be active partners in the research process. The authors concluded that older adults using their video games for cognitive stimulation improved their confidence.

Subramaniam and Woods (2016), compared multimedia digital life storybooks with conventional life storybooks in people with dementia in care homes. They evaluated six patients at 12 and 18 weeks of use. Their conclusions showed improvement in depression scores, autobiographical memory and quality of life but identified the small sample size as the most important limitation.

A. Pilloto et al. (2011), designed a smart platform which helped elderly patients with Alzheimer Disease and their caregivers to have a more independent lifestyle after detecting their needs. This platform had the objective of improving quality of life, quality of care and safety. In this study participated 223 patients along with their caregivers. At the end of the study the researchers concluded that caregivers considered the system useful to improve the management of patients with moderate Alzheimer Disease especially of those aged 75-84 years. Caregivers with low education and older caregivers had higher expectations on the potential role of ICT systems in improving the management of Alzheimer Disease patients. Furthermore, caregivers had positive attitude towards improving quality of life, quality of care and safety.

C. Kerssens et al. (2015) designed a platform which delivered psychosocial, non-drug interventions to patients with dementia at home to address individual neuropsychiatric needs. This tool was used by 7 patients and their caregivers. One of the most important things in this study was that interventions were personalized and delivered at home for a minimum of three weeks. After intervention, the researchers concluded that the personalized computer-based tool for managing neuropsychiatric symptoms and common needs in dementia was feasible, usable, and useful. The intervention helped care recipients and caregivers to cope with symptoms and needs in daily life. The main limitation in this study was the small sample size.

L. Núñez-Naveira et al. (2016) proposed an e-learning platform to help informal caregivers of patients with dementia. They explored the technical and the pedagogical specifications of the solution and evaluated the impact of its use on the psychological status of the participants. Sixty-one caregivers participated in the study. The authors concluded that the platform had a significant positive impact on decreasing the depressive symptomatology of the caregivers. However, the obtained satisfaction scores were generally low.

A systematic review (Fleming et al. 2014) that analysed 41 articles (seven articles were considered as strong, 10 moderate and 24 weak) concluded that safety improvements have a limited evidence; acceptance and difficulties associated to the use of technology were clear. The authors claimed that that small samples in the studies are one of the reasons of their conclusions. On the other hand, the researchers that conducted this review concluded that communication is very important in patients with dementia, thus telecare and telehealth can be used for assessment and for simple therapeutic interventions. Some assistive technologies for the provision of therapies have good evidence to be useful for patients, for instance, devices like high-intensity lighting in nursing homes help older adults with dementia sleep better, reducing behavioural disturbances.

Another systematic review (Pinto-Bruno et al., 2016) that evaluated 6 articles which assessed the effects of ICT solutions on the social health in patients with dementia and mild cognitive impairment, concluded that there are many types of technologies, from based leisure activities to universal technologies. These interventions can contribute positively, helping improve the wellbeing and quality of life. New approaches must be developed to improve social relationship in patients with dementia.

Finally, Powell et al. (2016) in the systematic review they conducted, where 6 articles were analysed, concluded that networked technologies supporting carers have moderate effects on improving their stress and depression. Nevertheless, these results should be treated with caution as they often come from multiple subgroup analyses. Further studies are needed to determine the role of the ICT to support informal caregivers and improve their needs.

Finally, it is important to remark the main innovation of DECI: patient monitoring and training approach enables to control patient's clinical status, demonstrating decay curves trends. Moreover, monitoring of patient's vital signs is one of the most effective ways to address patients' and their caregivers' needs. Additionally, DECI will not only pilot a new organisational model but also it is a multidisciplinary intervention. Moreover, the number of patients that will participate in testing the DECI solution will be significantly higher than in previous studies, so it is expected to obtain more reliable and significant results.

3 Appropriate methods for research of individuals affected by Mild cognitive impairment and Mild dementia

Dementia is one of the most important problems of aging. Dementia is a neurodegenerative disease that implies progressive deterioration in the cognitive function (memory, orientation, calculation, language, comprehension, learning capacity and judgement), behaviour and care needs. Assessment in dementia relies on collateral as well as patient-derived information. Several tools are today available to assess the different domains affected by the disease both for clinical and research purposes (e.g. tests, questionnaires, structured and un-structured interview). Specifically looking at scales used in MCI and dementia, the ideal one should demonstrate face validity and concurrent validity against gold standard assessments, should be reliable, practical, and should rely more on objective rather than subjective information. Another important point concerns the usability, the tool should be practical to use (e.g. being short) and acceptable (e.g. it does not upset, exhaust or embarrass the patient or assessor).

A specific aspect of dementia assessment, with respect to other medical conditions, is the increased need of information from external sources (e.g. caregivers, family members) to reach a reliable picture of patient status. Dementia may affect patient judgement capabilities so that information from proxies, or from external monitoring devices if available, could be crucial at all stages in the care process. This is directly relevant to the choice of assessment scales to be used in dementia care and research. In particular,

judgements about functional impairment, quality of life and behaviour problems may have to be mainly, or entirely, derived from proxy reports (Sheehan 2012). According to the above considerations, the best approach to dementia patient assessment combines performance-based tools (e.g. MMSE and CDT) and proxy measures recollected from caregivers (e.g. ADL and IADL). Moreover, as a great number of caregivers of people with dementia experience significant impact on their daily life, measures related to caregiver burden are also of great importance to define the whole impact of dementia.

4 Methodology of assessment

The purpose of this study is to examine the introduction of digitally-supported services in four different contexts, highlight implications for stakeholders and identify characteristics of DECI solution that have been well appreciated, and the ones that need improvement. Starting from the framework of Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) adopted for the development of deliverables 2.2 and 3.1, the chapter 4 describes how assessment was carried out.

Figure 1. Domains of DECI evaluation

Methods for data collection and analysis of each perspective have been selected after consideration of methods used in other studies (in particular, a research protocol in the ISISEMD project (Mitseva et al., 2010), and a study protocol in the National Evaluation of the Department of Health's Integrated Care Pilots (RAND Europe, 2012). The methods for data collection and analysis in the DECI project are described in detail in the chapters 4.1-4.6 of this document.

In each Country, the assessment was performed considering the three patient's groups:

- **Control group:**
The care received by the control group in each pilot was a routine care from each local site. Patients from the control group did not receive ICT and a business model of DECI.
- **Intervention group 1: IT-based organizational model:**
Intervention group 1 was related to the IT-based organizational model. Patients belonging to the Intervention group 1 received both technological (limited) and organizational intervention. The key organizational change was

an introduction of a Case manager role who was responsible for patient's care coordination using the Integrated platform (valid for all pilot sites). The key technological change concerned introduction to the IT platform which was used for scheduling activities and meetings, and for communicating to the specialists. Patients received a tablet device with access to the Integrated platform (not received in Sweden).

- **Intervention group 2 - IT-based organizational model and IT-based cognitive and physical training and activity monitoring**

Intervention group 2 was the all-inclusive intervention, offering both IT-based organizational model and IT-based physical and cognitive exercises, and also activity monitoring wearable device. Patients belonging to the Intervention group 2 received both technological (all-inclusive) and organizational interventions.

Intervention group 2 was divided into patients with wearable activity sensors and without.

It should be noted that differences in the interventions between pilot sites exist (see chapter 5.7 in documents D5.1, D5.2, chapter 2.7 in D5.3, and chapter 1.7 in D5.4). These differences will affect how data should be interpreted.

4.1 Clinical perspective

4.1.1 Patient perspective

Use of DECI can have diverse effects on patients. The effects will be evaluated through different domains (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Evaluation domains in the patient perspective

In the following chapters, each domain of the patient perspective and its evaluation methodology are described in detail.

Patients' Quality of Life

Understanding the effects of the DECI solution to the patients' quality of life is one of the principal goals of the DECI project. Therefore, the objective is to assess whether perceived quality of life by patients was affected by DECI. Also, to investigate which features comprising the concept of quality of life as defined by Brooks (1996) were affected. The quality of life will be assessed by using a EuroQL-5D-5L questionnaire, which was developed by the EuroQoL Group in 2005, and translated in different languages. The questionnaire was used only by patients, and in all groups of the pilot: Intervention 2, Intervention 1 and Control group. The questionnaire was administered twice: at the baseline and after 6 months (completion of the intervention).

EuroQL-5D-5L is a 5-dimensional questionnaire with 5 answer options in each. The dimensions of the questionnaire are: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression (Brooks, 1996). The answers to each dimension can range from no problems to extreme problems, comprising 5 answer levels in total per each dimension. The result of the questionnaire is a 5-number string which describes the coded health state of the respondent.

EQ-5D Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) is used together with the 5-dimensional questionnaire, and it reflects patient's self-rated health at the moment of administering

the instrument. The scale is a continuum from 0 to 100, where a patient marks A number indicating his/her perceived health state today. 100 reflects the best possible health state, and 0 – the worst possible health state.

EQ-5D-5L health states derived as a 5-digit string can be converted into a single index value using the Crosswalk calculator. The index values are the advantage of the EQ-5D instrument that allow to calculate the quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) that are used in cost-effectiveness assessment.

Methods of data analysis

The data analysis was first conducted for the total sample by combining populations from all countries into a single sample. Then, results from a population of each country were analysed separately.

Demographic and background data were calculated in percentages to facilitate comparisons between groups. To assess EQ-5D dimensions, the responses ranging from 1 to 5 in each of the five dimensions (mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression) were combined into two dichotomous groups. Level 1 represented a 'no problem' state, and Levels 2, 3, 4, 5 were combined into a 'problem' state as recommended in the EQ-5D user manual. Statistical analysis in SPSS software was performed using Chi-square and Fisher's exact statistical tests, with confidence level set at 0.05.

EQ-5D VAS scale results were compared between baseline and follow-up stages for each patient group. The significance of the changes was checked using one-way ANOVA with confidence level set at 0.05. Significance of the results between different patient groups was calculated using a post-hoc Bonferroni test.

For calculation of the EQ-5D index values, the value sets were not readily available for Italy, Sweden and Israel. Therefore, the value set of Spain was used for Italian index values, Danish value set was used for Swedish and Israeli index values. The index values represent the 'stated preference' of a general population of a particular countries and are not disease-specific. Using the value sets of different population (like Danish for Israel and Sweden, and Spanish for Italian) introduces variance that does not emerge from the actual patient data of the researched populations. Such limitation has to be taken into account when summarizing the results of EQ-5D index values and stipulating about the significance of the differences between patient groups or different populations. The significance of the changes was checked using one-way ANOVA with confidence level set at 0.05. Significance of the results between different patient groups was calculated using a post-hoc Bonferroni test.

Cognitive performance

Methods of data collection

Cognitive functions are among the first impaired competences in patients suffering from MCI or Dementia. Two screening tools widely used to assess global cognitive function in patients suspected for dementia are Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE; Folstein et al. 1975) and Clock Drawing Test (CDT; Schulman 2000). MMSE is also used to grossly categorize the global cognitive performance in four stages: normal, mild impairment, moderate impairment, severe impairment (NICE Guidelines, 2015). Moreover, the combined use of MMSE and CDT shown, in some study, to be useful to discriminate MCI from dementia patient (Umidi et al. 2009).

In the DECI project, MMSE and CDT (according to Schulman 2000 scoring system) will be used to assess the global cognitive performance of the enrolled patients, and the scores obtained will be used as measures of outcome for the cognitive area. Both for intervention groups and control group, MMSE and CDT will be administered at the beginning of the study (T0) and at the end of the 6 months of intervention (T1).

Methods of data analysis

Descriptive statistics will be computed using mean and standard deviation for continuous variables and counts for categorical variables. Differences at baseline will be tested by Chi-square or Fisher exact tests for categorical variables, one-way ANOVA for normally distributed continuous variables and Kruskal-Wallis H tests for non-normal continuous variables. Post-hoc will be computed by mean of independent t-tests for normally distributed continuous variables and Mann-Whitney U-tests for non-normal continuous variables (Bonferroni correction has been used to correct for multiple comparisons).

To test the impact of the intervention on cognitive performance, Change Scores (CSs), both for MMSE and CDT, will be computed using the raw scores of each participant according to the following formula: $T1 \text{ score} - T0 \text{ score}$. The result of this computation will be a positive value for better performance at T1, a negative value for worse performance at T1, and 0 for a stable performance. Differences in CSs obtained for MMSE and CDT among the three groups of participants will be computed by one-way ANOVA or by Kruskal-Wallis H tests according to the type of distribution emerged. Post-hoc test will be selected according to the test used and Bonferroni corrected for multiple comparisons.

Autonomy in daily life

Methods of data collection

According to the Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5, American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and to Petersen (2004), the main difference between Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and Dementia is the interference of the patients' cognitive impairment with the Basic or Instrumental Activities of the Daily Living (B-ADL, I-ADL). MCI patients' cognitive deficits do not widely interfere with the autonomy in the B- and I-ADL, while dementia patients' deficits do (i.e., at a minimum, requiring assistance with complex instrumental activities of daily living such as paying bills or managing medications). The evaluation of daily living activities could be carried out either by using Barthel (Collin et al. 1988) or Katz Index (Katz et al. 1963), among others, for B-ADL, and Lawton Index (Lawton and Brody, 1969) or Functional Activities Questionnaire (Pfeffer et al. 1982), among others, for I-ADL. Cornelis et al. (2017) developed and validated an evaluation of every functioning in basic and instrumental ADL based on the Katz Index and Lawton Scale, linking them to the definition and codes of the International Classification of Human Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF). This evaluation of B- and I-ADL can contribute to the diagnostic differentiation between cognitively healthy ageing and neurocognitive disorders in older age (Reed et al. 2016; Cornelis et al. 2017). Besides, ADL disability might increase the risk for incident dementia, therefore, the cognitive assessment must evaluate both basic and instrumental of daily living activities in all patients, because it is useful, not just as diagnostic tool but also as indicator of the risk future dementia (Di et al. 2016). Thus, making evaluation of autonomy in ADL is essential to diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment or mild dementia.

In the DECI project, B-ADL and I-ADL will be evaluated to assess the autonomy of the enrolled patients, and the scores obtained will be used as measures of outcome for the autonomy area. Both for intervention groups and control group, B-ADL and I-ADL will be assessed at the beginning of the study (T0) and at the end of the 6 months of intervention (T1).

The two areas of B-ADL and I-ADL have been assessed in a slightly different way in the four pilot sites, due to local specificity in clinical practice. In order to harmonize the obtained measures, the following recoding activity has been implemented.

Basic Activity of Daily Living (B-ADL) scoring

Instruments used in the pilot sites to measure the B-ADL were different. Italy and Sweden used a 6-item Katz Index. Spain and Israel used Barthel 10-item instrument with different scoring options: in Spain, the scores were 0/5/10, while in Israel 0/1/2. To enable a cross-case analysis, the instruments have been aligned between all countries by converting the answers to match the shorter instrument Katz Index used in Italy and Sweden (see Table 1)

Italy/Sweden	Israel	Spain
Q1 Bathing 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q4 Bathing 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q2 Bathing 5=fully independent, converted to 1 0=dependent
Q2 Dressing 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q3 Dressing 2=fully independent, converted to 1 1=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0	Q3 Dressing 10=fully independent, converted to 1 5=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0
Q3 Toileting 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q5 Toileting 2=fully independent, converted to 1 1=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0	Q5 Toileting 10=fully independent, converted to 1 5=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0
Q4 Transferring 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q8 Transferring 3=fully independent, converted to 1 2=dependent, converted to 0 1=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0	Q8 Transferring 15=fully independent, converted to 1 10 dependent, converted to 0 5 dependent, converted to 0 0 dependent, converted to 0
Q5 Continence 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q6 (Bladder control) + Q7 (Defecation) If both Q6 and Q7 gave score 2, the answer was assumed "full independent", converted to 1. If either of Q6 or Q7 answers gave any score other than 2, the answer was assumed "dependent", converted to 0.	Q6 (Defecation) + Q7 (Continence) If both Q6 and Q7 gave score 10, the answer was assumed "full independent", converted to 1. If either of Q6 or Q7 answers gave any score other than 10, the answer was assumed "dependent", converted to 0.
Q6 Feeding 1=fully independent 0=dependent	Q1 Feeding 2=fully independent, converted to 1 1=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0	Q1 Feeding 10=fully independent, converted to 1 5=dependent, converted to 0 0=dependent, converted to 0

Table 1. Alignment of B-ADL scores and questions

In Israel, the questions Q2 (Personal Hygiene), Q9 (Mobility), Q10 (Up and down stairs) were beyond the scope of the Katz index, and these questions were not included in the analysis.

In Spain, the questions Q4 (Cleanliness), Q9 (Up and down stairs), Q10 (Transferring) were beyond the scope of the Katz index, and these questions were not included in the analysis.

Instrumental Activity of Daily Living (I-ADL) scoring

Instruments used in the pilot sites to measure the I-ADL were the same Lawton-Brody Instrumental Activities of Daily Living Scale. Answers to different questions grant scores 0 or 1. However, the scoring system was different in the Israeli pilot. The answers in Israeli instrument grant 4, 3, 2, 1, 0. The following table describes how the scores of an Israeli instrument were converted to the scoring system used in other pilot sites, in order to enable a cross-case analysis (see Table 2).

	Italy, Sweden, Spain	Israel
Q1 Telephone	1 0	3,2,1 converted to 1 0 converted to 0
Q2 Shopping	1 0	3 converted to 1 2, 1, 0 converted to 0
Q3 Cooking	1 0	3 converted to 1 2,1,0 converted to 0
Q4 Household	1 0	3,2,1 converted to 1 0 converted to 0
Q5 Laundry	1 0	2, 1 converted to 1 0 converted to 0
Q6 Transport	1 0	4, 3, 2 converted to 1 1, 0 converted to 0
Q7 Medication	1 0	2 converted to 1 1, 0 converted to 0
Q8 Money	1 0	2,1 converted to 1 0 converted to 0

Table 2. Alignment of I-ADL scores and questions

Methods of data analysis

Descriptive statistics will be computed using mean and standard deviation for continuous variables and counts for categorical variables. Differences at baseline will be tested by Chi-square or Fisher exact tests for categorical variables, one-way ANOVA for normally distributed continuous variables and Kruskal-Wallis H tests for non-normal continuous variables. Post-hoc will be computed by mean of independent t-tests for normally distributed continuous variables and Mann-Whitney U-tests for non-normal continuous variables (Bonferroni correction has been used to correct for multiple comparisons).

To test the impact of the intervention on autonomy, Change Scores (CSs), both for B-ADL and I-ADL, will be computed for each participant according to the same formula used for cognitive data: T1 score – T0 score. The result of this computation will be a positive value for better performance at T1, a negative value for worse performance at T1, and 0 for a stable performance. Differences in CSs obtained for B-ADL and I-ADL among the three groups of participants will be computed by one-way ANOVA or by Kruskal-Wallis H tests

accordingly to the type of distribution emerged. Post-hoc test will be selected according to the test used and Bonferroni corrected for multiple comparisons.

Satisfaction

Data collection in DECI project evaluation is specific due to magnitude of the scope and patient sample, and, most importantly, MCI and mild dementia diagnosis of elderly patients. During the final study meeting with clinicians, MCI or mild dementia affected patients will have to fill-in a number of questionnaires comprising of a considerable number of questions. In order to achieve depth of knowledge, additional qualitative interviews will be performed. However, the cognitive burden of answering the questionnaires and also an interview has to be taken into account for MCI and MD patients. While conducting interviews in qualitative research, significance of readiness to take part and share experiences and perceptions in “articulate, expressive, and reflective manner” has been emphasized by Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979). Therefore, interview respondents have been selected based on convenience which is the most feasible strategy of purposeful sampling in DECI project case. In qualitative research, purposeful sampling allows to identify and look for rich cases to gain depth and richness of understanding (Palinkas et al., 2015). Convenience sampling is useful in this situation, since the respondents are selected based on accessibility to the researchers (Palinkas et al., 2015). Although this strategy might not reach the saturation of information or capture variety of cases, it is a feasible strategy given the constraints of the population.

Same number of respondents have been agreed to interview at each site. 10 patients within each intervention group and a control group should be interviewed (see Figure 3 below). Preferably, informal caregivers should be present during the interview in order to support the patient and enrich information obtained with additional insight.

Figure 3. Interview sampling

The interviews will be recorded, transcribed and translated to English language by the project team members.

The key principles of interview strategy are:

- Patients for interview shall be selected based on their availability.
- Interviews will be performed after the patient completes participation in the pilot.
- Patients to be interviewed must have demonstrated the use of the system that is recognizable as valid intervention.
- Patients that have dropped out of the study will be asked to share reasons of the drop-out. No formal interview will be performed with these patients. The reasons of the drop-out will be reported by clinical partners according to specific questions agreed among the Consortium (see D5.1) and later analyzed.

The following table lists the interview questions for each patient group.

Category	Intervention group 2 – IT-based org. model and IT-based training and monitoring	Intervention group 1 – IT-based org. model	Control group
Care model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What did you like best in the care you received? 2. What did you like less in the care you received? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What did you like best in the care you received? 2. What did you like less in the care you received? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What did you like best in the care you received? 2. What did you like less in the care your received?
Overall DECI solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Did you need to learn new things before you could start using the system? 4. Would you like to use DECI system in the future? (Why?/Why not?). <p>Extra question (if possible): Do you think the instructions and training that you got in order to use the system, was enough?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Did you need to learn new things before you could start using the system? 4. Would you like to use DECI system in the future? (Discuss the reason of the answer). <p>Extra questions (if possible): Do you think the instructions and training that you got in order to use the system, was enough?</p>	N/A
Physical exercise system	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. What do you think about the training with the help of a system? 	N/A	N/A
Cognitive exercise	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Have you tried cognitive exercises with DECI solution? What do you think about it? 	N/A	N/A

Activity monitoring (watch)	<p>7. Have you tried the watch? What do you think about it?</p> <p>8. How do you feel about the fact that your activity is monitored by professionals and family members?</p> <p>Extra question (if possible): Is there anything within the watch that you would prefer to change (design/size/weight etc.)?</p>	N/A	N/A
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Table 3. Interview questions to patients

Methods of data analysis

The analysis of the patient perceptions was performed through a computer-aided deductive thematic analysis in the NVivo software developed by QSR International. Coding of the information was based on the scheme that was derived from the concepts included in several prominent models: Diffusion of Innovation (Rogers, 2003), Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), Service Quality Framework SERVQUAL (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985), Product Quality Framework (Garvin, 1987). Hence, patient perceptions were deductively coded using the following codes: performance, features, aesthetics, product reliability, ease of use, usefulness, compatibility, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service reliability, tangibles, trialability, observability, relative advantage, communicated quality. Qualitative data will be analyzed through a thematic comparison of the key statements between intervention and control groups within a specific pilot site, and between intervention and control groups of different sites. The assumption in qualitative data analysis of DECI project will be that there can be differences in the views and perceptions of different aspects of intervention by different service user groups under study. The emergence of common patterns in giving meaning and perceiving experiences will be looked for.

4.1.2 Informal caregiver perspective

A problem directly related to the progressive loss of independence of patients suffering from dementia is the burden of patient's informal caregiver. The burden refers to the actual demands the caregiving requires, and to the subjective stress the caregivers experience (Deeken et al. 2003). Great amount of the help provided to patients comes from family members (Alzheimer's Association, 2016). Informal caregiver tasks range

from helping with ADLs and IADLs to managing behavioural symptoms of the disease (e.g. night time disturbances, aggressive behaviours). It is now well known that a great number of caregivers of people with dementia experience significant financial, emotional and physical difficulties with possible impact not only on quality of life but also on health and mortality (Alzheimer’s Association, 2016).

DECI services are expected to reduce the burden that relates to care for the patient. Physical and cognitive activity monitoring of the patient, and subsequent contact that specialists can initiate based on alerts of low or insufficient physical or cognitive activity are expected to have effect on the burden of care. Furthermore, meeting scheduling and possibility to communicate with specialists via Integrated platform are expected to facilitate contacts between patient, caregiver and multi-disciplinary teams.

Figure 4. Evaluation domains in the informal caregiver’s perspective

Methods of data collection

The informal caregivers’ burden will be assessed using Zarit Burden Interview which is a 22-item questionnaire. The survey will be filled-in at two time spots during patient’s participation in the pilot: at baseline and after 6 months of the intervention.

Methods of data analysis

The method selected to analyse the data regarding the Zarit test applied to DECI patients’ caregivers consists in calculating the difference in the T0-T1 slope between the two intervention groups and the control group, which shows the intervention effect of the

DECI platform in terms of caregivers' burden. The results obtained are the estimate difference of the T0-T1 slope, the standard error (Std. Error) and the statistical significance of the results, which will be reported in the way: *slope (std. error) with p*.

Apart from the analysis related to the effect of the intervention, a table per patient group is shown to depict the evolution of the Zarit score level (divided into 3 groups) from T0 to T1.

4.1.3 Healthcare professional perspective

Healthcare professional’s perceptions and experiences regarding eHealth are recognised as one of the critical elements of eHealth adoption. While national policies and decision making can be a macro-level barrier to adoption, healthcare professionals’ hesitation to adopt solutions represent one of the micro-level barriers to diffusion of the solution. A systematic literature review performed by Li et al. (2013) identified 40 factors that are important to healthcare professional’s acceptance of eHealth solution. The factors were categorized into 7 clusters (see Figure 5):

Figure 5. eHealth acceptance factors and clusters (adopted from the study by Li et al (2013))

Perceptions and experiences of staff involved in the DECI intervention in all pilot sites will be collected through in-depth interviews that will be conducted locally in pilot sites. The targeted sample for the interview will involve all the healthcare professionals that have been involved in care process of Intervention groups 1 and 2. While a part of interview will cover the perceptions and experience during the intervention itself, another part of the interviews will address areas based on the 7 clusters identified in the study of Li et al (2013). Taking into account time and resource demands to do a complete interview addressing all the factors, the most relevant ones are selected from each cluster.

The interviews will be conducted in the last months of the intervention, transcribed and translated to English. The following table contains interview questions.

Category	Interview questions
Healthcare provider characteristics	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Your occupational group: nurse, physiotherapist, geriatrician, psychiatric, occupational therapist, administrator/manager 2. How many years have you worked in your current job? 3. Your age group: 16-30; 31-50; 51+65; 66+ 4. Gender: male/female 5. What is your experience with information technologies: Experienced user; Intermediate user; Basic user; No experience
Performance expectancy	<p>Perceived usefulness and needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. What did you like best in the care you provided? 7. What should be improved in the care process? <p>Relative advantage:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. In your opinion, is the care process using DECI better or worse compared to the usual care process for MCI and mild dementia patients? 9. Did you have a responsibility of a case manager during intervention? What do you think about this role? <p>Perceived usefulness and needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. What do you think about patient physical and cognitive training with the help of the system? 11. What do you think about the watch and its usefulness to patients, caregivers and healthcare professionals? <p>Job-Fit:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Do you think that throughout intervention you were able to do your job to a standard you are personally pleased with? And do you believe that DECI helped you improve your job performance? 13. On average, how many hours a week have you normally worked specifically on the DECI intervention? Throughout the DECI intervention, could you manage all time demands at work?
Effort expectancy	<p>Perceived ease of use:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. Was the technology easy to understand and use? 15. Were the instructions and training sufficient?
Perspectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16. Would you like to use the DECI system in the future? (Discuss the reason of the answer).
Other comments	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 17. Do you have any other insights or concerns regarding DECI system or intervention? (Privacy, security, suppliers, cost, etc.)

Table 4. Interview questions to healthcare professionals

Methods of data analysis

The analysis of the healthcare professionals' perceptions was performed through a computer-aided deductive thematic analysis in the NVivo software developed by QSR

International. Coding of the information was based on the scheme that was derived from the concepts included in several prominent models: Diffusion of Innovation (Rogers, 2003), Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), Service Quality Framework SERVQUAL (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985), Product Quality Framework (Garvin, 1987). Hence, patient perceptions were deductively coded using the following codes: performance, features, aesthetics, product reliability, ease of use, usefulness, compatibility, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service reliability, tangibles, trialability, observability, relative advantage, communicated quality. Qualitative data will be analyzed through a thematic comparison of the key statements between intervention and control groups within a specific pilot site, and between intervention and control groups of different sites. The emergence of common patterns in giving meaning and perceiving experiences will be looked for.

4.2 Technological perspective

During assessment of DECI project, technology perspective is very important, as the intervention mainly happens through IT-enabled services. The evaluation of technology can have different evaluation criteria, as can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Criteria of technology evaluation

The basic evaluations focus on functionality (does a technology function as it should?), and if it is reliable (is it always available?). Within the technological outcomes evaluation of the DECI solution, we will focus on the following elements: technological functioning and reliability. The results of the study will allow us to 1) determine the quality of the technology, 2) further improve the quality of the technology and 3) to come towards a market ready product that can be implemented in clinical practice.

Methods of data collection and analysis

Regarding the Technical KPI the data have been collected assessing site by site the involved DECI Platform servers, database and logs archive. To collect and analyse all data Microsoft Excel and Splunk (<https://www.splunk.com/>) were employed. Concerning the Adamo watch usage and monitoring, the database from each site as been dumped and analysed with Opensource BI tools and Datasets (Python Pandas and Numpy).

Figure 7. Evaluation domains in technological perspective

Group 1 patients in Sweden did not receive IT modules and were not included in the analysis of technological outcomes.

Usage of the system

Assessment of the actual usage of the system will apply to intervention groups 1 and 2 and will not be applicable to the control group. Data will be taken at the end of pilot in each site. The following performance indicators will help assess the usage of the system.

Usage of the system			
TECH_KPI identifier	KPI title	KPI	Applicability
TECH_KPI 001	Login frequency to Integrated care platform	Reports all individual patients accesses to the Integrated care system , analysed per user and week of observation	Intervention group 2 Intervention group 1
TECH_KPI 002	Access frequency to Activity coaching system	Reports all individual patients accesses to Activity coaching program , analysed per user and week of observation	Intervention group 2

Usage of the system			
TECH_KPI identifier	KPI title	KPI	Applicability
TECH_KPI 003	Usage of Cognitive games system	Reports all individual patient accesses to Cognitive exercise application , analysed per user and week of observation, and measures its cumulative usage in terms of session duration	Intervention group 2
TECH_KPI 004	Access frequency to Activity Monitoring	Reports all individual user's (patients, caregivers and doctors) accesses to Activity monitoring sensor (watch) data analysed per user and week of observation, and its cumulative usage in calculating and visualizing reports.	Intervention group 2
TECH_KPI 005	Usage of Activity monitoring sensor	Activity monitoring sensor (watch) system wearing time and data evaluation	Intervention group 2

Table 5. KPIs to measure system usage

Technical stability of the system

Technical stability of the system will be assessed through bug reporting and statistical data of server. Once system bug is noticed or encountered, a user ought to fill-in the bug report and send it to a project partner responsible for resolution of technical issues. If the user is a patient, he /she should inform responsible healthcare professionals who will further report the bug to project partners.

During assessment, a number and typology of bug reports will be summarized per site. Reasons of the bugs will be analysed and reported in order to obtain knowledge of the technical barriers for DECI implementation within each context.

Technical stability of the system			
KPI identifier	KPI title	KPI	Applicability
TECH_KPI 006	Bug fixing and maintenance support	Overall analysis of issue reports received and their category	Intervention group 2 Intervention group 1
TECH_KPI 007	Service uptime	Percentage of time on which the system was accessible to work properly, based on system logs	Intervention group 2

			Intervention group 1
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Table 6. KPIs to measure technical stability of the systems

Assessment of technical dimension of DECI implementation will be complemented with assessment of experienced technical barriers, installation problems and local technical implementation problems within each site in DECI. Such knowledge and insights can be of high value for future transferability and exploitation of DECI solution in new contexts. The assessment will be addressed through interviews with the technical developers of each technology partner and local IT representatives from pilot sites. The prospective output from the interviews will be a description of the key technical issues and patterns of problems encountered, as well as the checklist for future implementations of DECI solution in a new context. This information will mainly feed the project document D6.3 which is intended to discuss transferability and exploitation of DECI solution.

4.3 Safety, ethical, legal and social perspectives

When introducing new technologies in healthcare (like the case of DECI) ethical, legal or social concerns, including benefits and risks, can be acknowledged in advance, and promising solutions can be identified if needed. To a large extent, evaluation in ethical, legal and social aspects will build on the MAST model (Kidholm et al 2012) which contributes with outlined aspects to be evaluated in these dimensions.

Ethics

Ethical aspects may involve concepts of right and wrong conduct. This conduct can be inspired by social values, norms and rules. Moreover, different countries may possess different sets of these aspects. It is worth to notice that these concepts comprise the context in which the DECI solution is implemented. Kidholm et al (2012) suggest that “ethical analysis appraises the ethical questions raised by the application itself and by the consequences of implementing / not implementing it”.

MCI and dementia patients are a vulnerable group of populations with certain needs. Hence, ethical analysis should address specific concerns related to this patient group. Preliminary ethical concerns in DECI are the following:

- Personal dignity
- Patient data monitoring by other people
- Access to the service
- Future affordability of the service

Since concerns have been reported that researchers often do not take ethical issues into sufficient consideration, DECI evaluation will address ethics beyond making sure that formal ethical procedures are followed and informed consent has been received from the

patients. Important questions have been raised by Kidholm et al (2012) as topics to consider additionally in the ethical analysis:

- Does the application challenge religious, cultural or moral beliefs?
- Potential ethical problems, e.g. giving the responsibility to the patients
- Autonomy: Is the patient's autonomy challenged or increased?
- Equity among different groups in society.

To increase transparency, ethical issues that might be identified during the intervention will be listed and discussed using interactive and participatory approaches (Reuzel et al 2001). Mainly, the thematic analysis will be carried out from interview transcription materials. Ethical questions will not be addressed directly to the respondents. Instead, ethical nuances will be searched for in the interview transcriptions. Moreover, workshops will be organized within consortium and other stakeholders in each country regarding transferability, after project results will be obtained. Importance of each identified ethical issue will be assessed by consensus seeking procedures, so that only significant ethical problems are emphasized during consideration of the transferability of the solution.

Legal aspects

Legal aspects include intellectual property rights, legislation and other regulations, as well as needed interventions by government which can determine the future of the technology. Since eHealth technologies have potential to improve healthcare operations and outcomes, investment decisions should be supported by policies and regulations. The legal aspects of DECI are mainly illuminated in other work packages (WP2 and WP7 D7.1 "IPR protection").

Social aspects

Social aspects include "soft impacts" and cultural and religious perspectives. The term "soft impacts" "reflects the effects of the technology on the quality of human life, which are difficult to quantify and more related to the psychological capacities such as experience, motivation, emotion, perception, habit and deliberation about action (Vijayavenkataraman et al. 2016). eHealth has a potential to change the usual ways of healthcare delivery which eventually has effect over people's lives.

Although the assumption is that DECI technology can improve care and help patients, and has, on a general level, a positive effect on life of the patients, it may not succeed without social acceptance by users. Hence, it is important to acknowledge that soft impacts can determine the adoption of the technology. Building on MAST framework (Kidholm et al 2012), relevant questions of the social aspects in DECI would be:

- How different users perceive digitally-enabled care using DECI technology?
- Changes in the patient's role in major life areas (e.g. social life, working life)
- Changes in responsibility. Are the patients and/or relatives capable of handling the responsibility?

- Gender issues. Has the service any consequences on the position of gender?
- Given a choice, would they prefer to use DECI technology over the current care?
- What are the changes to technology or processes are needed in order to soften the social impacts?
- Societal, political context and changes. Will the application influence the general model for the delivery of healthcare services if deployed?

These questions would help extract the potential barriers that would affect the adoption of DECI technology in the future. During evaluation, these issues will be covered through interviews with patients (see chapter 4.1.1 of this document) and healthcare professionals (see chapter 4.1.3 of this document). The interviews are expected to reveal users' position and acceptance of digitally-enabled care model using DECI technology in light of their cultural backgrounds and religious perspectives. It is highly advantageous that DECI project involves different countries, and the perceptions of users will be possible to compare. Surely, one should keep in mind that neither cultures, nor humans are static, and perceptions may change over time. During evaluation, it will be possible to obtain views of users at the end of intervention.

Safety

While DECI solution may bring a range of benefits that are outlined in the deliverable D1.4 "Key performance indicators to be monitored", evaluation of patient safety mainly relates to "identification and assessment of harms" (Kidholm et al. 2012). Patient safety in DECI will be assessed through clinical and technological perspectives, and side effects.

Clinical perspective will evaluate the experienced adverse events or harms due to the use of DECI solutions. The key potential areas of harms are identified as follows (Murray et al. 2005): false or misleading information circulating using the system, privacy violations, malpractice, lack of consistent quality criteria and regulation. Strategies of preventing such harms are outlined in the deliverable D8.5 "Data management plan". As Kidholm et al (2012) suggest, evaluation activities will concern the identification of the typology of harms experienced, their frequency and severity by answering the following questions:

- What are the direct or indirect harms when using DECI solution?
- What is the scope of the harms?
- What are the types of harms?
- Are there estimates of incidence of harms?
- What is the timing of onset of harms?
- What is the duration and severity of the harms?
- What can be done to minimise the harms?

The actual harms will be monitored and discussed within consortium in a bi-weekly call. The caused harms and strategies of dealing with the situation will be documented and reported together with the results of the intervention.

As Kidholm et al (2012) suggest, patient safety in **technological perspective** relates to technical reliability of the application. The evaluation of this aspect includes backup, interference and security of data. Strategies to deal with these issues have been discussed while planning the system installation which is eventually decided to be done locally while building on local policies and regulations for data security and backup. Although the preventive strategies have been in place, technical reliability will be assessed during evaluation by answering the following questions (Kidholm et al 2012):

- How did the back-up system work?
- What did the Service Level Agreements cover?
- Did the technology experience interference and what were the consequences?
- How was security of data and the database (data privacy) and quality of data managed? (Encryption/cryptography, data storage and ownership)

The last aspect of patient safety evaluation is **side effects**. Monitoring of the side effects of using DECI solution will be performed during bi-weekly calls between partners where any issues arising from the pilots will be discussed. Applicability and risk of the reported problem at the consortium level will be analysed and documented for future learning.

4.4 Business perspective

4.4.1 Process effectiveness perspective

Considering the process effectiveness perspective, the main impacts to consider could be mainly referred to three areas: effectiveness, efficiency and governance.

Figure 8: KPI categories in the process effectiveness perspective evaluation

The main hypothesis is that DECI solution will improve effectiveness, efficiency and governance within healthcare structures, from an organizational point of view, respectively by:

- Improving responsiveness of the contacts between clinicians and patients in case of need
- Reducing unnecessary consumption of healthcare resources and better allocating assistance time on added value activities
- Improving collaboration within healthcare providers
- Supporting better planning of treatment care plan

Use of DECI can have diverse effects on organizational structure and that will be evaluated through different domains.

Figure 9: Evaluation domains in the process effectiveness perspective

In the following chapter, each domain of the process effectiveness perspective and its evaluation methodology are described in detail.

Methodology

As described in previous deliverables, DECI project has the potential to affect care processes from various points of view, and it has the goal of improving the performances of the system/actors involved in these processes.

The analysis of the performances is realized between control groups and intervention groups, and among intervention groups. It includes several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) useful to consider various relevant standpoints.

The identified KPIs are the following:

- **Responsiveness (R):**
 - Description: the usage of a platform should allow to increase the number of interactions between patient/caregiver and clinical personnel, and to

decrease the response time of the various actors adopting it; thus, the KPI describes the latency and frequency of interactions between patient/caregiver and clinical personnel

- **Objective:** to know if frequency of contacts between clinicians and patients increase and the response time of the various actors decrease by adopting the platform
- **Healthcare Resources (H):**
 - **Description:** the adoption of DECI solution offers the opportunity to monitor the evolution of patient's diseases; thus, the KPI monitors the consumption of healthcare resources in relation to the evolution of patient's diseases and his/her clinical needs
 - **Objective:** to know if the reduced frequency and severity of the risks of the patient, decreases the number of hospital admissions/emergency visits and unplanned assistance
- **Assistance Time (T):**
 - **Description:** the adoption of DECI solution will impact on the time that clinical personnel spend in assisting the patient (e.g. for visits, phone calls, messages, hospital admission); thus, the KPI monitors the evolution of patient's diseases and his/her clinical needs
 - **Objective:** to know if monitoring patients has an impact on the assistance time employed by clinical personnel
- **Collaboration (C):**
 - **Description:** the adoption of DECI platform increases the chances of interactions among clinical personnel; thus, the KPI monitors the multidisciplinary interactions among clinical personnel
 - **Objective:** to know if the use of DECI has an impact on the multidisciplinary meeting in terms of number of patients discussed, mix of professional categories, time spent by professionals
- **Planning (P):**
 - **Description:** the usage of DECI solution enables the analysis of the evolution of patients' disease and the possibility to promptly review care plans in coherence to the changes of patients' needs over time; thus, the KPI monitors the evolution of patient's care plan
 - **Objective:** to know if the use of DECI has an impact on the definition of patients' care plans in terms of revisions and time spent by professionals

The analysis of these different aspects requires a deeper investigation of several elements (called Items) listed below.

Responsiveness is composed of:

- Time between the contact of the patient and the answer of the clinical personnel (and vice versa) (R_1);

- Number of times in which the patient contacts clinical personnel (and vice versa) (R₂).

Healthcare Resources are composed of:

- Number of visits per type (H₁).

Assistance time is composed of:

- Hours spent for the assistance in the presence by the clinical personnel (e.g. visits, calls) (T₁);
- Hours spent for the assistance in back office by the clinical personnel (e.g. answers to messages) (T₂).

Collaboration is composed of:

- Numbers of team meetings involving clinical personnel (for each patient) (C₁);
- Hours spent in multidisciplinary team meetings (C₂);
- Number of participant per professional category involved in multidisciplinary team meetings (C₃).

Planning is composed of:

- Number of revised physical training program (P₁);
- Number of revised cognitive games (P₂);
- Number of unplanned calls performed (P₃);
- Number of unplanned home/hospital visits performed (P₄);
- Hours spent for the definition of treatment plans (P₅);
- Hours spent for the revision of treatment plans (P₆).

Key performance indicators

Domain: Effectiveness	
KPI 001: Responsiveness	Applicability
Time between the contact of the patient and the answer of the clinical personnel (and vice versa)	Control group (CG) Intervention group 1 (GR1) Intervention group 2 (GR2)
Number of times in which the patient contacts clinical personnel (and vice versa)	CG, GR1, GR2

Domain: Efficiency	
KPI 002: Healthcare Resources	Applicability
Number of visits	CG, GR1, GR2
Domain: Efficiency	
KPI 003: Assistance Time	Applicability
Hours spent by the clinical personnel to care patients (e.g. visits, calls)	CG, GR1, GR2
Hours spent for the assistance in back office by the clinical personnel (e.g. answers to messages)	CG, GR1, GR2
Domain: Governance	
KPI 004: Collaboration	Applicability
Numbers of team meetings involving clinical personnel (for each patient)	CG, GR1, GR2
Hours spent in multidisciplinary team meetings	CG, GR1, GR2
Number of participant per professional category involved in multidisciplinary team meetings	CG, GR1, GR2
Domain: Governance	
KPI 005: Planning	Applicability
Number of revised physical training program	GR2
Number of revised cognitive games	GR2
Number of unplanned calls performed	CG, GR1, GR2
Number of unplanned clinical visits performed	CG, GR1, GR2
Hours spent for the definition of treatment plans	CG, GR1, GR2
Hours spent for the revision of treatment plans	CG, GR1, GR2

Table 7. KPIs to measure process performance

Methods of data collection

Mixed-method approaches based on quantitative and qualitative data, will be employed in order to obtain knowledge to answer to research questions. These approaches are seen as complementary in this study in order to go over limitations and constraints that each method inherently has. Moreover, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, allows

appreciating even small variations on observed groups, thus overcoming study limitations such as: i) limited time-span of observation; ii) home-based intervention that limits observation of patients; iii) diagnosis of MCI and dementia that affects data collection from patients.

To this extent, data collection will be performed mainly involving clinicians, through two different instruments:

- **Integrated platform**, developed by MACCABI;
- **Set of questions** addressed to clinicians and aimed at capturing information both from clinicians and patients (or caregivers) when data are not elsewhere available.

Both instruments will be employed to collect quantitative and qualitative data. Note that Integrated platform will collect only data referred to intervention groups (1 and 2). Data from control group will be collected only through the set of questions.

Data collection from **Integrated platform** will be performed throughout the study period, thanks to the continuous feed of clinicians that will update data on the platform whenever needed. In particular, data collected through the platform are the following:

- R1Time between the contact of the patient and the answer of the clinical personnel (and vice versa)
- R2Number of times in which the patient contacts clinical personnel (and vice versa)
- H3Number of visits per type
- P3Number of unplanned calls performed

Data collection through the **set of questions** will be performed at the end of each patient's journey in the pilot. The recipient of questions will be the clinician responsible for each patient (or the case manager). The clinician (or case manager) will be also in charge to address some specific questions to his/her patients at the end of their journey. If patients are not able to directly answer to the questions, their caregivers will be in charge of answering. Questions are distinct to each observed group (i.e.: control group, intervention group 1, intervention group 2) and to each recipient (clinician or case manager, patient or caregiver). According to this schema, the following data will be collected:

	CG	GR1, GR2
R1 Number of contacts between the patient and the clinical personnel (and vice versa) –and waiting time (on the platform)		X
R2 Number of contacts between the patient and the clinical personnel (and vice versa) –and waiting time (outside the platform)	X	X
H1 Number of visits per type	X	X

T1 Hours spent for the assistance in the presence by the clinical personnel (e.g. visits, calls)	X	X
T2 Hours spent for the assistance in back office by the clinical personnel (e.g. answers to messages)	X	X
C1 Numbers of team meetings involving clinical personnel (for each patient)	X	X
C2 Hours spent in multidisciplinary team meetings	X	X
C3 Number of participant per professional category involved in multidisciplinary team meetings	X	X
P1 Number of revised physical training program		X
P2 Number of revised cognitive games		
P3 Number of unplanned calls performed	X	X
P4 Number of unplanned home/hospital visits performed	X	X
P5 Hours spent for the definition of treatment plans		X
P6 Hours spent for the revision of treatment plans		X

Table 8. List of data to be collected

Collection of Key Performance Indicators for Business perspective

The following performance indicators related to business perspective will be collected as follows.

With respect to the **Integrated platform**, data will be collected by fulfilling the following sections of the platform:

- “Messages” (see figure below), is the section accessible from clinician’s side where clinicians and patients can communicate. For each message, data and time stamp are provided, thus allowing us to collect the following data:
 - R1Time between the contact of the patient and the answer of the clinical personnel (and vice versa)
 - R2Number of times in which the patient contacts clinical personnel (and vice versa)

With respect to the **set of questions**, data will be collected through a specific excel file that clinicians are requested to compile and keep updated.

Following the same logic of KPIs area, the excel file is elaborate as follows:

- For **responsiveness**, clinicians are asked to compile the following table adding rows for each patient:

		Responsiveness		
	Patient ID	Timestamp of the contact from the patient (by mail, phone, other) [if happens outside DECI ICS platform]	Timestamp of the answer of case manager or clinician (by mail, phone, other) [if happens outside ICS platform]	Channel (mail, phone, other - specify)
Example	DECI002	02/11/2017	02/11/2017	Phone
Example	DECI002			
Example	DECI002			

- For **healthcare resources and assistance time**, clinicians are asked to compile the following table adding rows for each patient:

		Healthcare resources - visits			
	Patient ID	Date of the visit	Professionals involved in the visit (geriatrician, nurse, psychologist, physiotherapist, etc.)	Aim of the visit: Study protocol visit or clinical, social care, technical assistance, etc.)	Length of the visit (hour)
Example	DECI002				
Example	DECI002	09/11/2017	Geriatrician, nurse	Protocol visit	1
Example	DECI002	13/11/2017	Geriatrician	Technical assistance	0,5
Example	DECI002				

- For **planning**, clinicians are asked to compile the following table adding rows for each patient:

		Planning	
	Patient ID	Date of revision of the cognitive games	Date of revision of the physical exercises
Example	DECI002		
Example	DECI002		
Example	DECI002		
Example	DECI002	09/11/2017	10/11/2017

- For **collaboration**, clinicians are asked to compile the following table adding rows for each multidisciplinary team meeting:

Collaboration - Multidisciplinary team meetings						
	Date of the meeting	Total number of patients discussed during the same meeting	DECI Patient IDs discussed	Number of Patients that are not in DECI discussed	Number of professionals involved per type (geriatrician, therapists, etc.)	Length (in hours) of the meeting
Example:	01/11/2017	9	DECI 001, DECI 004	7	1 geriatrician, 1 nurse, 1 physiotherapist	3

- For **assistance time** and average time of **planning**, clinicians are asked to compile the following table:

	Assistance time				Planning	
	On average, how many hours do you spend to visit the patient for the first time?	On average, how many hours do you spend to visit the patient during the 6-months intervention (if any visits occur)?	On average, how many hours do you spend to call the patient during the 6-months intervention (if any calls occur)?	On average, how many hours do you spend to answer to messages of the patient during the 6-months intervention (if any contacts occur)?	On average, how many hours do you spend to define the treatment plan of the patient at the beginning of the intervention?	On average, how many hours do you spend to update the treatment plan of the patient during the 6-months intervention?
Control group patients	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]
Intervention groups patients	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]	[hours]

Methods of data analysis

Data were collected considering all active patients by end of May and analysed using descriptive statistics. Count and mean were calculated after an accurate data cleaning, useful to remove outliers and standardize unit of measures (e.g. days, hours, timestamp, etc.).

4.4.2 Cost-minimization perspective

Methodology

The time in which the QALY effect should be detected in the DECI study protocol is limited, and there is a strong assumption that no significant difference between intervention groups and control group in health status will be found. Due to lack of apparent improvement in the health outcome, for which more time is needed to significantly detect and report, a Cost Minimization Analysis (CMA) will be most feasible to perform an economic evaluation on short notice. This study aims at providing evidence of minimizing healthcare costs with similar health outcomes between two intervention groups and a control group. We will do an empirical study, where actual costs are collected. The objective of the CMA is to determine cost per patient. We perform a CMA from a hospital perspective. This means that we do not take into consideration costs incurred by the patient.

Key performance indicators

Cost type	Type of specialist	Measurement	Allocated price
Consult / visit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ GP/Family doctor ▪ Physician ▪ Nurse ▪ Psychiatrist/psychologist ▪ Social worker ▪ Physiotherapist ▪ Occupational therapist ▪ Dietician 	<p>Number of consults/visits</p> <p>Duration of visit</p>	Tariff per hour

Table 9. Key Performance Indicators for Cost Analysis

Methods of data collection

Cost outcomes

Direct healthcare costs are measured within the evaluation from a hospital perspective. Direct healthcare cost are those costs directly connected to treatment or healthcare in the current care and intervention. So, all the directly involved costs connected to the healthcare patients receive and utilize while being in the study, for both intervention and control groups, will be assessed. In sum, one can state that via this analysis we will create an overview of the monetary costs for all conditions. Success in this definition is considered to be a positive outcome in the intervention groups compared to the control condition (i.e., lower costs in the intervention groups).

Willingness to pay (WTP)

Intervention groups 1 (partial intervention) and group 2 (complete intervention) are asked whether they would be willing to pay to remain in the DECI program. In addition, informal caregivers are asked to value the service by indicating their willingness to pay as well. Among those willing to pay for the service (i.e., $WTP > €0$), are asked how much they would like to pay each month. Besides, intervention groups and their informal caregivers are asked whether they would recommend DECI to others.

Procedure

The intervention will be implemented in four pilot sites for a period of 6 months for each patient. The cost outcomes will be compared between Intervention group 1, Intervention group 2 and the control group which will not receive intervention. Number of patients in each group is different in each site. To assess Willingness to Pay, we designed a questionnaire composed of 12 questions. The cost time range is 6 months. So, at the end of the intervention measurements of the demand/utilization of healthcare and WTP is done for patients and informal caregivers.

Methods of data analysis

Direct costs will be calculated. Number of visits to a specialist for the six months are calculated for each patient and compared between groups and pilot site specific. Protocol visits are not taken into account in the cost calculation as those are similar between groups. The sources of the cost data are internal records (patient health records) of each pilot site. Internal records are obtained retrospectively from historical data after the intervention has ended (patient charts). Expert opinions will be used when it is impractical to derive certain detailed costs. When attaching monetary value to costs, we apply current and locally relevant unit costs (pilot site specific). For that, we use published data sources when available from within the different hospitals and region where DECI takes place. All costs are reported in 2018/2019 prices. Costs were obtained in NIS (Israel), SEK (Sweden), and Euro's (Spain, Italy) and exchanged to € using the average 2018/2019 exchange rate.

Statistical analyses

Total costs will be compared between control and intervention groups between pilot sites. All hospital service use and costs are reported as means where descriptive statistics are presented. Willingness to pay will be summarized as not willing to pay, willing to pay and amount willing to pay. It will be calculated for treatment condition and pilot site specific.

Investment costs needed for DECI

Investments needed for DECI refers to the costs needed to successfully implement the DECI solution. One-time direct costs associated only with the clinical trial, preparing the organization and developing the DECI technology were excluded. This because, in the light of the health economic evaluation and the choice of performing a CMA, this is distorting the cost outcomes. Since we do not know what the initial investments costs of the control, the standard of care are, we cannot compare this on equal base. In other words, there will be always a negative cost-effectiveness effect on a new innovation in terms of investments costs if the benefits (as established earlier due to the CMA approach) will be the same in control and intervention. We therefore, will disconnect this assessment of investments cost from the CMA. However, this cost data will be needed, to ensure sustainable business cases and assessment of the connected business models and to determine whether the savings are worth the investment. As such, these one-time direct costs will be calculated during the project but will not be taken into account when performing the CMA. One-time direct costs are costs of hardware, installation costs, maintenance and support costs, training costs for healthcare professionals, patient-specific training, monitoring costs and project management costs. These costs will be classified as recurrent or capital. Capital costs are associated with hardware, as well as equipment and training of helpdesk workers. Recurrent costs are for example: administrative, management, travel and transport, monitoring, technology-related fees and support, help desk/ support. On a sole-base assess the expected investments cost connected to implementation and business

model. Most appropriately, this requires questionnaires' amongst involved stakeholders, pricing models on the technology, and a threshold analysis on break-even / ROI determination.

4.5 Expected results

Domain	Instrument of evaluation	Expected result
Clinical outcomes		
Quality of Life	EuroQL-5D-5L	For Intervention group 2, stable or increased perceived quality of life is expected. Group mean index value is expected to be higher than for Intervention group 1 and Control group. For Intervention group 1, stable or increased perceived quality of life is expected. Group mean index value is expected to be higher than for Control group. For Control group patients, no change in quality of life index value is expected.
Cognitive performance	MMSE	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of MMSE score in terms of group mean is by 0-3 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, expected worse or stable performance. Mean decrease of group score by 0-4 points.
	Clock Drawing Test	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of score in terms of group mean is by 0-1 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.
Autonomy	Basic ADL Barthel / Katz Index	For all groups, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.
	Instrumental ADL Lawton-Brody	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of score in terms of group mean is by 0-2 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.
Patient satisfaction	Interview	Group 2 and group 1 patients will be satisfied with the received DECI care and will be willing to use DECI solution in the future.
Informal caregiver's perspective		
Caregiver burden	Zarit test	Intervention group 2 caregivers are expected to report reduced burden in comparison to Intervention group 1 and Control group. Intervention group 1 caregivers are expected to report reduced or stable burden compared with Control group.
Healthcare professional's perspective		
Healthcare professional's satisfaction	Interview	Healthcare professionals will be satisfied with the provided care and will positively perceive the DECI business model and will be willing to use DECI solution in the future.

Safety, ethical, legal and social aspects		
Safety	Interview, drop-out information	DECI solution will be safe for the studied population.
Ethical aspects	Interview, drop-out information	DECI solution and study does not violate ethical principles.
Legal aspects	Interview, drop-out information	N/A
Social aspects	Interview, drop-out information	Patients in Group 2 and 1 will be more empowered using DECI solution. Healthcare professionals will be more empowered using DECI solution. Caregiver's burden will decrease for group 2 and group 1 patients.
Technology perspective		
System usage and stability	IT logs data, DECI platform	Good penetration of DECI solution will be achieved.
Business perspective		
Process effectiveness perspective	DECI platform data and data from outside platform	DECI solution will improve effectiveness, efficiency and governance within healthcare structures, from an organizational point of view, respectively by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving responsiveness of the contacts between clinicians and patients in case of need Reducing unnecessary consumption of healthcare resources and better allocating assistance time on added value activities Improving collaboration within healthcare providers Supporting better planning of treatment care plan
Cost-minimisation perspective	Data from outside platform	We expect healthcare consumption to be organized differently in the different groups, with on the long-term lower health care costs in intervention group 1 and 2 compared to the control group.

Table 10. Expected results

4.6 Data management during evaluation

The chapter provides description of data transfer aspects to be applied during evaluation process. The chapter also describes how data should be translated and handled by the collecting party.

As stated in the general terms of the deliverable D8.5, the appropriate data protection principles will be observed, including:

1. Data are fairly and lawfully processed
2. Data are used only in ways that are compatible with the original consent
3. The amount of data collected is relevant and not excessive
4. All reasonable efforts are taken to ensure data accuracy
5. The data are used in accordance with the rights of the study participant
6. The data are stored securely
7. The relevant international and national guidance will be consulted

In order to fulfil data security aspects, the underlying principles shall be applied:

- Data collection should be run with the use of convenient digital tools

- Data transfer to CHI, RRD or FPM should be done in a secure way (only anonymous and mandatory data for evaluation purposes)
- Bi-weekly discussions on data collection within consortium

Ethical and legal considerations regarding data management

Two articles from the Helsinki Declaration discussed in D 8:5 have special relevance for data collection and usage:

14. The design and performance of each research study involving human subjects must be clearly described in a research protocol. The protocol should contain a statement of the ethical considerations involved and should indicate how the principles in this Declaration have been addressed. The protocol should include information regarding funding, sponsors, institutional affiliations, other potential conflicts of interest, incentives for subjects and provisions for treating and/or compensating subjects who are harmed as a consequence of participation in the research study. The protocol should describe arrangements for post-study access by study subjects to interventions identified as beneficial in the study or access to other appropriate care or benefits.

23. Every precaution must be taken to protect the privacy of research subjects and the confidentiality of their personal information and to minimize the impact of the study on their physical, mental and social integrity.

The key principle in terms of data management is that all data has to be stored locally, in each country. A limited and personally approved research group at the Centre for Healthcare Improvement (Chalmers), Fondazione Politecnico di Milano and Roessingh Research and Development will be the only instances to access raw data of all study groups delivered for analysis purposes. Other partners of the consortium will receive aggregated results of data analysis that will be interpreted with the help of expertise of consortium partners.

Monitoring of data collection

For the purpose of monitoring the data collection during the pilots, a feedback/monitoring system will be created (described in Change management plan, deliverable 2.3). A monthly report will be extracted from the integrated platform, such as a number of enrolled patients in different groups, and response date for finalizing specific questionnaires (before and after intervention). The report data will be analysed within consortium on monthly basis.

Data transfer

Data from integrated platform will be transferred monthly to the researchers leading evaluation through a secure solution. Interview data will be delivered monthly, in order to save time, since it does not require waiting till the last patient finishes participation in the pilot.

5 Results of the assessment

In this chapter, assessment results of evaluation domains will be presented.

5.1 Clinical perspective

5.1.1 Cognitive performance and autonomy of daily living

Descriptive statistics, all pilot sites combined

One hundred and thirty-eight patients completed the protocol at the date of 30th of April 2018 (64 in Italy, 49 in Sweden, 13 in Israel, and 12 in Spain) and their results have been used for this preliminary analysis. Table 10 shows descriptive statistics for these patients at baseline. The groups of participants did not differ for age, years of education, gender (F/M) and principal diagnosis (MCI/MD), which were the variables used to stratify the patients in the three groups at randomization. Moreover, no differences were present among the three groups for mean Body Mass Index and mean number of comorbidity (for this variable, no data available for the Israeli patients at the moment).

	Control group N 37	Intervention group 1 N 48	Intervention group 2 N 53	<i>p</i> -Value
	N = 138			
Age (Mean ±SD)	78.24 ±6.10	76.88 ±6.98	76.08 ±5.08	<i>P</i> = ns
Education (Mean ±SD)	9.59 ±4.02	10.04 ±3.90	10.79 ±3.99	<i>P</i> = ns
Gender (F/M)	21/16	28/20	29/24	<i>P</i> = ns
Principal diagnosis (MCI/MD)	30/7	39/9	43/10	<i>P</i> = ns
Body Mass Index (Mean ±SD)	24.03 ±2.49	25.33 ±4.51	25.90 ±3.39	<i>P</i> = ns
N. Comorbidity#	2 ±1.10	1.89 ±1.51	1.64 ±1.21	<i>P</i> = ns

Table 11. Baseline characteristics and between group differences. #No data for Israel

Descriptive statistics, Italian pilot

Sixty-four patients completed the protocol at the date of 30th of April 2018 in the Italian pilot site and their results have been used for this preliminary analysis. Table 12 shows descriptive statistics for these patients at baseline. The groups of participants did not differ for age, years of education, gender (F/M) and principal diagnosis (MCI/MD), which were the variables used to stratify the patients in the three groups at randomization. No differences were present among the three groups for mean Body Mass Index and mean number of comorbidity.

	Control group N 26	Intervention group 1 N 17	Intervention group 2 N 21	<i>p</i> -Value
	N = 64			
Age (Mean ±SD)	80.73 ±5.15	80.47 ±5.33	78.24 ±4.43	<i>P</i> = ns
Education (Mean ±SD)	9.38 ±4.03	8.71 ±4.27	8.95 ±4.50	<i>P</i> = ns
Gender (F/M)	15/11	13/4	12/9	<i>P</i> = ns
Principal diagnosis (MCI/MD)	20/6	11/6	14/7	<i>P</i> = ns
Body Mass Index (Mean ±SD)	23.87 ±2.62	24.81 ±5.28	24.84 ±3.26	<i>P</i> = ns
N. Comorbidity	1.85 ±1.01	1.88 ±1.27	2.10 ±1.14	<i>P</i> = ns

Table 12. Baseline characteristics and between group differences for patients of the Italian pilot

Descriptive statistics, Swedish pilot

Forty-nine patients completed the protocol at the date of 30th of April 2018 in the Swedish pilot site and their results have been used for this preliminary analysis. Table 13 shows descriptive statistics for these patients at baseline. The number of patients is not well balanced across the three groups at the moment, with only 5 patients in the Control group, and 23 and 21 patients in the Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2 respectively. Considering the very low number of patients in the control group, with respect to the intervention groups, in the computation of differences for baseline characteristics Control group has been excluded.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 23	Intervention group 2 N 21	<i>p</i> -Value*
	N = 49			
Age (Mean ±SD)	71.40 ±2.88	74.35 ±7.94	74.05 ±5.37	<i>P</i> = ns
Education (Mean ±SD)	11.40 ±2.51	10.52 ±2.41	11.71 ±3.08	<i>P</i> = ns
Gender (F/M)	2/3	11/12	10/11	<i>P</i> = ns
Principal diagnosis (MCI/MD)	4/1	20/3	18/3	<i>P</i> = ns
Body Mass Index (Mean ±SD)	24.81 ±1.75	25.41 ±4.05	26.86 ±3.67	<i>P</i> = ns
N. Comorbidity	1.40 ±0.55	1.57 ±1.16	1.05 ±1.07	<i>P</i> = ns

Table 13. Baseline characteristics and between group differences for patients of the Swedish pilot.

**P* values refers just to confrontations between Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2.

The participants of the two intervention groups did not differ for age, years of education, gender (F/M) and principal diagnosis (MCI/MD), which were the variable used to stratify the patients in the three groups at randomization. Moreover, no differences were present among the two intervention groups for mean Body Mass Index and mean number of comorbidity.

Descriptive statistics, Israeli pilot

Thirteen patients completed the protocol at the date of 30th of April 2018 in the Israeli pilot site. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol and their unbalanced distribution across the three groups (1 patient in the Control group, 4 patients in the Intervention group 1 and 8 patients in the Intervention group 2), the data of these participants have been used just for the analyses computed for all sites combined. No further analyses have been computed on this set of data at this stage. Table 14 shows descriptive statistics for the patients at baseline.

	Control group N 1	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 8	<i>p</i> -Value
		N = 13		
Age (Mean ±SD)	73	76.50 ±4.12	75.0 ±3.59	
Education(Mean ±SD)	8	14.75 ±2.06	13.75 ±1.98	
Gender (F/M)	1/0	2/2	5/3	
Principal diagnosis (MCI/MD)	1/0	4/0	8/0	
Body Mass Index (Mean ±SD)	27.77	28.25 ±1.50	27.37 ±1.92	
N. Comorbidity	NA	NA	NA	

Table 14. Baseline characteristics for patients of the Israeli pilot. NA = Not available

Descriptive statistics, Spanish pilot

Twelve patients completed the protocol at the date of 30th of April 2018 in the Spanish pilot site. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol (5 patients in the Control group, 4 patients in the Intervention group 1 and 3 patients in the Intervention group 2), the data of these participants have been used just for the analyses computed for all sites combined. No further analyses have been computed on this set of data at this stage. Table 15 shows descriptive statistics for the patients at baseline.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 3	p-Value
	N = 12			
Age (Mean ±SD)	73.20 ±4.82	76.50 ±3.32	78.0 ±6.24	
Education (Mean ±SD)	9.20 ±5.72	8.25 ±6.95	9.33 ±4.51	
Gender (F/M)	3/2	2/2	2/1	
Principal diagnosis (MCI/MD)	5/0	4/0	3/0	
Body Mass Index (Mean ±SD)	23.35 ±2.11	23.89 ±2.81	25.87 ±2.19	
N. Comorbidity	3.40 ±0.89	3.75 ±2.99	2.67 ±0.58	

Table 15. Baseline characteristics for patients of the Spanish pilot.

5.1.2 Cognitive performance

5.1.2.1 Cognitive performance, all sites combined

Table 16 shows the baseline scores for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups. The three groups did not differ for MMSE and CDT mean scores.

	Control group N 37	Intervention group 1 N 48	Intervention group 2 N 53	p-Value
	N = 138			
MMSE (Mean ±SD)	26.35 ±2.83	26.88 ±2.65	27.23 ±2.41	<i>P</i> = ns
CDT (Mean ±SD)	3.65 ±1.34	3.98 ± 1.19	4.11 ±1.20	<i>P</i> = ns

Table 16. Mean scores for cognitive outcome variables at baseline. All pilots combined

Table 17 shows the mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of participants. The screening of the outcome variables data revealed a non-normal distribution at the Shapiro-Wilk's test ($P < 0.001$ for all variables), therefore a non-parametric approach has been used in the analyses both for all pilot combined and each single pilot site for which analyses have been computed (Italy and Sweden, see below). The computation of a Kruskal-Wallis H test (non-parametric analysis of variance) does not revealed any difference among the three groups for MMSE and CDT CSs (respectively $H = 2.59$, $P = 0.27$ and $H = 0.66$, $P = 0.72$), and this suggest that the intervention had no effect on cognitive performance (see figure 10).

	Control group N 37	Intervention group 1 N 48	Intervention group 2 N 53	p-Value
N = 138				
MMSE (Mean \pm SD)	-0.47 \pm 2.18	-0.13 \pm 2.46	-0.37 \pm 2.08	<i>P</i> = ns
CDT (Mean \pm SD)	-0.06 \pm 1.04	0.04 \pm 0.97	-0.17 \pm 1.13	<i>P</i> = ns

Table 17. Mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables. All pilots combined.

Figure 10. Mean CSs for cognitive outcome variables. Error bars: 95% CI. All pilot combined.

5.1.2.2 Cognitive performance, Italian site

Table 18 shows the baseline scores for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Italian pilot. The three groups did not differ for MMSE and CDT mean scores.

	Control group N 26	Intervention group 1 N 17	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value
	N = 64			
MMSE (Mean \pm SD)	26.0 \pm 2.99	24.94 \pm 3.31	26.19 \pm 3.09	P = ns
CDT (Mean \pm SD)	3.31 \pm 1.26	3.12 \pm 1.22	3.05 \pm 1.20	P = ns

Table 18. Mean scores for cognitive outcome variables at baseline. Italian pilot.

Table 19 shows the mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Italian participants. The computation of a Kruskal-Wallis H test (non-parametric analysis of variance) does not revealed any difference among the three groups for MMSE and CDT CSs (respectively H = 3.97, P = 0.14, and H = 0.29, P = 0.86). The result suggests that the intervention had no effect on cognitive performance.

	Control group N 26	Intervention group 1 N 17	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value
	N = 64			
MMSE (Mean \pm SE)	-0.62 \pm 2.47	-0.29 \pm 3.58	-0.90 \pm 2.12	P = ns
CDT (Mean \pm SE)	-0.08 \pm 1.06	-0.18 \pm 1.07	-0.05 \pm 1.63	P = ns

Table 19. Mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables. Italian pilot.

5.1.2.3 Cognitive performance, Swedish site

Table 20 shows the baseline scores for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Swedish pilot. Considering the very low number of patients in the control group, with respect to the intervention groups, in the computation of differences for baseline characteristics Control group has been excluded. The two intervention groups did not differ for MMSE and CDT mean scores.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 23	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value*
	N = 49			
MMSE (Mean \pm SD)	28.60 \pm 2.19	28.17 \pm 1.30	28.29 \pm 1.35	P = ns
CDT (Mean \pm SD)	4.20 \pm 1.79	4.65 \pm 0.83	4.90 \pm 0.30	P = ns

Table 20. Mean scores for cognitive outcome variables at baseline. Swedish pilot.

*P values refers just to confrontations between Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2.

Table 21 shows the mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Swedish participants. The analysis, performed using Mann-Whitney U test, does not revealed any difference between the two intervention groups for MMSE and CDT CSs (respectively $U = 220, P = 0.60$, and $U = 189, P = 0.08$). The result suggests that, at the moment and mainly for the two intervention groups, no significant difference emerged in cognitive performance. Since for Control group just five patients were present in the analysis, it will be needed to have more balanced groups to obtain more interpretable results.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 23	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value*
	N = 49			
MMSE (Mean \pm SE)	-0.60 \pm 1.14	0.04 \pm 1.58	0.48 \pm 1.94	$P = ns$
CDT (Mean \pm SE)	0.40 \pm 0.89	0.13 \pm 0.69	-0.29 \pm 0.64	$P = ns$

Table 21. Mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables. Swedish pilot.

**P-values refers just to confrontations between Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2.*

5.1.2.4 Cognitive performance, Israeli site

Table 22 shows the baseline scores for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Israeli pilot. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol and their unbalanced distribution across the three groups the data of these participants has not been separately analysed at this stage.

	Control group N 1	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 8	p-Value
	N = 13			
MMSE (Mean \pm SD)	24	28.25 \pm 1.50	27.37 \pm 1.92	
CDT (Mean \pm SD)	5	4.0 \pm 0.82	4.75 \pm 0.46	

Table 22. Mean scores for cognitive outcome variables at baseline. Israeli pilot.

Table 23 shows the mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Israeli participants. No analyses have been performed at this stage.

	Control group N 1	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 8	p-Value
	N = 13			
MMSE (Mean ±SE)	1	0 ±1.41	-0.75±1.91	
CDT (Mean ±SE)	-1	0±1.63	-0.25±0.71	

Table 23. Mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables. Israeli pilot.

5.1.2.5 Cognitive performance, Spanish site

Table 24 shows the baseline scores for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Spanish pilot. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol the data of these participants has not been separately analysed at this stage.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 3	p-Value
	N = 12			
MMSE (Mean ±SD)	26.40 ±1.67	26.25 ±0.50	26.67 ±0.58	
CDT (Mean ±SD)	4.60 ±0.55	3.75 ± 0.96	4.33 ±1.15	

Table 24. Mean scores for cognitive outcome variables at baseline. Spanish pilot.

Table 25 shows the mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables in the three groups of the Spanish participants. No analyses have been performed at this stage.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 3	p-Value
	N = 12			
MMSE (Mean ±SE)	0.25 ±1,26	-1 ±1.41	-2±1.41	
CDT (Mean ±SE)	-0.25 ±1,26	1±1.41	0±0	

Table 25. Mean CSs for the cognitive outcome variables. Spanish pilot.

5.1.2.6 Cognitive performance, preliminary discussion of results

The results of the analyses performed on the cognitive data, at this stage, did not show any effect of the intervention for these variables both for all pilots combined and for the two pilots that have the large number of patients that completed the intervention (Italy and Sweden).

In the present study, a specific cognitive intervention was delivered to patients of the Intervention group 2 through a computer-based program. According to the definition proposed by Woods and colleagues (2012), cognitive interventions could be organized in three different categories: *Cognitive stimulation*, which is aimed at engage patients in a range of activities and discussions aimed at general enhancement of cognitive and social functioning; *Cognitive training*, that is a guided practice on a set of standard tasks designed to reflect particular cognitive functions; *Cognitive rehabilitation*, that is an individualized approach where personally relevant goals are identified and the therapist works with the person and his or her family to devise strategies to address these. The characteristics of our computer-based cognitive intervention adapt well to the second one of the cited categories: *Cognitive training* interventions.

In a recent review of psychosocial interventions for elderly people with cognitive impairment, programs based on cognitive training did not resulted associated to significant improvements in general cognitive outcomes (McDermott et al. 2018). Whereas, promising moderate effects on cognition emerged for computer-based cognitive interventions which incorporate cognitive recreation, cognitive rehabilitation, cognitive stimulation and cognitive training (Garcia-Casal et al. 2017). Our results, at this stage, are in line with this recent observation. Further useful insights on this topic emerge from considerations proposed by Lampit and colleagues (2015). After a careful analysis of the several studies on computer-based cognitive training in older adults with and without cognitive impairment, they suggest that the evidence for this kind of interventions supports group-based computerized cognitive training for older adults of at least 30 minutes per session one to three times per week. According to their results, this ought to be the recommended “prescription”. The main difference between the reported intervention scheme and what has been done in the DECI study during cognitive training activities is related to the physical and social context where the intervention has been delivered. In the DECI case, patients worked at home with the only support of their caregivers, if needed. Whereas according to Lampit and colleagues the intervention should be delivered in a group format. The implementation of a protocol with group-based computerized cognitive training was out of the scope of DECI. If the final results on all patients enrolled in our study will confirm the absence of effect on global cognitive performance, for future research or clinical application of intervention models similar to DECI, will be useful to consider the integration in the patient platform multifunctional computer-based cognitive interventions with not only cognitive training programs but also cognitive stimulation and cognitive rehabilitation activities, or, as alternative, considering the group format to delivery computer-based cognitive training.

5.1.3 Autonomy in daily life

5.1.3.1 Autonomy in daily life, all sites combined

Table 26 shows the baseline scores for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups. The three groups did not differ for B-ADL mean scores, whereas a difference emerged between Control Group and Intervention Group 1 for mean I-ADL score (5.97 ± 2.15 and 7.21 ± 1.62 respectively, $P < 0.01$). However, this difference is not expected to affect the analysis of outcome, because the computation of the CSs (see section 4.1.1) is a within subjects procedure so that each patient operates as a control of her/himself.

	Control group N 37	Intervention group 1 N 48	Intervention group 2 N 53	p-Value
N = 138				
B-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	5.86 \pm 0.42	5.81 \pm 0.45	5.85 \pm 0.36	$P = ns$
I-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	5.97 \pm 2.15*	7.21 \pm 1.62*	6.73 \pm 2.22	* $P < .01$

Table 26. Mean scores for B-ADL and I-ADL variables at baseline. All pilots combined.

Table 27 shows the mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of participants. The screening of the outcome variables data revealed a non-normal distribution at the Shapiro-Wilk's test ($P < 0.001$ for all variables), therefore a non-parametric approach has been used in the analyses. The computation of a Kruskal-Wallis H test (non-parametric analysis of variance) revealed a significant difference among the three groups for B-ADL CSs ($H = 9.98$, $P = 0.007$). Post hoc comparisons (see Figure 11), performed by Mann-Whitney U test, show a significant difference between Intervention group 2 and Control group ($U = 684$, $P = 0.002$), and between Intervention group 2 and Intervention group 1 ($U = 1004$, $P = 0.027$). No difference emerged between Intervention group 1 and Control group ($U = 741$, $P = 0.27$). The results suggest that, at this stage, patients of the Intervention group 2, after 6 months of intervention with all the functionalities of the DECI protocol, have a more stable performance in basic activity of daily life with respect to the other groups of participants.

	Control group N 37	Intervention group 1 N 48	Intervention group 2 N 53	p-Value
N = 138				
B-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	-0.33 \pm 0.79	-0.28 \pm 0.89	0 \pm 0.35	$P = 0.007$
I-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	-0.08 \pm 1	-0.20 \pm 1.13	0 \pm 0.98	$P = ns$

Table 27. Mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables. All pilots combined.

Figure 11. Mean CSs for autonomy outcome variables. Error bars: 95% CI. All pilot combined.

5.1.3.2 Autonomy in daily life, Italian Pilot

Table 28 shows the baseline scores for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Italian pilot. The three groups did not differ for B-ADL and I-ADL mean scores.

	Control group N 26	Intervention group 1 N 17	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value
N = 64				
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	5.85 ±0.46	5.53 ±0.62	5.67 ±0.48	P = ns
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	5.42 ±2.23	6.18 ±2.30	5.57 ±2.73	P = ns

Table 28. Mean scores for B-ADL and I-ADL variables at baseline. Italian pilot.

Table 29 shows the mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of participants of the Italian pilot. The computation of a Kruskal-Wallis H test (non-parametric analysis of variance) revealed a significant difference among the three groups for B-ADL CSs ($H = 6.78, P = 0.034$). Post hoc comparisons, performed by Mann-Whitney U test, show a significant difference between Intervention group 2 and Control group (U

= 177, $P = 0.007$). No difference emerged between Intervention group 2 and Intervention group 1 ($U = 148,5$, $P = 0.19$), and between Intervention group 1 and Control group ($U = 187$, $P = 0.32$). The results suggest that patients of the Intervention group 2, after 6 months of intervention, have a more stable performance in basic activity of daily life, with respect to the Control group.

	Control group N 26	Intervention group 1 N 17	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value
	N = 64			
B-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	-0.50 \pm 0.86	-0.41 \pm 1.06	-0.05 \pm 0.50	$P = 0.034$
I-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	-0.08 \pm 1.09	-0.29 \pm 1.36	0 \pm 1.26	$P = ns$

Table 29. Mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables. Italian pilot.

5.1.3.3 Autonomy in daily life, Swedish Pilot

Table 30 shows the baseline scores for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Swedish pilot. Considering the very low number of patients in the control group, with respect to the intervention groups, in the computation of differences for baseline characteristics Control group has been excluded. The Intervention group 1 and the Intervention group 2 did not differ for B-ADL (no statistics have been computed for absence of variability in the data) and for I-ADL mean scores.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 23	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value*
	N = 49			
B-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	6 \pm 0	6 \pm 0	6 \pm 0	
I-ADL (Mean \pm SD)	7.80 \pm 0.45	7.96 \pm 0.21	8 \pm 0	$P = ns$

Table 30. Mean scores for B-ADL and I-ADL variables at baseline. Swedish pilot.

**P values refers just to confrontations between Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2.*

Table 31 shows the mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of participants of the Swedish pilot. The data for B-ADL CSs show a total absence of variability. In fact, all patients across the three groups received the maximum possible score both at T0 and T1. This result suggest that no difference is present among participants for this variable. Moreover, the computation of Mann-Whitney U test for I-ADL CSs obtained from Intervention group 2 and intervention group 1 did not show any significant difference ($U = 220$, $P = 0.16$). The results suggest that patients of the two

Intervention groups did not have significant modification of autonomy after the intervention.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 23	Intervention group 2 N 21	p-Value*
	N = 49			
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	0 ±0	0±0	0 ±0	
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	0.20 ±0.45	0.04 ±0.21	-0.05 ± 0.22	<i>P = ns</i>

Table 31. Mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables. Swedish pilot.

**P values refers just to confrontations between Intervention group 1 and Intervention group 2.*

5.1.3.4 Autonomy in daily life, Israeli Pilot

Table 32 shows the baseline scores for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Israeli pilot. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol and their unbalanced distribution across the three groups the data of these participants has not been separately analysed at this stage.

	Control group N 1	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 8	p-Value
	N = 13			
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	6	5.75 ±0.50	5.86 ±0.38	
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	6	7.50 ±0.58	6.29 ±2.36	

Table 32. Mean scores for B-ADL and I-ADL variables at baseline. Israeli pilot.

Table 33 shows the mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Israeli participants. No analyses have been performed at this stage. The only relevant point that emerges from the observation of the raw data of the two intervention groups is a tendency to a better outcome in patients of the intervention group 2, and this is in line with what has been observed in the all data combined and in the Italian pilot. The analyses on the complete dataset will allow to confirm or reject this first tendency of the data.

	Control group N 1	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 8	p-Value
N = 49				
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	0	-1.25±1.89	0.14±0.38	
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	0	-1.25 ±2.63	0.43 ± 1.27	

Table 33. Mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables. Israeli pilot.

5.1.3.5 Autonomy in daily life, Spanish Pilot

Table 34 shows the baseline scores for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Spanish pilot. Considering the low number of patients that completed the protocol and the unbalanced distribution of them across the three groups the data of these participants has not been separately analysed at this stage.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 3	p-Value
N = 12				
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	5.80 ±0.45	6.0 ±0	6.0 ±0	
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	7.0 ±1.73	7.0 ±1.41	7.0 ±1.73	

Table 34. Mean scores for B-ADL and I-ADL variables at baseline. Spanish pilot.

Table 35 shows the mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables in the three groups of the Spanish pilot. No analyses have been performed at this stage.

	Control group N 5	Intervention group 1 N 4	Intervention group 2 N 3	p-Value
N = 12				
B-ADL (Mean ±SD)	0.25 ±0.50	-0.50±0.71	0 ±0	
I-ADL (Mean ±SD)	-0.50 ±1.00	0 ±0	-1.00 ± 1.41	

Table 35. Mean CSs for the autonomy outcome variables. Israeli pilot.

5.1.3.6 Autonomy in daily life, preliminary discussion of results

The results of the analyses performed on the autonomy data, at this stage, shown an effect of the complete intervention (Organizational model combined with computer-based cognitive training and computer-based physical activity) in reducing the worsening of B-ADL performance over time. The analysis on patients of all pilots combined reveals that participants enrolled in Intervention group 2 presented a stable condition at B-ADL questionnaire, whereas patients of Control group and of Intervention group 1 (only organizational model) shown a slight decrement. Looking specifically at the results of the two pilot sites that have the large number of patients that completed the intervention (Italy and Sweden), what can be seen is that the effect emerged in all pilots combined is present, and slightly more pronounced, in the Italian participant and disappeared in the Swedish one. Considering that Swedish patients recollected until now were all stable at the B-ADL questionnaire at T1, so they added no variability in the aggregated data, the result emerged for all pilots combined are probably “dragged” from the results obtained by Italian patients.

A Cochrane systematic review on cognitive interventions on elderly people suffering from cognitive impairment suggests that cognitive training have no effect on B-ADL (Bahar-Fuchs et al. 2013). On the other hand, from some previous research and from a recent review, positive results emerged about improvement of B-ADL after physical interventions across different stages of dementia (Blankevoort et al., 2010; McDermott et al. 2018). A further review of several randomized controlled trials (Rao et al., 2014) found that the longer the duration of exercise had a statistically significant moderate effect size at the outcome. All these evidences combined, even though not totally conclusive at the moment due to the low number of randomized controlled trials performed and the heterogeneity of the motor protocol implemented (McDermott et al. 2018), suggest that the effect on B-ADL emerged in our patients could dependent on physical activity intervention.

But why an effect emerged for BADL? The reason could be mainly related to demographic characteristics of respondent participants. As shown, Italian patients are, until now, the only group where the effect is present. Considering that, among the four pilot sites, the Italian participants are the older one (mean age of about 80) and those with the higher rate of Mild dementia, they are probably more exposed to frailty and disability and so more prone to change in BADL activities over time (Arrighi et al. 2013). As mentioned above, there are evidences that physical activity, and not the cognitive one, can impact on BADL measures, so it is possible that the effect of intervention, in terms of reduced decrement of BADL over time, emerged in the participants’ population more at risk for BADL decrement, that is, the more elderly and cognitive impaired one. If the results of the study will be similar at the end of data recollection, a further analysis to confirm this hypothesis will be possible analysing in a separate way MCI and MD patients.

Another question suggested from these results is why an effect emerged for BADL and not for IADL, as could be more expected in patients with less severe cognitive impairment as MCI. As discussed in the section dedicated to cognitive outcomes, no difference has been detected after the intervention on global cognition. IADL consist of activities with high rate of cognition involved (e.g. preparing meals, handling the finances, driving or using public transportation), in particular executive functions (Marshall et al. 2011). The absence of effect, until now, on global cognition could be the reason why no effect emerged not only on cognitive measures but also on IADL.

Conclusions

The findings emerged until now on clinical outcomes measures suggest that patients participating in the complete intervention group present more stability in BADL over time. This result could be interpreted as a benefit from physical activity program. No effect on global cognition has been found at this stage. If these data will be confirmed at the end of the study, and further similar research works will be in line with our results, ICT based intervention models like DECI could be a promising approach to delay BADL worsening in elderly people at the first stages of cognitive impairment.

5.1.4 Quality of Life

5.1.4.1 Quality of Life results for all pilots combined

Patient characteristics

The analysed sample of all pilots combined consisted of 124 participants with mean age 77.25 ± 6.04 years old, with 58.06% female (mean age 78.26 ± 5.93) and 41.94% male (mean 75.85 ± 5.96). In the combined sample, 31 people belonged to control group (25%), 43 people to Group 1 (34.68%), and 50 people to Group 2 (40.32%). In the combined Control group, 80,65% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 19,35% Mild dementia. In the combined Group 1, 79,07% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 20,93% Mild dementia. In the combined Group 2, 82% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 18% Mild dementia. The table 36 represents characteristics of each patient group.

	Age		Gender		ICTLiteracy				LivingSituation		
	Mean	Standard Deviation	F Row N %	M Row N %	Basic user Row N %	Experienced user Row N %	Intermediate user Row N %	No experience Row N %	Alone Row N %	With another elderly Row N %	With Child/Younger Family Row N %
Control Group	79.48	5.46	58.06%	41.94%	6.45%	22.58%	35.48%	35.48%	35.48%	54.84%	9.68%
Group 1	77.30	6.97	60.47%	39.53%	4.65%	60.47%	11.63%	23.26%	41.86%	51.16%	6.98%
Group 2	75.82	5.14	56.00%	44.00%	4.00%	58.00%	22.00%	16.00%	32.00%	64.00%	4.00%

Table 36. Characteristics of each group (%) all pilots combined

EQ-5D-5L dimensions

The following figure represents proportions of users in 'problems' or 'no problem' state in EQ-5D dimensions at baseline (T0) and after 6 months of intervention (T1) in every patient group.

Figure 12- Dichotomous dimension (%) All countries combined

There is not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in different dimensions in most of the results:

- Mobility: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.045$, $p=0.832$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.205$, $p=0.651$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=1.253$, $p=0.263$.
- Self-care: Group 2: Fisher's exact test $p=1$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.281$, $p=0.596$ Control group: Fisher's exact test $p=0.707$.
- Usual activity: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.508$, $p=0.476$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.195$, $p=0.659$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=0.876$, $p=0.349$.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.372$, $p=0.542$; Group 1: $\chi^2(0.054)=0$, $p=0.816$. Control group: $\chi^2(1)=4.168$, $p=0.041$.
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.360$, $p=0.548$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=1.675$, $p=0.196$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=1.613$, $p=0.204$.

Based on the results, the difference of proportions between baseline and follow-up was inconclusive in two intervention groups. Statistical significance of an increased proportion of people reporting more 'problems' after six months was observed in the Control group in Pain/discomfort dimension.

However, from the descriptive point of view, after 6 months, proportion of patients who have reported 'no problem' in different dimensions were the following:

- Mobility: Group 2: decreased by 2%; Group 1: decreased by 4,65%; Control group: decreased by 12,90%.
- Self-care: Group 2: decreased by 2%; Group 1: increased by 4,65%; Control group: decreased by 3,23%.
- Usual activity: Group 2: increased by 4%; Group 1: increased by 2,33%; Control group: decreased by 3,23%.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: decreased by 6%; Group 1: increased by 2,33%; Control group: decreased by 25,81%.
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: increased by 10%; Group 1: increased by 13,95%; Control group: increased by 9,68%.

For the sample analysed, differential changes in the proportion of people reporting 'no problems' in Pain/discomfort showed the best result in Group 1. The biggest increase which was also statistically significant was in 'problems' of pain/discomfort showing an increase by 25,81% in the Control group, while the intervention groups had a smaller change (not statistically significant). For most of the results, the difference of proportions between baseline and follow-up was inconclusive.

EQ-5D VAS

Control group				
N=31	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	75	75.16	17.72	3.18
25 th percentile	70			
75 th percentile	90			
Follow-up	75.00	70.97	18.99	3.41
25 th percentile	50			
75 th percentile	85.00			
Group 1				
N=43	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	80	74.07	18.36	2.80
25 th percentile	65			
75 th percentile	90			
Follow-up	80	71.16	20.26	3.09
25 th percentile	55			
75 th percentile	90			
Group 2				
N=50	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	80	74.03	18.02	2.55
25 th percentile	60			
75 th percentile	87.25			
Follow-up	80.00	71.98	18.85	2.67
25 th percentile	60			
75 th percentile	81.25			

Table 37. EQ-5D VAS Scale Descriptive statistics (all countries combined)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and after 6 months of intervention: Group 2: $p=0.580$; Group 1: $p=0.488$; Control group: $p=0.372$. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores decreased indicating worse 'health today' in all groups: decrease by 5.58% in Control group, 3.92% in Group 1, and 2.77% in Group 2. The decrease was highest in the Control group, and the lowest in the Group 2. However, the result was not statistically significant.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups showed that mean changes between baseline and follow-up were not statistically significant between the groups ($p=1$).

EQ-5D index

Control group				
N=31	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.857	0.85606	0.16171	0.02904
25 th percentile	0.751			
75 th percentile	1			
Follow-up	0.887	0.75742	0.28549	0.05128
25 th percentile	0.648			
75 th percentile	0.914			
Group 1				
N=43	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.787	0.7676	0.16978	0.02589
25 th percentile	0.687			
75 th percentile	0.859			
Follow-up	0.802	0.81242	0.14201	0.02166
25 th percentile	0.68			
75 th percentile	1			
Group 2				
N=50	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.824	0.8229	0.13541	0.01915
25 th percentile	0.756			
75 th percentile	0.914			
Follow-up	0.8435	0.81696	0.15203	0.0215
25 th percentile	0.737			
75 th percentile	0.91			

Table 38. EQ-5D Index Value descriptive statistics (all countries combined)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D Index value between baseline and after 6 months of intervention: Group 2: $p=0.837$; Group 1: $p=0.188$; Control group: $p=0.099$. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores decreased in two groups: the highest decrease by 11.52% in Control group, and 0.72% in Group 2. Increase was observed in Group 1 by 5.84%.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups showed that mean changes between baseline and follow-up were statistically significant between the Control group and Group 1 ($p=0.008$). Other groups' comparisons did not yield significant results: Control group with Group 2 ($p=0.131$), and Group 1 and Group 2 ($p=0.666$).

QALY for all patient groups combined is:

- Group 2: mean QALY = -0.003 ± 0.069
- Group 1: mean QALY = 0.022 ± 0.077
- Control group: QALY = -0.049 ± 0.154

Summary

<i>Changes in proportions reporting 'no problem' between T0 and T1</i>			
Dimensions	Control group	Group 1	Group 2
Mobility	-12,9%	-4,65%	-2%
Self-care	-3,23%	4,65%	-2%
Usual Activity	-3,23%	2,33%	4%
Pain/Discomfort	-25,81%	2,33%	-6%
Anxiety/Depression	9,68%	13,95%	10%
<i>Changes in mean values between T0 and T1</i>			
	Control group	Group 1	Group 2
VAS scale	-5,58	-3,92	-2,77
Index Value	-11,52	5,84	-0,72

Table 39. EQ-5D summary (all countries combined)

The majority of positive changes in proportions of people reporting 'no problem' in EQ-5D dimensions between baseline and follow-up were observed in Group 1 from the descriptive statistics point of view. However, all the Group 1 results were statistically insignificant. Comparing the negative changes in proportions of people reporting 'no problem' in EQ-5D dimensions between baseline and follow-up stages indicating a reduced proportion in people reporting a declined health state, Group 2 reported smaller negative differences than other groups. However, all the Group 2 results were statistically insignificant. Control group reported highest decreases in the dimensions, with only Pain/Discomfort result being statistically significant.

5.1.4.2 Italian Quality of Life results

Patient characteristics

Italian sample consisted of 64 participants with mean age 79.69 ± 5.02 years, with 62.50% female (mean age 80.37 ± 4.31) and 37.50% male (mean age 78.58 ± 5.95). In Control group, 76,92% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 23,08% Mild dementia. In Group 1, 64,71% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 35,29% Mild dementia. In Group 2, 66,67% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 33,33% Mild dementia. However, the only control variable used in the analysis was the patient group. In Italy, 26 people belonged to control

group (40.60%), 17 people to Group 1 (26.60%), and 21 people to Group 2 (32.80%). The table 40 represents characteristics of each patient group.

	Gender		Age		ICTLiteracy				LivingSituation		
	F N %	M N %	Mean	SD.	No experience N %	Intermedi ate user N %	Experienced user N %	Basic user N %	Alone N %	With another elderly N %	Child/Younger Family N %
Control Group	57.69%	42.31%	80.54	5.10	38.46%	34.62%	19.23%	7.69%	34.62%	53.85%	11.54%
Group 1	76.47%	23.53%	80.41	5.30	47.06%	23.53%	17.65%	11.76%	52.94%	29.41%	17.65%
Group 2	57.14%	42.86%	78.05	4.49	38.10%	38.10%	19.05%	4.76%	33.33%	61.90%	4.76%

Table 40. Characteristics of each group (%) Italy

EQ-5D-5L dimensions

The following figure (Figure 13) represents proportion of users in 'problems' or 'no problem' state in EQ-5D dimensions at baseline and after 6 months of intervention in every patient group.

Figure 13 - Dichotomous dimension (%) Italy

There is not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in different dimensions in most of the results:

- Mobility: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=1.109$, $p=0.292$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.125$, $p=0.724$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=2.185$, $p=0.139$.
- Self-care: Group 2: Fisher's exact test $p=1$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.567$, $p=0.452$; Control group: Fisher's exact test $p=0.703$.
- Usual activity: Group 2: Fisher's exact test $p=0.606$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.515$, $p=0.473$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=0.433$, $p=0.510$.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.095$, $p=0.758$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0$, $p=1$. Control group: $\chi^2(1)=4.923$, $p=0.027$
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.096$, $p=0.757$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.472$, $p=0.492$; Control group: $\chi^2(1)=0.693$, $p=0.405$.

Based on the results, the difference of proportions between baseline and follow-up was inconclusive in two intervention groups, with a statistical significance of an increased proportion of people reporting more 'problems' after six months was observed in the Control group in Pain/discomfort dimension.

However, from the descriptive point of view, after 6 months, proportion of patients who have reported 'no problem' in different dimensions were the following:

- Mobility: Group 2: increased by 14,28%; Group 1: increased by 5,89%; Control group: decreased by 19,23%.
- Self-care: Group 2: decreased by 4,76%; Group 1: increased by 11,76%; Control group: decreased by 7,70%.
- Usual activity: Group 2: increased by 9,52%; Group 1: increased by 11,76%; Control group: decreased by 7,69%.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: decreased by 4,76%; Group 1: no change; Control group: decreased by 30,77%.
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: increased by 4,76%; Group 1: increased by 11,76%; Control group: increased by 11,54%.

For the sample analysed, differential changes in the proportion of people reporting 'no problems' showed the best result in Group 1 (not statistically significant). The biggest increase which was also statistically significant was in 'problems' of pain/discomfort showing an increase of proportion by 30,77% in the Control group, while the intervention groups had a smaller change or no change (not statistically significant). For most of the results, the difference of proportions between baseline and follow-up was inconclusive.

EQ-5D VAS

Control group				
N=26	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	80	77.69	17.56	3.44
25 th percentile	70			
75 th percentile	91,25			
Follow-up	77.50	71.92	19.55	3.83
25 th percentile	50			
75 th percentile	90			
Group 1				
N=17	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	75	73.24	20.31	4.92
25 th percentile	60			
75 th percentile	90			
Follow-up	70	65.59	23.84	5.78
25 th percentile	43			
75 th percentile	85			
Group 2				
N=21	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	80	75.48	19.29	4.21
25 th percentile	60			
75 th percentile	92			
Follow-up	70	65.24	18.47	4.03
25 th percentile	50			
75 th percentile	80			

Table 41. EQ-5D VAS Scale Descriptive statistics (Italy)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and follow-up stages: Group 2: $p=0.087$; Group 1: $p=0.322$; Control group: $p=0.268$. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores decreased in all groups: decrease by 7.42% in Control group, 10.44% in Group 1, and 13.5% in Group 2. Descriptively, this indicates a lower 'health today' reported after 6 months. However, the result is not statistically significant.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups showed that mean changes between baseline and follow-up were not statistically significant between the groups ($p=1$).

EQ-5D index

Control group				
N=26	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.87200	0.86235	0.15889	0.03116
25 th percentile	0.72800			
75 th percentile	1			
Follow-up	0.81800	0.73238	0.30036	0.05890
25 th percentile	0.50600			
75 th percentile	0.88700			
Group 1				
N=17	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.78100	0.73206	0.19888	0.04823
25 th percentile	0.55100			
75 th percentile	0.79900			
Follow-up	0.80000	0.81147	0.15391	0.03733
25 th percentile	0.64000			
75 th percentile	1			
Group 2				
N=21	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.91000	0.87119	0.10494	0.02290
25 th percentile	0.71900			
75 th percentile	0.91000			
Follow-up	0.91000	0.84314	0.17511	0.03821
25 th percentile	0.73100			
75 th percentile	1			

Table 42. EQ-5D Index Value descriptive statistics (Italy)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D Index value between baseline and follow-up: Group 2: $p=0.533$; Group 1: $p=0.202$; Control group: $p=0.057$. However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores decreased in two groups: decrease by 15.07% in Control group, and 3.21% in Group 2. Increase was observed in Group 1 by 10.84%. However, the result is not statistically significant.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups showed that mean changes between baseline and follow-up were statistically significant between the Control group and Group 1 ($p=0.034$). Other groups' comparisons did not yield significant results: Control group with Group 2 ($p=0.543$), and Group 1 and Group 2 ($p=0.613$).

QALY for Italian patient groups is:

- Group 2: mean QALY = -0.014 ± 0.095
- Group 1: mean QALY = 0.0397 ± 0.103
- Control group: QALY = -0.064981 ± 0.162

5.1.4.3 Swedish Quality of Life result

Patient characteristics

Swedish sample for Quality of Life analysis included 39 participants with mean age 74.31 ± 6.86 . 48.72% participants were female of mean age 76.52 ± 7.68 years and 51.28% male of mean age 72.20 ± 5.09 years. In Control group, there were no patients included in the sample. In Group 1, 85% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 15% Mild dementia. In Group 2, 89,47% of the sample had MCI diagnosis, and 10,53% Mild dementia. However, the only control variable used in the analysis was the patient group. Patient proportions in different groups were the following: Group 2 comprised of 20 participants (51%) and Group 1 included 19 participants (49%). No control group participants had complete data of Quality of Life and were not included in the analysis.

	Gender		Age		ICTLiteracy			LivingSituation	
	F N %	M N %	Mean	SD.	No experience N %	Intermedi ate user N %	Experienced user N %	Alone N %	With another elderly N %
Control Group	0.00%	0.00%	N/A	N/A	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Group 1	50.00%	50.00%	75.00	8.10	5.00%	5.00%	90.00%	35.00%	65.00%
Group 2	47.37%	52.63%	73.58	5.38	0.00%	10.53%	89.47%	36.84%	63.16%

Table 43. Demographic data of each group (%) Sweden

EQ-5D-5L dimensions

The following chapters represent percentage of users in ‘problems’ or ‘no problem’ state in EQ-5D dimensions at baseline and after 6 months of intervention in every patient group.

Figure 14. Dichotomous dimension (%) Sweden

There is not enough evidence to suggest that there was a statistically significant change in proportions of people reporting different health states in different dimensions in most of the results:

- Mobility: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.117$, $p=0.732$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.125$, $p=0.723$.
- Self-care: No change.
- Usual activity: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.110$, $p=0.740$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.102$, $p=0.749$.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: Fisher's exact test, $p=1.00$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.476$, $p=0.490$.
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: $\chi^2(1)=0.00$, $p=1.00$; Group 1: $\chi^2(1)=0.902$, $p=0.342$.

Based on the results, the difference of proportions between baseline and follow-up was inconclusive in the two intervention groups.

However, from the descriptive point of view, after 6 months, proportion of patients who have reported 'no problem' in different dimensions were the following:

- Mobility: Group 2: decreased by 5,26%; Group 1: decreased by 5%.
- Self-care: no change.
- Usual activity: Group 2: decreased by 5,26%; Group 1: increased by 5%.
- Pain/discomfort: Group 2: decreased by 5,26%; Group 1: increased by 10%.
- Anxiety/depression: Group 2: no change; Group 1: increased by 15%.

For the sample analysed, differential changes in the proportion of people reporting 'no problems' showed the best result in Group 1 (not statistically significant).

EQ-5D VAS

Control group				
N=0	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
25 th percentile	N/A			
75 th percentile	N/A			
Follow-up	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
25 th percentile	N/A			
75 th percentile	N/A			
Group 1				
N=20	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	82.5	76.50	18.57	4.14
25 th percentile	66.25			
75 th percentile	90			
Follow-up	82.50	77.00	16.01	3.58
25 th percentile	65			
75 th percentile	90			
Group 2				
N=19	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	75	71.92	18.67	4.28
25 th percentile	60			
75 th percentile	87			
Follow-up	80	77.58	16.13	3.70
25 th percentile	75			
75 th percentile	85			

Table 44. EQ-5D VAS Scale Descriptive statistics (Sweden)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D VAS scores between baseline and follow-up: Group 2: $p=0.324$; Group 1: $p=0.928$.

However, from the descriptive point of view, mean scores increased by 0.65% in Group 1, and 7.86% in Group 2 indicating better 'health today' after 6 months. However, the result is not statistically significant.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups (Group 1 and Group 2) showed that changes between baseline and follow-up were not statistically significant between the groups ($p=0.106$).

EQ-5D index

Control group				
N= 0	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
25 th percentile	N/A			
75 th percentile	N/A			
Follow-up	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
25 th percentile	N/A			
75 th percentile	N/A			
Group 1				
N=20	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.78700	0.77680	0.15742	0.03520
25 th percentile	0.66900			
75 th percentile	0.85600			
Follow-up	0.82900	0.81670	0.13915	0.03112
25 th percentile	0.65500			
75 th percentile	0.85600			
Group 2				
N=19	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Baseline	0.78700	0.78016	0.11637	0.02670
25 th percentile	0.63300			
75 th percentile	0.79700			
Follow-up	0.78700	0.79600	0.09958	0.02285
25 th percentile	0.68800			
75 th percentile	0.85900			

Table 45. EQ-5D Index Value descriptive statistics (Sweden)

No statistically significant difference was found in mean EQ-5D Index value between baseline and follow-up: Group 2: $p=0.655$; Group 1: $p=0.401$. From the descriptive point of view, mean scores increased in two groups: increase by 5.14% in Group 1, and 2.03% in Group 2. However, the result is not statistically significant.

Bonferroni adjustment for pairwise comparisons between the patient groups (Group 1 and Group 2) showed that changes between baseline and follow-up were not statistically significant between the Group 1 and Group 2 ($p=0.410$).

QALY for Swedish patient groups is:

- Group 2: mean QALY = 0.0079 ± 0.039
- Group 1: mean QALY = 0.02 ± 0.050
- Control group: N/A

5.1.4.4 Spanish Quality of Life result

The sample of the Spanish pilot, consisting of 8 patients with full quality of life data, and when divided between different groups and different health states, was too low for the statistical analyses, and Chi-square test and Fisher's exact tests could not be calculated for the Spanish site. However, from the existing sample the QALYs were the following:

- Group 2: mean QALY = -0.006 ± 0.057
- Group 1: mean QALY = -0.0285 ± 0.040
- Control group: QALY = 0.0290 ± 0.076

5.1.4.5 Israeli Quality of Life result

The sample of the Israeli pilot, consisting of 13 patients with full quality of life data, and when divided between different groups and different health states, was too low for the statistical analyses, and Chi-square test and Fisher's exact tests could not be calculated for the Israeli site. However, from the existing sample the QALYs were the following:

- Group 2: mean QALY = 0.0009 ± 0.053
- Group 1: mean QALY = 0.0134 ± 0.068
- Control group: QALY = 0.445

5.1.4.6 Conclusion

The expected result was to have a stable or an increased Quality of Life for Group 2 and Group 1 patients. Group 2 mean index value was expected to be higher than for Intervention group 1 and Control group. Accordingly, Group 1 mean index value was expected to be higher than for Control group. For Control group patients, no change in quality of life index value was expected.

The expectation could be justified when data from all pilots was combined into a single sample. Comparison of mean changes in EQ-5D index values showed that the difference between Group 1 and Control group was statistically significant: Group 1 has improved the perceived overall health state (mean change = +5,84), while Control group had a deteriorated perceived health state (mean change = -11,52). The same result with statistical significance was observed in the Italian sample.

The expected results with statistical significance were also seen in Italy, when more people from the Control group sample started experiencing pain/discomfort during the 6 months of the study (increase of proportion of people by 30,77%). The differential differences in proportions of people experiencing pain were smaller in other groups (however, not statistically significant). Overall, for Italian sample, there are indications

that the Group 1 had an increase in quality of life. However, since the Group 1 patients have not received DECI ICT modules related to physical or cognitive training, it cannot be assumed that the change in pain/discomfort could be caused by DECI.

For Swedish sample, differential results showed almost consistent improvement in EQ-5D dimensions in Group 1. However, the results were not statistically significant.

Due to too small sample sizes, the Quality of Life analysis could not be performed for Israel and Spain.

5.1.5 Patient satisfaction

The following table presents the interview sample included in the analysis.

	Total	Israel	Italy	Spain	Sweden
Control Group	15	1	10	1	3
Intervention Group 1	16	4	9	0	3
Intervention Group 2	25	7	10	1	7
Total	56	12	29	2	13

Table 46. The number of interviews included in the analysis

Patient characteristics

Italian interview sample consisted of 29 participants with mean age 78.45 ± 5.70 years. 55.2% were female (mean age 79.94 ± 5.14) and 44.8% male (mean age 76.62 ± 6.02). In Italy, 10 people belonged to control group (34.48%), 31.03% to Group 1 (9 people), and 10 people to Group 2 (34.48%).

Swedish interview sample consisted of 13 participants with mean age 75.62 ± 7.03 years. 38.50% were female (mean age 78.00 ± 9.30) and 61.50% male (mean age 74.13 ± 5.36). In Sweden, 3 people belonged to Control group (23.08%), 3 people to Group 1 (23.08%), and 7 people to Group 2 (53.84%).

Israeli interview sample consisted of 12 participants with mean age 74.75 ± 3.60 years. 66.67% were female (mean age 74.13 ± 4.26) and 33.33% male (mean age 76.00 ± 1.41). In Israel, 1 person belonged to Control group (8.33%), 33.33% to Group 1 (4 people), and 58.34% people to Group 2 (7 people).

Spanish interview sample consisted of 2 participants with mean age 75.50 ± 6.36 years old, with 50% female (71 years old) and 50% male (80 years old). In Spain, 50% belonged to Control group (1 person) and 50% to Group 2 (1 person). There were no respondents in Group 1.

The most appreciated features of DECI care received

Group 2 – The most appreciated features of DECI care received

Overall: A majority of the patients in Group 2 have highlighted the contact with healthcare professionals as the most beneficial element of DECI. The received care was perceived as emphatic, professional and highly patient focused.

- Sweden: All the interviewed Group 2 patients in Sweden have emphasized the home visits as their primary favourite element of the received care. The patients described that the home visits removed stress and provided a comfortable platform for discussions with healthcare professionals. Features of a case manager role was mentioned by one patient who emphasized that such set-up had not just released the patient, but also the patient received a follow-up. Additionally, medical assessments performed at home were appreciated by most of the interviewees. Using ICT of DECI was seen as a proactive approach to self-care, and the patients felt empowered to take action to avoid disease progression with physical and cognitive exercising. A majority of the patients have expressed willingness to continue using similar technologies in the future.
- Italy: Majority of the interviewed Group 2 patients in Italy emphasized empathic elements of care, in particular they felt the healthcare professionals were serious, friendly, kind and humane. *“It doesn’t make me feel inferior and I go home calm”*.
- Israel: The interviewed Group 2 patients in Israel appreciated ICT solutions of the DECI model, as stated by one-third of the patients. Physical exercise program and Cognitive training program were mentioned among favourite elements of the received care. One patient also mentioned a possibility to get professional assistance with using the platform as a satisfying part of care.
- Spain: There was one respondent from the Group 2 in Spain. The patient has not explicated any likable elements about DECI care, and indicated a numeric evaluation of DECI saying “4 points out of 10 being very generous”.

Group 1 – The most appreciated features of DECI care received

Overall: Most Interviewees from Group 1 expressed similar perceptions as patients of Group 2. The care was perceived as well handled in the care system.

- Sweden: Home visits were appreciated by all participants, as they helped develop a good contact with healthcare professionals. Also, medical examination performed at patient homes have been emphasized by the Group 1 patients as favourite parts of DECI care. It should be noted that the Group 1 patients in Sweden have not received DECI ICT solutions.
- Italy: All but one Group 1 patients in Italy emphasized empathic elements of care, such as kindness and attention from healthcare professionals, as well as their

demonstrated competence. The limited scope of DECI platform provided was not mentioned by the patients.

- Israel: All Group 1 patients in Israel were mentioning different digital games that they are used to play. However, since this group has not been introduced to physical or cognitive activity programs, the mentioned digital games must have been found elsewhere on the market.

Control group – The most appreciated features of care received

Overall: The patients that received “care-as-usual” stated their appreciation of healthcare professionals.

- Sweden: All patients from Control group appreciated good interaction with healthcare professionals and reasonable waiting times. One patient mentioned memory exercises performed together with a nurse (e.g. re-telling a story). Most patients also were positive about the medical examination, including Lumbar puncture.
- Italy: With one exception, patients from Control group in Italy emphasized empathic and social elements of care, such as helpful and competent healthcare professionals providing good assistance. The overall functioning of the care system was also appreciated by one person. One person perceived the received care as ‘no treatment’.
- Spain: There was one respondent from the Control group in Spain, and the person expressed a positive outlook to the care received.

Less appreciated features of DECI care received

Group 2 – Less appreciated features of DECI care received

Overall: Less appreciated features in Group 2 were highly diversified between different pilots, however the ease of use and stability with provided ICT-solution was stressed as the most important by majority of the participants.

- Sweden: The Group 2 have mentioned unstable ICT functioning, and the ease of use issues, such as the buttons on the tablet not reacting to dry fingers. One patient would have appreciated more follow-up meetings with healthcare professionals, after the finished intervention.
- Italy: The group 2 patients have mostly related to the care-as-usual and referred to their overall experiences in the healthcare system. Hence, a majority of Group 2 patients have expressed disappointment in time delays when meeting the professionals and have perceived the issue as a lack of competence of professionals booking the medical examination or clinical visits. One patient also stated the discontinuity in contact with doctor as an experienced drawback.

- Israel: Most Group 2 patients have expressed issues in the ease of use; problems were experienced with starting the system, insensitivity of the buttons of the tablet, and some shapes in the cognitive exercise system were too small. Sometimes the Internet connection was unstable and the system was disconnected. One patient reflected that some physical exercises targeted at hand movements were too difficult, while two patients perceived the cognitive games as too easy and incompatible with their cognitive level. One patient has expressed that “Physical exercise was less fun”.
- Spain: There was one respondent from the Group 2 in Spain, and the person only provided an opinion about the Adamo activity monitoring sensor noting that it was not state-of-the-art.

Group 1 – Less appreciated features of DECI care received

Overall: A majority of patients could not find something specific that they were not satisfied with. However, ease of use issues has been mentioned as a reason to drop using the DECI solution.

- Sweden: One Group 1 patient mentioned the Lumbar puncture as less liked feature of the received care. However, it was appreciated to be thoroughly examined, even with spinal fluid testing.
- Italy: The group 1 patients have mostly related to the care-as-usual and referred to their overall experiences in the healthcare system. Hence, out of two Group 1 patients interviewed, one expressed the disappointment in the fees of treatments, and the critique received by one healthcare professional. Another participant did not identify any less liked features of the received care.
- Israel: Group 1 patients expressed difficulties in starting to use the tablet. Inappropriate translation to Hebrew was frustrating for some patients. One patient has reflected upon discontinuation of using the DECI system due to a lack of constant access to IT assistance and guidance.

Control group – Less appreciated features of care received

Overall: Most Control group participants have not stated any less appreciated features of the care that they had been provided. However, one-third of patients have mentioned a lack of integration within the care system as a perceived problem.

- Sweden: One patient expressed that information regarding the different care stages and the next steps over the study was missing.
- Italy: Most interviewed patients from the Control group had no reflections on the less liked elements of the care received. However, three patients mentioned a too long waiting time between a request and a visit, due to lack of integration. Bureaucracy and fees for medical services that are not covered by the State were also mentioned.

- Israel: One interviewed patient from Israel did not see the care received as a treatment.
- Spain: No reflections regarding the less liked elements by the interviewed Control group patient.

Perceptions regarding the Physical activity training program

A clear majority of Group 2 patients in all pilot sites have stated that the physical training program seemed to have been applicable for them. Also, patients of different sites have declared a positive outlook to the system, implicating that instructions have been watched and exercises have been performed. However, despite an overall positive opinion towards the system, one third of the interviewees have also reported that there were occasions when it was challenging to understand how to operate the system, and to understand specific exercises. Almost half of the patients considered exercises as being not challenging enough.

- Sweden: Statements from Swedish patients indicate that most of them have appreciated the possibility for IT-assisted exercise programs to be performed in one's own home. Half of the patients think that the system was easy to log on to, to understand and to use. One patient stressed the importance of information provided by the healthcare professional, in order to be motivated *"...it (training) felt very natural to me, and they explained why I felt like I did."* In many cases, the patients declared that they would like to continue using this program after finished interventions. Perceived drawbacks were reported by a few patients mainly in relation to instructions for specific exercises. One patient has also argued that a display for monitoring the remaining time of an exercise performed is needed, as not knowing the remaining time in different exercises can be stressful and unclear.
Improvement suggestions: Implement visual time keeper.
- Italy: Half of the Italian patients especially highlight the system's simplicity, as a benefit for participants understanding and motivation. One patient stated that *"I like physical exercises, because I could learn sequences and I can perform them independently"*, a quote that implies that the remote physical training can be beneficial for patients in a good physical health. The system's value was appreciated by patients who were not used to perform physical training, as stated by a few patients. Furthermore, a majority of participants think that the exercises were not challenging enough for them. Additionally, one patient reported that it would have been useful to have some kind of interaction with clinicians when performing different activities in order to secure that performed exercises were done in a proper and harmless way.
Improvement suggestions: Develop a system for providing live feedback to patients when performing exercises.
- Israel: Most patients have reported appreciation of physical exercises, prescribed by healthcare professionals. However, a majority of patients also implied that the

recommended exercises did not match their physical status: *“The level was very low, and the movies were very slow. I did not have patience for that.”* Another participant argued that there was no obvious connection between physical training and memory. Yet another patient did not feel confident when using the system, deriving from many perceived software problems in the physical exercise program.

Improvement suggestions: Implement a possibility to increase the speed of instruction and exercise demonstration.

- Spain: no patients provided an opinion on the physical activity training program.

Perceptions regarding the Cognitive activity stimulation program

The Cognitive activity stimulation program was considered as stimulating and meaningful by more than half of the patients. However, logging-on and operating cognitive games was perceived as very problematic by more than a third of participants in different sites.

- Italy: Most interviewees in the Italian pilot thought that the cognitive games have been challenging and stimulating, especially in relation to the fact that a treatment was provided on a progressing level over time. The entertaining features of the games were also recognized as attractive, highlighted by one patient: *“...they (games) helped me feel better. Using cognitive exercises distracted me from home-occupations like prepare dishes or cleaning”*. However, a quarter of the patients using the cognitive stimulation program considered it hard to navigate, especially one participant who could not use the system without an informal caregiver being present for aid.

Improvement suggestions: none.

- Israel: The cognitive games were appreciated by participants due to the possibility to customize the program for different needs. Also, as described by one interviewee: *“I felt that it helped me in making connections and paying attention to details”*. Most patients have argued that the exercises were not challenging enough. But the system itself was challenging to operate. Language translation issues and sensitivity of the touch screen were the most reported problems.

Improvement suggestions: Improve language translation and sensitivity of the touch screen.

- Sweden: A majority of Swedish patients valued a variation and the amusement aspects of the games, stimulating them to use the system and to challenge themselves. As one patient answered: *“...I could hear all the cheering for me (in the game). The funniest part was when it yielded Bingo!”* More than half of the Swedish interviewees have repeatedly experienced log-in problems. Patients have reported that they got tired of not being able to log-on to the system. Translations were perceived as incorrect and software design could have been more intuitive.

Improvement suggestions: Improve translation and pressure registration.

- Spain: Interview data from one Spanish patient indicated that the system was perceived too immature which led to discontinuing using the system after 15-20 days: *"It upsets my nerves. I continue with my exercise books"*.

Perceptions regarding the Activity monitoring sensor

Wearing the watch was reported as a non-disturbing experience by most interviewed patients. However, most patients argued that it was difficult to understand a need of the watch, especially since the patients perceived they were not able to monitor own data. Furthermore, from an aesthetic viewpoint, the watch was considered as visually non-appealing and big, also stated by a majority of the interviewed patients.

- Italy: All interviewed Italian patients who had received the watch argued that they got used to wear it. *"I have always kept the watch, it was a loyal companion"* as one participant stated. However, all patients reported that they did not like the size of the watch.
Improvement suggestions: Reduce the size of the watch.
- Israel: Israeli patients who received and tried the watch have reported that using the watch was not troublesome, however the purpose of using it was not clear.
Improvement suggestions: none.
- Sweden: Among the interviewed Group 2 patients in Sweden, only two had received a watch. One patient reflected that the watch worked well. Both patients perceived the watch as not visually appealing, due to its design and size. Interviews also indicated that patients were interested in monitoring their own pedometer data which they are used to do in other similar devices like smartwatch or smartphone application: *"...should I wear two watches at a time?"*. The worn-out armband during the 6 months was also mentioned by one patient.
Improvement suggestions: none.
- Spain: No patients gave opinions on the watch.

Perceptions regarding the Tablet

Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the tablet. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service.

- Italy: some patient reported that prior IT experience helped using the tablet.
- Israel: patients without prior IT experience needed support by family members or professionals. One patient reported that she is used to her own tablet and do not want to learn using a new one.
- Sweden: a tablet was perceived as not such well-working tool as other smart devices. Moreover, logging-in each time and restarting the tablet made patients upset.
- Spain: no information.

Perceptions regarding the Integrated care platform

- Italy: no information provided.
- Israel: two patients reported that they didn't use the messaging and scheduling function. Two patients expressed to be in need of IT assistance, especially at the beginning of usage.
- Sweden: Two Swedish patients stated that they had problems handling the overall system.
- Spain: no information provided.

Perceptions regarding the ease of use of the DECI system

DECI system seems to have been intuitive enough for a majority of patients to navigate. However, a few patients in each site have argued that they were in need of assistance by a professional or an informal caregiver.

- Italy: Majority of the interviewed patients in Italy have reported that they did not have to learn many new skills to be able to navigate and handle the DECI system. Nevertheless, in a few cases help was needed from a family member to get started with the system.
- Israel: Diverse views were reported from Israeli pilot. Most patients could use the solution independently but for some patients it was difficult to operate the system, and support by family members was needed.
- Sweden: Most Swedish patients seemed to have managed to navigate in the system, with support from professionals. One participant reported that guidance from a family member was needed in the beginning.
- Spain: no information.

Indications on the willingness to use the DECI solution in the future

Majority of the interviewed patients have declared their willingness to use different parts of DECI solution in the future.

- Italy: A greater part of the Italian interviewees emphasized the future use of DECI, as an aid for themselves to keep active both physically and cognitively: *"... because it's an instrument that improves my well-being and it helps me to pass the time. <...> I don't have a great experience with technology but the training phase is fundamental"*.
- Israel: Patients had mixed views towards the future use of the DECI solution, with half of the interviewees having expressed willingness to continue using it. In the

interviews, there was a clear connection between patients that were able to operate the system without assistance and the willingness of future use.

- Sweden: Most patients in Swedish intervention have highlighted the physical activity training program as a feature that they are willing to continue using after the study. As declared by one patient, *“I have been searching for a physical exercise program looking like this”*, besides the need of such program adding the importance of having it recommended by the healthcare professionals.
- Spain: The one interviewed Spanish patient has not provided information regarding the willingness to use the DECI solution in the future.

Conclusion

The patient perception analysis indicated that eHealth solutions of **DECI were seen as complementary tools to the care system**. Along the ICT, the appreciated elements of care related to the experienced empathy, kindness and competence of healthcare professionals (Italy, Sweden), and home visits (Sweden). **Personal contact with healthcare professionals played an important role** in patient satisfaction in all the study groups, including a control group. However, patient satisfaction and the positive outlook towards the future use of the DECI solution can be negatively affected by ICT log-on issues or technical instability of the system, and even cause a discontinuation of the system use. A constant access to IT assistance in a format of an **IT helpdesk** indicated a need for a **new role in the care system**. Some patients in the **Control group** (Italy) mentioned a **lack of integration in the healthcare system**.

The physical activity training program was appreciated and perceived as relevant and easy to use by MCI and MD patients, although less challenging for people with good physical condition. The **home-based training was perceived as empowering and autonomy-increasing** tool. To better suit the study population, the **identified improvement areas** for the physical activity training program were: (1) to introduce a timer display indicating the remaining time when performing exercises, (2) to implement a possibility to increase speed of instruction, and (3) to introduce a means for live feedback to secure that the exercises are performed correctly. In comparison with the cognitive activity training system, the physical training program was perceived as “less fun” by one patient, indicating that for some individuals an **entertainment function is important**.

The cognitive activity training program was appreciated and perceived as **stimulating** by more than half of the patients. The system was positively perceived due to its entertaining features and **customization**, again raising the **importance of entertainment features**.

However, some patients argued that the **exercises have not been challenging enough**. Some patients found the system harder to navigate and had experienced log-on issues. To better suit the study population, the **identified improvement areas** for the cognitive activity training program were: (1) to improve pressure registration, (2) ensure correctness of local language translations.

The activity monitoring sensor wearing experience was perceived as **non-invasive**. However, the interview results indicate that function and **benefits of the watch should be thoroughly explained** to the patients and caregivers, especially in comparison with other products on the market. Most patients have argued that it was difficult to understand a need of the watch, since they were not able to monitor own data. Furthermore, from an aesthetic viewpoint, the watch was considered as visually non-appealing and big, also stated by a majority of the interviewed patients. To better suit the study population, the **identified improvement areas** for the activity monitoring sensor were: (1) to reduce size of the watch, (2) to improve aesthetic features.

Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the **tablet**. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service.

Overall, navigation in the DECI system has been intuitive enough for a majority of the interviewed patients. However, a few patients in each site have argued that they were in need of assistance by a professional or an informal caregiver.

Lastly, majority of the interviewed patients have **declared their willingness to use different parts of DECI solution in the future**, mostly the physical and cognitive training modules.

5.1.6 Caregiver burden

First, it must be noted that in Swedish site the data employed to analyse Zarit burden test lacked gender and age information. Therefore, to be able to carry out a multicentre analysis it was decided to use as control variables only the group to which caregiver's patient belongs.

From a **multicentric perspective**, the following tables show the evolution between T0 and T1 of the Zarit score levels corresponding to the caregivers recruited in the study:

- Control group

		Zarit T=1		
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	38	2	0
	level 2 (47-56)	4	2	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0

- Intervention group 1

		Zarit T=1		
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	12	0	0
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	1
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0

- Intervention group 2

		Zarit T=1		
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	34	1	0
	level 2 (47-56)	0	1	1
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0

Table 47. All countries result

The cells highlighted in yellow show the number of caregivers who changed the Zarit level score in the final visit of the study. In the control group, 4 patients have improved (the less the better) their Zarit score. Otherwise, 1 patient from Intervention group 1 and 2 patients from Intervention group 2 have increased the score to reach the following Zarit level which implies a worsening in the burden suffered.

Regarding the statistical analysis, the T0-T1 slope difference between Control group and Intervention group 1 is -0.3463 (2.6269) with $p=0.89538$. The comparison between Control group and Intervention group 2 is 0.2271 (1.8530) with $p=0.90271$. Both cases **do not have statistical significance** ($p>0.05$).

Apart from the multicentre statistical analysis of the intervention effect, an intra-analysis among the different centres have been carried out by considering Italy as a reference because it is the site that recruited the largest number of patients. Thus, only Sweden, that presents a difference of -14.1875 (2.7574) with $p=1.23e^{-06}$; and Spain with difference of -12.1648 (4.2233) with $p=0.00477$ are **statistically significant**. Considering these relevant results, it seems feasible to perform an analysis per country to see the intervention effect in each site.

Israel

Israel site has data from only one patient therefore the effect intervention analysis is not feasible.

Italy

Similar to the multicentric analysis, below the evolution in Zarit score levels of caregivers per each patient group is shown:

- Control group

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	16	2	0	0
	level 2 (47-56)	4	1	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	0	0	0	3

- Intervention group 1

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	11	0	0	0
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	1	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	0	0	0	5

- Intervention group 2

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	15	1	0	0
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	1	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	0	0	0	4

Table 48. Italian result

Following the same reasoning as before, the cells highlighted in yellow show the number of caregivers who change the Zarit level score at the end of the study. In the control group, 4 patients have improved (the less the better) their Zarit score. Otherwise, 1 patient from Intervention group 1 and 2 from Intervention group 2 have increased the score to reach the following Zarit level, which means a worsening in caregivers' burden. It must be noted, that a total of 12 patient (cells in red) did not present the correspondent Zarit score associated to their caregivers.

On the other hand, by comparing the T0-T1 slope of the Control group and the two interventions groups, the following results are obtained: **there is no statistical**

significance in both groups since group intervention 1 shows an estimate of -0.02899 (3.73108) with $p=0.9938$; and the group intervention 2 has 0.01023 (3.35117) with $p=0.9976$.

Spain

The evolution in the Zarit score levels is shown in the following tables:

- Control group

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	3	0	0	1
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	1	0	0	0

- Intervention group 1

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	1	0	0	2
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	1	0	0	0

- Intervention group 2

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	3	0	0	0
	level 2 (47-56)	0	0	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	0	0	0	0

Table 49. Spanish result

In case of Spanish site, there are not caregivers who have changed their Zarit level. Nevertheless, we should refer to those cases (cells in red) in control group and intervention group 1 who represents a mismatching between T0 and T1. These cases happened because in one of the visits, either T0 or T1, the caregiver didn't show up.

In addition, performing the statistical analysis of T0-T1 slope we find **results statistically significant** in both comparisons: Control group vs Intervention 1 group, and Control group vs Intervention 2 group. In the first case the estimate slope is -10.610(3.137) with $p=0.02058$, while in the other case the result is -9.034 (2.326) with $p=0.01739$. Checking these results with the above tables, we could affirm that although there are no patients who change between Zarit score levels some significant Zarit score changes (improvement of caregiver's burden in T1) must happened inside the groups.

Sweden

It must be noted that in case of Swedish study the Intervention group 1 was not considered. Also, the data were obtained from the family members present at the first meeting. However, the family members in Sweden do not consider themselves as caregivers, and the results should be seen in this perspective. The tables that show the changes in Zarit score levels are depicted below.:

- Control group

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	19	0	0	2
	level 2 (47-56)	0	1	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	5	0	0	1

- Intervention group 2

		Zarit T=1			
		level 1 (0-47)	level 2 (47-56)	level 3 (56-88)	N/A
Zarit T=0	level 1 (0-47)	15	0	0	1
	level 2 (47-56)	0	1	0	0
	level 3 (56-88)	0	0	0	0
	N/A	3	0	0	1

Table 50. Spanish result

Similar to Spain, there are no caregivers who change their Zarit level. Nevertheless, it must be remarked those cases who presents the mismatching between T0 and T1 (11 cases in total) as well as two patients that were not accompanied by their caregivers at the time of the visits.

On the other hand, the comparison of the T0-T1 slope between control group and intervention group 2 doesn't show a statistical significance by having as estimate 1.619(1.820) with $p=0.380$.

Conclusion

Considering the expected results mentioned above: "Intervention group 2 caregivers are expected to report reduced burden in comparison to Intervention group 1 and Control group; and Intervention group 1 caregivers are expected to report reduced or stable burden compared with Control group."; only the Spanish site can justify these expectations with a statistical significance. Nevertheless, in this site all caregivers' Zarit score level were maintained along the study.

In case of rest of the sites, i.e. Sweden and Italy, the results were no statistically significant. Thus, the number of lost cases (cells in red) could have influence in this non-statistical significance.

5.1.7 Healthcare professional satisfaction

Healthcare professionals' characteristics

Perceptions of the healthcare professionals were collected from the English-speaking professionals included in the delivery of DECI-based care. A total of 12 in-depth structured interviews were performed. 9 oral interviews were conducted using communication technologies (Skype and Whatsapp) and 3 interviews were obtained in a written form using the same protocol of the structured interview.

In *Israel*, 3 interviews were conducted. The age category was 31-50 years old, and all interviewees were female occupational therapists. 66% of the interviewees were experienced ICT users, and 33% were intermediate users. At the time of the interview, all interviewees were involved in DECI project for at least 6 months.

In *Italy*, 4 interviews were conducted. 50% of interviewees were male, and 50% female. 50% of interviewees belong to the age group 16-30, and 50% to the age group 31-50. Among the interviewees, the occupations were: Geriatrician, Social worker, Neuropsychologist, Clinical and Neuropsychologist. The ICT literacy varied: 50% were experienced users, and 25% intermediate users and 25% basic users. 75% of respondents were involved in DECI for 1 year or more, and one respondent was new to the project (2 months).

In *Spain*, 3 interviews were conducted. 66% of interviewees were female, and 33% male. Among the interviewees, the occupations were: Geriatrician (66%), Psychologist (33%). 66% are experienced ICT users, and 33% intermediate users. 66% of respondents were involved in DECI project more than 1 year, and 33% less than 1 year.

In *Sweden*, 2 interviews were conducted. All respondents were female, and age groups were 31-50, and 51-65. Both respondents are intermediate users of ICT. One respondent was a geriatrician, and one was a nurse. Both respondents have been involved in DECI for more than 1 year.

	Total	Israel	Italy	Spain	Sweden
Number of interviews	12	3	4	3	2

Table 51. Number of interviews

The most appreciated features of DECI care provided

When asked about favourite features of DECI care model as a way to provide care to MCI and MD patients, professionals from all countries emphasized technological features of

DECI such as physical and cognitive training programs, and a possibility to monitor patient's performance through these tools.

- *Italy*: All interviewed professionals agreed that the infrastructure and technological features of DECI provided an opportunity for patients to exercise at home and to monitor their performance. A case manager being dedicated, available to answer questions and guide patients, is a new way of building relationship between patient and professionals.
- *Israel*: All the interviewed staff members considered cognitive and physical exercise programs as the best features of DECI. Professionals perceived DECI-model as introducing a new way to treat patients with MCI and MD and to monitor their performance. DECI provided an opportunity for patients to practice cognitive skills that do not get trained that much otherwise due to a lack of a computer or skills to use it.
- *Sweden*: DECI introduced a new way of meeting MCI and MD patients by visiting them at home, stated in both interviews. It allowed to observe their level of functionality, and to see how patients differ from one another. It helped professionals form positive relationships with patients.
- *Spain*: The Spanish staff all reported that using a DECI platform and physical and cognitive exercises, it could be a complementary way of learning for patients, in addition to group sessions. It allows to monitor and evaluate physical and cognitive treatment. Provides a possibility of easy and direct contact with patients. DECI saves time because patients do not need to come to care facilities.

Perceptions regarding the Physical activity training program

Usefulness of the physical training program was perceived as high throughout the different sites. A majority of interviewed healthcare professionals in all countries considered the training program as a well-functioning and useful part of the DECI solution. The feature that was most appreciated by the interviewed clinicians was the possibility to personalize the training program for each patient, on their own level, and staff being able to recommend exercises not normally performed. However, in general, most of the interviewees reported that the exercises did not challenge their patients enough. To some extent this was seen as a risk for non-compliance as patients considered themselves in a better physical shape than the level of exercises implied.

- *Italy*: One of the clinicians reported: *"The exercises are appreciated by the patients, even if they are not doing things right"*. Such perception indicates that patients appreciated to be instructed to perform activities, even if they could not receive feedback from the system or staff on their practical interpretation of the exercises. Physical exercise program was also considered to provide an advantage to usual care, by providing clinical staff tools to offer patients with conditions of MCI and MD rarely found elsewhere. The interviews also draw attention to the fact that some of the exercises, even if considered less challenging for most of the patients,

may be less safe for some participants and may cause physical harm. Safety risks were especially pinpointed for older patients indicating that some supervision on location has to be offered for certain patients.

From an aesthetic perspective, there were challenges for patients concerning the navigation of the system. Also, one professional emphasized that it was difficult for patients to report feedback to staff after a performed exercise.

Improvement suggestions: To improve the button design, font size and colour; to eliminate the option to request feedback, since patients consider it challenging to write feedback on a keyboard. To avoid the visualization of different levels, since the patients need to be focused on their own capabilities.

- Israel: Two of the three interviewed professionals in Israeli pilot noticed that there are not many suitable alternatives for online physical training programs on the market, and the DECI solution fills that gap. A structured physical training was seen as a feature that clinicians have not been able to offer before the study. However, the physical exercises were considered too easy for their physically fit population, that exclusively consisted of MCI-patients. This opinion was reported by all interviewed health care professionals in Israel.

Improvement suggestions: to provide a more intuitive design for change of training level.

- Sweden: A physical training was seen as a feature of the DECI solution that clinicians have not been able to offer before the study to the relatively healthy population (despite cognitive problems). The exercises were recognized as useful, since many exercises included in the system are not performed otherwise. One of the interviewees stated: “<...>the ones who are in good physical shape discover that the system is really good, because they are using muscles that they don't normally use when they are outside practicing their exercises”. A possibility to personalize training programs was also highly valued by staff. Even though physical exercises were appreciated, both interviewees also draw attention to the fact that these activities primarily are designed for patients with minor cognitive problems. For patients in more severe stages, assistance from health care professional was more needed.

Improvement suggestions: to improve stability and reliability of the system, and to improve integration with other systems.

- Spain: Most professionals have reported that they appreciated the videos, and the instructions for patients, in the physical training module. The interviewees also valued the fact that is possible to instruct patients from distance, especially when a level of difficulty needs to be changed. All the interviewees have also highlighted the fact that their population have found the training program being not challenging enough: “Some patients with higher educational level or MCI may find it

too easy but this is related to the program, you can change the level, but from some point you can't do anything.

Improvement suggestions: to add more challenging exercises in order to fit a physically healthy MCI population.

Perceptions regarding the Cognitive activity stimulation program

The cognitive activity stimulation program was appreciated by a majority of the interviewed healthcare professionals, especially as they report patient satisfaction with the system. The most highlighted feature is the system's ability to automatically rise the level of difficulty, depending on progress of a patient. Furthermore, the system was considered easy to understand and to use for healthcare staff as well as patients. However, the system was perceived as the most challenging feature of the DECI solution due to technical issues as emphasized by approximately half of the professionals. Over time, there have been multiple occasions when staff and patients could not log on and reach the cognitive exercises. There are reasons to assume that these problems could have had an effect on compliance and willingness to use the system in the future.

- Italy: Cognitive games were perceived as well suited for MCI and MD patients by all interviewees. *"Cognitive games and the theory behind them is very good. When I compare these games with other cognitive apps, in my experience, they are equal."* Additionally, half of the Italian interviewees have reported that instructions were easy to follow for the targeted population, and that the cognitive games can even be played as amusement. The system's drawbacks mostly concerned the log-on and technical problems that have been present from the beginning of the study, according to most of the interviewees. Therefore, major technical assistance had to be assigned during the study. One professional also noticed the fact that translations could be improved in system, an issue especially important if one already experienced problems at the log-on stage.

Improvement suggestions: to improve technical stability and facilitate log-on to the system.

- Israel: A majority of interviewed healthcare staff reported that cognitive games were easy to operate. Moreover, the system itself stimulates progress of performance level. One interviewee has indicated that patients could be motivated to use cognitive games at a time that suits them well *"It is very comfortable because they are doing it on their free time"*. In contrast to other sites, log-on problems were not reported in Israel. However, most interviewees drew attention to aesthetics within the system: the patients perceived that the buttons in the system were challenging to press correctly, in order not to cause multiple signals in the system. *Improvement suggestions:* to improve pressure registration.

- Sweden: The Swedish healthcare professionals have reported that the pace of training, and progress of levels, was well suited for their patients. One interviewee also perceived the exercises to be on a level that stimulated MCI and MD-patients enough, but that patients in more severe stages could perceive the games as too challenging. According to both professionals, the major problems were mainly in the area of repeating log-on issues (also reported occasions when patients were logged in and accidentally were logged out). These issues were most evident for patients in the beginning of project: *"...we notice that the ones who are calling are the ones who have recently received the tablet. The ones who had it for 1-2 months – they don't call because they know "Aha! Now there's problem again.""* In addition, some aesthetic issues were reported, such as "jumping pictures" and language translation issues.

Improvement suggestions: to establish more research-based guidelines in how to personalize selection of games according to patient's unique cognitive state. To develop a more stable log-on environment. To improve translations and system stability in relation to visual elements in the system.

- Spain: Most healthcare professionals in Spain perceived that patients appreciated the cognitive games. Exercises were also valued by professionals because of the possibility to adapt a program for each patient, based on individual cognitive challenges. Spanish interviewees also highlighted that providing cognitive games via ICT stimulated patients' independence, and that patients do not have to see their healthcare provider physically each time: *"I can give recommendations without visiting the patients in person"*. The fact that the cognitive stimulation system was located outside the DECI platform may indicate that the patients would have to manage too many steps in order to reach the system, as perceived by one interviewee.

Improvement suggestions: to further integrate cognitive games into the DECI solution.

Perceptions regarding the Activity monitoring sensor

Healthcare professionals' perceptions regarding *usefulness, compatibility to patient needs, and reliability* of the wearable activity monitoring sensor (hereinafter – a watch) can be clustered into 2 groups based on similarities in opinions: (1) Italian and Spanish, and (2) Swedish and Israeli.

- (1) *Usefulness:* Most healthcare professionals from Italy and Spain reported that the tool was valuable for activity monitoring, and the reports based on the collected data were accessible for healthcare professionals and provided information that would have been difficult to measure by other means. Also, it could replace some oral questions to the patients and caregivers. Moreover, it was perceived that the

information in the reports could offer a possibility to correlate physical activity to other measures.

Compatibility with patient needs: It was perceived that wearing a watch made patients feel calmer, since they were monitored, stated by one interviewee. (Italy)

Reliability: Although sometimes the presentation of the data or the data itself was not fully understandable, the watch was perceived equally or more reliable than Fitbit or Apple Watch, as one healthcare professional reported.

(2) *Usefulness:* All respondents from Sweden and Israel perceived the watch as a less useful technology and believed they could not easily verify patient's adherence to the recommended watch wearing time. Also, the professionals believed that the market offers better solutions with more features, such as step calculators visible on the display which is an important motivator for patients to ensure adherence.

Compatibility with patient needs: It was experienced that for patients who have maintained a good physical shape and regular activity which was the case of Swedish and Israeli patients, wearing the watch was of low interest. The healthcare professionals reported extra workload such as phone calls and home visits to convince patients to wear the watch and adhere to the recommended wearing duration.

Reliability: Swedish staff reported that sometimes the data was perceived unreliable, such as minus steps in the report, 50 km/hour speed. Also, step count did not work when the watch was kept in a pocket, and not on a hand.

Aesthetics: Regarding the physical features of the watch, a majority of healthcare professionals from all countries shared similar opinions. Although the weight of the watch was good, the size was perceived as too big, and the base station - too bulky. Appearance of the watch was perceived less appealing, and the patients were hesitant to wear it during vacation or on social occasions such as church activities or other social gatherings, as wearing it could create an "image of a sick person".

Suggestions for improvement:

- To introduce a step-calculator on the display, to make it competitive to other products on the market. (Sweden)
- To measure pressure, hour of activity, sleep analysis to provide extra value for clinicians. (Italy)
- Data for patients and caregivers should be made easier to read (presentation). (Italy)
- Design and appearance – related disadvantages (all countries, see "Aesthetics").

Perceptions regarding the Integrated care platform

The Integrated care platform had ambivalent reviews by the respondents. Overall, ICT experience can help patients to appreciate the platform, and the interviewed healthcare professionals provided different ideas of how to smoothen the introduction of patients with the platform, and how to provide the support needed.

- Italy: Several advantages of the platform have been mentioned: a messaging function that is usually not used by patients and caregivers, the facilitated data organization and sharing, and an overall advanced design of the DECI app compared to other solutions on the market. Overall, the platform was observed as easy to use even for people with less ICT experience. But for elder patients, problems in interaction with platform have been observed. Hard to login into the platform, and to find a right game. Some patients requested a lot of live support to use the platform. For clinicians, usage of the platform was easy and simple. However, data entry should be simplified, because it needs too many clicks to find a patient and to track the data. Moreover, the platform does not have patient's social and health diary to have access to a patient's path.
Improvement suggestions: more instruments on the platform should be created to be more relevant to services of particular institutions. The platform is suggested to developed into a smartphone app. A direct access to the platform is preferred (due to login windows). Aesthetics: font size is too small, and patients don't know how to zoom it. Small keys should be eliminated (enter, login, etc.).
- Israel: Due to a lack of ICT experience, some patients were hesitant to agree using the system. One interviewee mentioned that it could be a good idea to provide patients with a workbook and instructions how to use the system, supported by visual images. This could improve usage of the system and cooperation by patients. Additionally, some connection problems were mentioned by one interviewee.
- Sweden: the platform was perceived as less useful due to unused messaging functions which was a particularity of the care model in Sweden and reliance on phone contact on the road.
- Spain: The platform was perceived as good to handle information about patients. However, the platform should be more interactive, for example the cognitive stimulation exercises should be an integral part of the platform. The platform helped to easily and directly contact patients (highly appreciated feature). The platform can save time since the patients and doctors do not need to meet as often. However, the platform requires healthcare professionals to be very alert of the messages and patient's progress, which may sometimes not match with the clinician's schedule, and increase expectations by patients: *"You have to find time to check the system, the messages and patient data"*.

Perceptions regarding the Tablet

Previous ICT experience was a facilitator to use the tablet. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service.

- Italy: For older people, especially with low ICT experience, it was observed that tablets were difficult to use. Help by caregivers and professional support was needed to assist with the use of tablets. Cost of a tablet for patients has been

identified as a main potential disadvantage that might hinder the future use of the DECI solution.

- Israel: Tablets were perceived as providing a flexibility to use the ICT modules on convenient time. However, it was hard to convince patients to use the system, if they were not experienced with tablets. Sometimes, the tablets did not catch the Internet signal.
- Sweden: Professionals perceived that the tablet was easy to use for patients, since most patients are used to the smartphones. The tablet was perceived as easy to use even for the patients without prior ICT experience. In case of any usage issues, volunteers in different municipalities were recruited to provide extra technical help at home of patients, such as starting the tablet.
- Spain: One healthcare professional mentioned that it takes time for some elderly people to learn using a tablet.

Perceptions regarding the role of a Case manager

All interviewed professionals, who knew about the existence of a case manager in DECI, perceived this role as a necessity for patients with MCI and MD. The key function of a case manager is seen to act as an intermediary between a patient and service provider, to answer questions and to help navigate different services for the patients and caregivers. In Italy, most professionals were positive about the fact that a case manager has an overview of a patient situation which saves time and effort for other professionals if information about a patient is needed. Moreover, case manager can create a sense of continuity and trust. In Sweden, both professionals believed that being a case manager is fun and rewarding.

Impact of DECI to the job performance

Professionals in all countries perceived DECI as providing benefits to their job, such as widened knowledge about cognitive impairment, obtained more tools facilitating work with patients, and better understanding of their needs and status. All the respondents believed that due to DECI they can keep the current or increase their job performance in relation to patients. However, the workload issues have been reported in three countries (Italy, Israel, Sweden). Since the care models differed in each country, the extent of professionals' participation in the DECI care also varied:

	Italy	Israel	Sweden	Spain
Average weekly hours spent in DECI	29,3h/week	1,5h/week	52,5h/week	4,3h/week

Table 52. Average hours per week spent for DECI care

- *Italy*: The workload had increased due to the research set-up when using the platform to enter the data.

- *Israel*: The project increased workload related to managing patients' participation (willingness to participate) in the DECI research.
- *Sweden*: Mobile team working principle keeps professionals out of office travelling, which makes it difficult for ad-hoc multi-disciplinary collaborations. Involved professionals travelled more than 10 000 km to patients' homes. Due to the DECI research set-up and high number of recruited patients, overtime has been reported.

Indications on the willingness to use the DECI solution in the future

All the interviewed professionals expressed willingness to use the DECI model in the future. DECI technologies were seen as complementary to the standard care offers of each country. Professionals believed that DECI can improve treatment, information flow and can have an effect on cognitive performance and overall health condition of a patient.

Conclusion

The healthcare professionals' perception analysis indicated that eHealth solutions of **DECI were seen as complementary tools to the care system**. Professionals from all countries have appreciated all the ICT modules of the DECI solution, and a possibility to monitor patient's performance through these tools.

The **physical training program** was perceived as **useful for the studied population** in all pilot sites, with an advantage of **customization possibility** to suit patient's condition. Additionally, the program includes certain types of the exercises stimulating particular muscles that otherwise do not receive proper attention, even if the person is generally physically active. While the exercises were perceived as **too light or less challenging for patients in good physical condition**, **safety concerns** were expressed in relation to the older population, implying that a supervision during performing of the exercises might be needed.

The **cognitive activity stimulation program** was perceived as useful and satisfying the studied population. The **entertaining features**, as well as a possibility of **customization** and different levels of difficulty make this program a great solution for MCI and MD patients. However, in order to ensure adherence to the cognitive stimulation games, the **technical stability of the system needs to be improved**.

The **activity monitoring sensor** was perceived as a **valuable tool to complement regular care** and physical activity training, especially in Italy and Spain. In these countries, the healthcare professionals viewed the sensor as an opportunity to extract additional value from the collected data. In contrast, the sensor was less positively perceived in Israel and Sweden, mainly in comparison to other similar solutions on the

market. The main **drawback of the sensor was its physical appearance and insufficient design**, such as a lack of a pedometer.

The **Integrated care platform** had ambivalent reviews by the respondents. In Italy and Spain, the **messaging function was highly appreciated** as a facilitator of clinical professional's work and **a time-saver**. While in Sweden, the usefulness of the same functions was not identified due to a local care model. Overall, **ICT experience can help patients to appreciate the platform**, and the interviewed healthcare professionals provided different ideas of how to smoothen the introduction of patients with the platform, and how to provide the support needed.

Previous ICT experience is a facilitator to use the **tablet**. An IT helpdesk and training introducing the tablet for patients needs to be a necessary part of DECI service. However, **cost** to provide a tablet to each patient is a concern.

Case manager role was perceived as a necessity for patients with MCI and MD, creating a sense of continuity and trust for patients.

Overall, DECI project has **increased workload** for healthcare professionals from all countries, and the different working hours per week depended on the local care models. At the same time, all the respondents believed that due to DECI they can keep the current or increase their job performance. Finally, all the interviewed professionals **expressed willingness to use the DECI model in the future**.

5.2 Technological perspective

Usage of the system

The following KPI analysis is mainly based on technical outcomes retrieved from the system log files and information saved in the system databases, this means that only patients who have had access to the platform at least once are included in the analysis. Also, some patients did not finished intervention at the time of data extraction and results could change while considering a wider timeframe in the future.

System usage is considered in the timeframe starting the 15th of May 2017 to the 15th of May 2018. To be considered that, actually, the platform was stated to be stable and fully available for the patients from July 2017.

TECH KPI001 - Login frequency to Integrated Care Platform

The first component to be reached while accessing to the DECI system is the Integrated Care Platform, to be used for scheduling activities and meetings, and for communicating

to the specialists. Only patients belonging to intervention group 1 (intermediate) and group 2 (full) have access to this specific module and are provided of a tablet.

Group 2 patients have access also to the others ICT modules, as specified in the following paragraphs.

Results in Italy

In the Italian site, 72 patients were active in the system at least once, divided in 25 subjects in group 1 (intermediate intervention) and 47 in group 2 (full intervention).

Figure 15. Intervention groups accesses trend

The average patient accessed 25 times to the platform; while the group 1 patients accessed on average 8 times each during the intervention period, the group 2 patients accessed on average 34 times each in the considered period of time. However, Italian patients who used the Cognitive Games did not entered the application from the DECI platform but from a separated button due to simplicity in the login process. This may affect the numbers presented here for intervention group 2.

Figure 16. Full intervention group accesses per patient in Italy

Figure 17. Intermediate intervention group accesses per patient in Italy

Group 1 behaviour can be related to the fact that platform features could be replaced by contacting the specialist by phone, while group 2 had also access to the more specific training and activity modules.

Figure 18. Number of accesses during the observed timeframe per group

The access peak for the intervention group 1 (intermediate) coincides with the declared start date, the 25th of July 2017 (week 30), then gradually decreases and attests to a minimum trend. This progressive lowering contrasts the higher use by the full intervention group. This result is interesting because it is in line with what emerged in other paper publications¹.

¹Killin, L. O., Russ, T. C., Surdhar, S. K., Yoon, Y., McKinstry, B., Gibson, G., &MacIntyre, D. J. (2018). Digital Support Platform: a qualitative research study investigating the feasibility of an internet-based, postdiagnostic support platform for families living with dementia. *BMJ open*, 8(4), e020281

Results in Sweden

In the Swedish site, 58 patients in group 2 (full intervention) were active in the system at least once.

Figure 19. Intervention groups accesses trend

The group 2 patients accessed on average 76 times each in the considered period of time.

Figure 20. Full intervention group accesses per patient in Sweden

The overall access for group 2 is can be appreciated as sustained in the frequency of accesses.

Figure 21. Number of accesses during the observed timeframe per group

While the declared start date is the 23rd of May 2017, the system usage starts to increase since the 20th of August 2017, with a probable phase of abandonment after February 2018.

Results in Spain

In the Spanish site, 71 patients were active in the system at least once, divided in 35 subjects in group 1 (intermediate intervention) and 36 in group 2 (full intervention).

Figure 22. Intervention groups accesses trend

The average patient accessed 51 times to the platform; while the group 1 patients accessed on average 14 times each during the intervention period, the group 2 patients accessed on average 86 times each in the considered period of time.

Figure 23. Full intervention group accesses per patient in Spain

Figure 24. Intermediate intervention group accesses per patient in Spain

The accesses of individual patients have a more heterogeneous aspect, symptom that only part of the patients have been loyal to the usage of the platform.

Figure 25. Number of accesses during the observed timeframe per group

With the declared start date is the 27th of September 2017 (week 39), the system usage has an irregular trend, mainly in growth, as the rate of abandonment can only be appreciated with the advent of May.

Results in Israel

In Israel site, 34 patients were active in the system at least once, divided in 11 subjects in group 1 (intermediate intervention) and 23 in group 2 (full intervention).

Figure 26. Intervention groups accesses trend

The average patient accessed 18 times to the platform; while the group 1 patients accessed on average 3 times each during the intervention period, the group 2 patients accessed on average 25 times each in the considered period of time.

Figure 27. Full intervention group accesses per patient in Israel

Figure 28. Intermediate intervention group accesses per patient in Israel

Group 1 patients (intermediate intervention) accessed to the platform few times, resulting in a low average, while among the group 2 patients (full intervention) there is a sharper division between loyalists and those not interested or unable to adopt a technological solution. Many communications between group 1 and care managers were made by phone.

Figure 29. Number of accesses during the observed timeframe per group

With the declared start date is the 6th of July 2017 (week 27), the system usage has a growth after the middle of November 2017 with a part for an inflection correspondent with the advent of the new year, a tendentially regular trend.

Overall considerations

Figure 30. Comparison between active patients on the system and their average access

This couple of graphs shows an overall summary. Here can be appreciated among with the already discussed gap between intervention groups access trend, the distribution of patients in each site.

Italian patients who used the Cognitive Games did not enter the application from the DECI platform but from a separated button due to simplicity in the login process. This may affect the numbers presented here for intervention group 2.

TECH KPI002 - Access frequency to Activity Coaching system

One of the integrated components to be used through to the DECI system is the Activity Coaching module, to be used throughout the study as a training for mainly physical

exercises. Only patients belonging to intervention group 2 (full) have access to this specific module, thanks to the provided tablet.

Results in Italy

In the Italian site, 45 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Coaching module at least once.

Figure 31. Accesses trend

The average patient accessed 40 times to the module in the considered period of time.

Figure 32. Accesses per patient

While the access trend depicts an overall equilibrate distribution between more loyal users and less interested patients, only the 24% of them accessed less than 10 times during the analysed timeframe.

Figure 33. Accesses per week

Although there are no significant increases in the use of the module in time, it remains somewhat relatively constant throughout the study.

Results in Sweden

In the Swedish site, 58 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Coaching module at least once.

Figure 34. Accesses trend

The average patient accessed 47 times to the module in the considered period of time.

Figure 35. Accesses per patient

Also, in Sweden, the access trend depicts an overall equilibrate distribution between more loyal users and less interested patients.

Figure 36. Accesses per week

Although there are no significant increases in the use of the module in time, it remains somewhat relatively constant throughout the study.

Results in Spain

In the Spanish site, 36 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Coaching module at least once.

Figure 37. Accesses trend

The average patient accessed 41 times to the module in the considered period of time, highlighting an accentuated loyalty only for some patients.

Figure 38. Accesses per patient

Figure 39. Accesses per week

The use of the module has increased reaching some significant peaks, thus decreasing with the beginning of March 2018.

Results in Israel

In Israel site, 22 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Coaching module at least once.

Figure 40. Accesses trend

The average patient accessed 14 times to the module in the considered period of time.

Figure 41. Accesses per patient

Module usage is overall low, with the exception of a patient.

Figure 42. Accesses per week

In the observed timeframe, the accesses throughout the weeks, showing a fluctuating trend. The major usage can be observed from October to December 2017.

TECH KPI003 – Usage of the Cognitive Games system

The Cognitive Games application was not integrated in the DECI platform, as login access was separated and needed a second pair of credentials. This also meant that logs files and the full DB was not in direct possession of the consortium.

The presented graphs show as per the other modules the penetration per single user and the trend of usage per week. It might be worth noting that there are heterogeneous indicators of loyalty, among the users: some used the service frequently and kept accessing to the platform, while others did not accepted the task in a decisive way. In terms of distribution, a general growth in usage can be seen throughout the study, following the increase of patient inclusion.

Results in Italy

Figure 43. Results in Italy

Results in Spain

Figure 44. Results in Spain

Results in Sweden

Figure 45. Results in Sweden

Results in Israel

Figure 46. Results in Israel

TECH KPI004 - Access frequency to Activity Monitoring

Results in Italy

In the Italian site, 34 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Monitoring module at least once and the average patient accessed 16 times during the observed timeframe.

Figure 47. Access proportion

The most of accesses was made by the patients (or their caregivers), indicating a good penetration of the service to the end-user.

Figure 48. Accesses per week by doctors and patients

The access to the module, by both doctors and patients, stays has a regular course, with the exception of the holiday periods.

Results in Sweden

In the Swedish site, 41 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Monitoring module at least once and the average patient accessed 4 times during the observed timeframe.

Figure 49. Access proportion

The accesses scenario is shared between patients (or their caregivers) and doctors.

Figure 50. Accesses per week by doctors and patients

The access to the module, by both doctors and patients, reaches an equilibrium after since August 2017 (week 34).

Results in Spain

In the Spanish site, 33 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Monitoring module at least once and the average patient accessed 6 times during the observed timeframe.

Figure 51. Access proportion

The most of accesses was made by the patients (or their caregivers), indicating a good penetration of the service to the end-user.

Figure 52. Accesses per week by doctors and patients

The access to the module, by both doctors and patients, follows a growth until the end of 2017, though presenting a bending after the advent of the new year.

Results in Israel

In the Israeli site, 13 patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were active in the Activity Monitoring module at least once and the average patient accessed 3 times during the observed timeframe.

Figure 53. Access proportion

The most of accesses was made by doctors. This may be indicative of the fact that the data, presented in that particular way, may have been found more interesting by professionals.

Figure 54. Accesses per week by doctors and patients

The access to the module, by both doctors and patients, has a peak corresponding to the start of the study, to then settle at a nearly uniform trend, until an overall abandonment towards the end of the study.

Overall usage and considerations

It is important to underline that the nature of the Activity Report module does not require frequent access in the short term. In fact, the data is a cumulative collection of small fragments of information, which acquire meaning only to a vision of ample time space.

Figure 55. Calculations made during the observed timeframe

Figure 55 shows the trend of calculation requests for actimetry reports and subsequent visualization for each country, highlighting an overall sustained use, more distributed over time in Italy and Israel, and more oriented toward viewing periods in Spain and Sweden.

TECH_KPI005 - Usage of Activity Monitoring sensor

The device used to monitor patients' activity through the intervention period was able to collect steps and activity levels, among the detection of falls, indoor/outdoor and immobility.

Only patients belonging to group 2 (full intervention) were given the Adamo watch and the transmitting base.

The considered parameters are as follows:

1. For each site, both usage and recorded activity levels are considered.
2. The Usage during trial is reported by means of graphs by userID. Its meaning is the percentage of time during which the watch has been worn. 50% means that the watch has been worn for 50% of time.
3. The mean activity level distribution during trial reports the percentage of the different activity levels: very low (VL), low (L), medium (M), high (H) and very high

(VH). Those levels are meant “mean” since they represent average measurements computed from the activity level distribution per each user.

- The percentage is the percentage of time for each activity level. 50% of VL means that 50% of time has been spent in VL activity (sleep, for instance).

The considered timeframes are as follows:

- Overall period is the whole monitoring period
- Baseline is represented by the first 15 days from the first worn packet received from a watch
- End of Study (EoS) is represented by the last 15 days of monitoring until the last worn packet received from a watch.

It is important to consider that some patients wearing the watch did not finished the intervention at data extraction time, so conclusions could be different while considering the study end.

Results in Italy

In the Italian site, the watch usage was relevant. Some watches were even used twice since the number of patients was higher than the number of available watches. Only 1 out of 24 was unused by the patient.

Figure 56. Watch usage

Most of the users wore the watch for less than the 70% of the time: that means that patients generally preferred to unworn the watch during night-time or while resting.

Figure 57. Mean distribution of activity levels during trial

The comparison between the baseline and the end of study shows that the activity level ratio did not increase at the end of the study, as instead happened in Spain and Sweden. This fact can depend on several factors; among them the overall higher age of the Italian patients and the bad weather in northern Italy during this spring may have had a strong impact, since it may have reduced the outdoor activity during the end of Study of the selected patients. Moreover, the stability in the activity level over time could be interpreted as in line with the stability in the BADL (as physical activity has high impact), though this can only be formulated as hypothesis as there is no way to compare data with control group or intervention group 1, where BADL decreased over time.

Results in Sweden

In the Swedish site, the watch usage was relevant.

Figure 58. Watch usage

Most of the users worn the watch for more than the 70% of the time: that means that they wore it even during night time or while sleeping or resting.

The graphs comprise also two dropout patients (DECI023 and DECI165). User DECI065 usage is low due to many journeys where he could not use the Adamo kit.

Figure 59. Mean distribution of activity levels during trial

The comparison between the baseline and the end of study shows that the activity level ratio increases at the end of the study. The percentage of high activity levels is higher at the end of the study; it can be considered as an achievement due to the physical and mental training.

Results in Spain

In the Spanish site, the watch usage was relevant: only 3 kits out of 19 were unused, of which one of them was damaged and another had battery problems.

Figure 60. Watch usage

Most of the users wore the watch for less than the 70% of the time: that means that patients generally preferred to unworn the watch during night-time or while resting.

Figure 61. Mean distribution of activity levels during trial

As in Sweden, the comparison between the baseline and the end of study shows that the activity level ratio increases at the end of the study. The percentage of high activity levels is higher at the end of the study; it can be considered as an achievement due to the physical and mental training.

Results in Israel

Usage of the watch in Israel was lower and statistics are not particularly relevant.

Figure 62. Watch usage

Figure 63. Mean distribution of activity levels during trial

Due to the few received data, no trend in the activity recordings can be detected, neither it's possible to understand if there is an index of abandonment of the device, given the lack of correlation.

Technical stability of the system

TECH KPI006 - Bug fixing and maintenance support

During the DECI system service, a issue tracker platform was used, to collect bug reports and requests for assistance. All issues were collected directly from the reporters, who were in charge to determine severity and priority; this means that the issues reported are most of the time to be read with a subjective view and must be considered as general indicators of perceived stability.

Figure 64. Distribution of issues reported

The figure 64 is indicator of that behaviour: of 124 reports, 53 were real and verified issues.

In the graphs the “not fixable” and “no change required” issues were related to requirements not met and the duplicate to bugs yet reported, while the others were temporary problems (mostly not reproducible). All verified issues were fixed.

Figure 65. Distribution over time of issue reports

Most issues were reported exactly in correspondence with the opening of the sites and the trend descends quickly up to the middle of the study. Also perceived problems (summed up with the real issues, in light blue) follows the same course.

Figure 66. Distribution over modules of issue reports

The distribution of issues reported between the modules is even, with the exception of the Integrated platform: the latter, in fact, being collector of user accesses, primary and connection point of the other modules has suffered from his role, showing a higher number of reports.

TECH KPI007 - Service uptime

To calculate this KPI, the Microsoft Event Viewer System Logs were used. Due to the system log limit, logs before around October 2017 were lost for Israel and Sweden. For Spain and Italy, all relevant logs were collected. In most cases, downtimes of the different services are (almost) equal. Here, the times at which the services were down coincide. In some cases, one service was down for longer than the others. So, for total downtime, we took the downtime of the service with the longest downtime.

Figure 67. Service uptime detected by the systems

For Israel, there has been 5 days downtime for most processes, mostly on October 4th and 8th.

Sweden had only about 3 ½ days of downtime around October 14th. Note however that data before Oct 12th is missing.

Spain has only about 4 hours of downtime (November 27th).

Italy only has 13 hours of downtime (January 4th-5th).

A summary of uptimes is given in the following graph (this does not include SmartBrain system).

Figure 68. Overall complete system downtime

Please note the some of the downtimes considered might concern only small parts of the whole system, resulting in a partial disservice.

Conclusions

Individual KPIs have their overall considerations section, whenever the data was comparable. In most of the cases, the differences in the approach with patients and the protocol deviations led to the need to differ the single analysis of each module. All collected usages, with a few exceptions, are highlighting a good level of penetration for a digital solution in intervention, though with an overall sense of slow progression. Those difficulties here might be seen only as discrete data in mere usage and load but can be related to those listed in the Sites' pilot reports described in WP5.

A new experimentation similar to DECI, of a follow-up of it, might need a complete list of **comparable** requirements, as a defined precise number of enrollments and obligatory fixed processes, following a stricter and contemporaneous timeline.

5.3 Safety, ethical, legal and social perspectives

Ethical aspects

In all pilot sites, none of the patients had concerns about their activity levels being monitored by healthcare professionals. As one patient stated, *"It makes me feel calm to know that there is someone who knew how I feel"*, or *"I felt protected rather than controlled"*, the statements implying that there are patients that actually would prefer being observed by healthcare, compared to current state of care.

The patients were also concerned about the self-image that a physical activity training program and the activity monitoring sensor (the watch) creates. For example, the single respondent from the Spanish site emphasized that the physical training system did not match his needs, since he does not consider himself old.

Regarding the watch, the healthcare professionals in Italy reported that some patients from Italy felt the watch makes them look sick and that patients are hesitant to wear the watch in the social gatherings, such as church activities. Such view was supported by the information received from the healthcare professionals in Sweden. They have reported patient feedback regarding the watch: *"No, am I supposed to wear one of those? I will look like I'm sick?"* and *"I will not wear this, I have never worn a watch in my entire life...and to wear this one when I'm in the gym..."*. Also, the design of the watch was perceived as too youthful (Italy) and not age-appropriate. All these observations indicate that image can influence willingness to adopt the technology. Additionally, one Spanish patient expressed: *"I don't really need to be monitored. I don't have medical problems that require close monitoring"*, indicating that perception of own condition can also influence willingness to adopt the technology.

Safety aspects

- Physical training program: One Italian and one Swedish healthcare professionals emphasized that physical training without supervision potentially can lead to harm in older population: “...Some moves in the platform are not safe for these patients and puts a lot of pressure on them”. This opinion was supported by a feedback from one patient stating that it would have been useful to have some kind of interaction with clinicians when performing different activities. An interaction in order to secure that performed exercises were done in a proper and harmless way.
- Activity monitoring sensor: Two patients have reported allergic reactions to nickel and plastic from wearing the Activity monitoring sensor – the Adamo watch. For one Italian patient this even affected the results: “...I had trouble with my skin because I have a lot of allergies and then especially at the beginning I removed it quite frequently and I put it on a little”.
- Further, when studying the causes behind the drop-outs from the DECI study, no patients described safety-related reasons for abandoning the study.

Legal aspects

The legal aspects of DECI are discussed in the documents of WP2 and WP7 D7.1 “IPR protection”).

Social aspects

The social aspects analysed in DECI related to the informal caregiver’s burden and responsibility to handle while taking care of MCI or MD patient. Caregiver’s burden analysis showed better results in the intervention groups compared to the control group, while analysis for other pilot sites did not yield significant results.

In terms of patient roles and changes in capabilities, the patient interview analysis revealed that patients using DECI solution (especially with ICT functionalities) felt more empowered to take action against chronic illness, in order to maintain or improve the condition. In the same way, healthcare professionals felt empowered by having tools to provide their patients for maintenance of the condition. However, DECI solution raised expectations to the healthcare system. A new function of IT helpdesk for patients was mentioned as a need by the majority of patients in a need of IT support or in case of system instability.

5.4 Business perspective

5.4.1 Process effectiveness perspective

Overall, all KPIs presented in the methodology were assessed for each group and Pilot, as shown in the table below.

KPI	Item	CG	GR1	GR2
Responsiveness	R1 Number of contacts between the patient and the clinical personnel (and viceversa) –and waiting time (on the platform)			
	R2 Number of contacts between the patient and the clinical personnel (and viceversa) –and waiting time (outside the platform)			
	T2 Average time spent for the assistance in back office by the clinical personnel of DECI project (e.g. answers to messages)			
Healthcare resources	H1 Number of visits per type			
Assistance time	T1 Average time spent for the assistance in the presence by the clinical personnel of DECI project (e.g. visits, calls)			
Collaboration	C1 Numbers of team meetings involving clinical personnel (for each patient)			
	C2 Average time spent in multidisciplinary team meetings			
	C3 Number of participant per professional category involved in multidisciplinary team meetings			
Planning	P1 Number of revised physical training program			
	P2 Number of revised cognitive games			
	P3 Number of planned/unplanned calls			
	P4 Number of unplanned clinical visits performed			
	P5 Average time spent for the definition of treatment plans			
	P6 Average time spent for the revision of treatment plans			

Table 53. KPIs assessed in each group

The table below shows all patients included in the analysis. It must be noted that for organizational KPI's perspective all patients included in the DECI program has been considered, thus both those whose finished their study period within the end of May as well as those still active in the program.

Pilot	Israel			Italy			Spain			Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2
Total patients included	22	17	24	51	54	56	37	35	38	55	58	60

Table 54. Total patients included

Responsiveness – Contacts

The table below shows the main results elaborated considering the contacts occurred between clinicians and patients and their respective waiting time.

Pilot	Israel			Italy			Spain			Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2
On the platform												
Sample		8	2		7	7		9	16		0	0
Messages		1,11	1		2,11	2,83		2,11	2,47		0	0
Average waiting time (hours)		0,029	0,03		44,54	23,88		43,26	51,1		-	-
Outside the platform												
Sample				51	53	56				5	23	21
Mobile phone				0,078	0,33	1,81				0	0	0
Phone				0,019	0,015	1,94				2,4	4,39	6,33
Average Waiting time Phone (min)				-	0	57,6				-	-	-
Mail				0,019	0,11	0,017				0	0	1
Average Waiting time mail (days)				-	0	14				-	-	-
Sms/whatsapp				0	0,18	0,092				0	0	0,86
Average time spent in back office (min)	60	300		0	12,5		0	3		60	240	

Table 55. Contacts

Considering contact on the platform, it can be noted that HUG (Spain) and FDG (Italy) are the most active clinical centres, even if the number of patients involved at least in one message on the platform is quite low in every sites. This is since patients in Intervention 1 group had no other occasions to use the tablet, thus reducing the opportunity to use it to contact their clinicians alternatively to other traditional methods (phone, mails, etc.). Intervention 2 group appears as the most suitable patients to use this functionality and in

effect the average number of contact between clinicians and patients is slightly higher for GR2. On average, intervention 1 group patients wait 2 days to receive an answer from their clinician/case manager while in FDG intervention 2 group patients wait one day less.

Considering contacts outside the platform, FDG and VGR (Sweden) are the only clinical sites to report messages (mail or SMS/Whatsapp) or call phones with patients. For FDG the number of contacts is irrelevant with respect to control group and intervention 1 group while there is a more constant pattern with intervention 2 group patients with more than 1 call phone on average per patient during the study period.

Interesting to note that in Sweden, call phones are a relevant part of the intervention for all groups. This is due to the peculiar organizational model that characterise VGR clinical site and that includes the presence of the “mobile team” which is in constant relation with patients. This model results in an average number of more than 2 phone calls for control group patients, then double (4,39) for intervention 1 group and then rise until an average of 6,33 calls for intervention 2 group.

As obvious, average time spent by clinicians/case managers for back-office activities (such as answering messages, call patients, etc.) is higher in Sweden if compared to Italy or Spain.

Healthcare resources/assistance time – Visits

The table below shows the main results elaborated considering the visits and their respective duration occurred to patients during the study period.

Pilot	Israel			Italy			Spain			Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2
Sample	19	15	22	51	54	57	37	35	38	5	23	21
Average visits per patient	28,9	33	34	3,53	3,50	7,36	1	1	1	4	5	5
Average time spent to visit (h)	-	-	-	1,24	1,32	1,38	3	3	3	0,96	0,98	0,98
Visitcount	373	376	519	124	145	193	37	35	38	20	115	105
VisitAvgduration (Hours)	-	-	-	1,04	0,92	1,13	3	3	3	0,9	0,9	0,9
Test (Count)	45	30	66	19	15	37	0	0	0	5	23	21
Test Avgduration (Hours)	-	-	-	2,55	4,9	3,74	-	-	-	1	1	1
Tech Assistance (Count)	0	0	0	1	15	32	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tech Assistance Avg duration (Hours)	-	-	-	1	1,41	0,91	-	-	-	-	-	-
OtherVisitCount	131	89	174	4	1	4	0	0	0	10	38	40
Other Visit Avg duration (Hours)	-	-	-	1,75	3	2,63	-	-	-	2	1,65	1,9

Table 56. Visits

Results are the expression of different levels of clinical knowledge associated to patients in each Country, mostly due to differences in Hospital Information System. In fact, it appears evident that Israel has a lot of knowledge referred to their patients: all clinical events occurred to patients are registered in their Electronic Medical Record and accessible to different healthcare structures all over the Country. This allowed Maccabi to gather a lot of information: from hospital admissions to GP consults. From the table it also appears evident that each patient had an incredibly number of visits during the study period: on average 28,9 visits for CG patients, 33 visits for GR1 and 34 for GR2. If we compare these results with Italy, it can be found a lower frequency of visits: on average 3,53 visits for CG, 3,50 visits for GR1, 7,36 visits for GR2. In Israel and Italy, the visits referred to the study protocol considered among these data are 2 (inclusion visit and

discharge visit), this means that the rest is extra visits required to address specific clinical conditions of patients. Instead, in VGR (Sweden) and HUG (Spain) all visits included in this analysis are compliant to their study protocol. This is mostly due to the fact that in Sweden and Spain it was not possible to automatically gather all clinical events referred to each patient outside DECI program. Any other clinical events occurred has to be directly asked to the patients and this was possible only for a small number of patients (those who finished the intervention period).

In the table, counts on clinical visits, test and laboratory exams, technical assistance and other visits (specialist, GP, ER, etc.) were reported with the average duration time (whenever possible).

Planning

The table below shows the main results elaborated considering the unexpected events requiring extra effort for clinical site to address needs of the patients during the study period. These events mainly refer to calls, visits and care plans.

Pilot	Israel			Italy			Spain			Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2
Sample	22	17	24	51	54	57	37	35	38	55	58	60
Plannedcalls (average)	0,18	1,94	3,29	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Unplannedcalls (average)	0	0,12	0,67	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Extra visits (average)												0,86
Average time spent to define care plans			6 min			30 min			105 min			30 min
Revision of physicalactivities			-			0,02			0			-
Revision of cognitive games (average)			-			0,04			2			-
Average time spent to update care plans			-			15 min			18 min			-

Table 57. Planning results

Results are affected by the opportunity for each clinical site to keep track of these information which are not standard and unexpected – *by definition*. Numbers here are very small but some considerations can be drawn as well. For instance, Maccabi (Israel) registered a small amount of unplanned calls especially addressed to Intervention 2 group patients while VGR (Sweden) encountered extra visits on the same group, in particular on average 0,86 extra visits per patient of GR2 were necessary to address clinical issue.

With respect to the definition of the care plan, this activity has to be done only for Intervention 2 group patients and includes the assignment of a certain amount and type of physical exercises and cognitive exercises to be executed through the tablet. Each clinician at the beginning of the intervention defines the care plan for each GR2 patient. Effort here is quite variable among Pilots: Maccabi employs very little time (6 minutes on average) because it has automatized the possible options to be selected to compose the care plan. FDG and VGR spent 30 minutes each to define care plans for their patients whereas HUG employs more than 1 hour and a half because they conduct this activity together with patients, thus also training them.

During the study period, some updates were registered with respect to the defined care plan, thus requiring extra effort. Actually, revisions were reported only by FDG (Italy) and HUG (Spain) and with a very low frequency, in particular: on average clinicians of FGD updated physical exercises assigned to GR2 patients 0,02 times per patient and cognitive games 0,04 times per patient. HUG updated only cognitive games but on average 2 times for each patient. This means that each patient in GR2 has received an updated version of his/her care plan with a different schedule of cognitive games. The update of care plans in both cases requires about 15-18 minutes.

Collaboration - Multidisciplinary team meetings

The table below shows the main results elaborated considering the multidisciplinary team meetings, which are a form of coordination that involves different professionals' figures involved in the treatment of patients to discuss the clinical status of their patients and further actions required to address their needs.

Pilot	Israel			Italy			Spain			Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2	CG	GR1	GR2
Total Meetings	-	-	-	30			-	-	-	38		
Average Number of Patients	-	-	-	1,8			-	-	-	5,42		
% of DECI patients discussed	-	-	-	3,9%	18,5%	48,2%	-	-	-	0	98%	100%
Total num of Patients Involved in Meeting	-	-	-	2	10	28	-	-	-	0	57	60
Average number of meetings per group				1	1,60	1,28				0	1,68	1,75
Average time duration meetings (hours)	-	-	-	1	0,65	0,87	-	-	-	0	3,78	3,81

Table 58. Multidisciplinary team meetings results

First, it has to be noted that only FDG (Italy) and VGR (Sweden) lead multidisciplinary team meetings. Comparing their results two different organizational models appear. In fact, FDG conducted 30 meetings discussing on average 1,8 patients while VGR on a total of 38 meetings discussed on average 5,42 patients. Duration also varies ranging from less than 1 hour in FDG to more than 3 hours in VGR. Another difference lies in the total number of patients discussed: in fact, VGR discussed all patients included in DECI program except for Control group, while FDG discussed only a smaller number of patients with a prevalence of Intervention 2 group patients (48%). Also, it is interesting to note the frequency – on average – of discussion of 1 patients in a meeting based on his/her group. With respect to FDG, each Control group patients was discussed on average in 1 meeting, while the more frequently discussed patients were those belonging to Intervention 1 group (1,60 meetings per each patient), followed by Intervention 2 group (1,28 meetings per each patient). In VGR frequency for GR1 is similar (1,68 meeting per each patient), whereas for GR2 a higher number of meetings per each patient were registered (1,70).

The tables below specify the effort required from each professional figure involved in the multidisciplinary team meetings.

Pilot	Italy		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2
Geriatrician N meetings	11		
Geriatrician Avg Time	0,63 h		
Geriatrician per Group	1	0	10
Case manager N meetings	28		
Case manager Avg Time	0,6 h		
Case Manager per group	1	4	26
Neuropsychologist N meetings	21		
Neuropsychologist Avg Time	0,75 h		
Neuropsychologist Per group	0	4	17
Psychologist N meetings	1		
Psychologist Avg Time	0,25 h		
Psychologist per group	0	1	0
Social Worker N meetings	1		
Social Worker Avg Time	1 h		
Social Worker per group	0	1	0

Pilot	Sweden		
Group	CG	GR1	GR2
Geriatrician N meetings	38		
Geriatrician Avg Time	3,79		
Geriatrician per group	0	57	60
Occupational Therapeut N meetings	38		
Occupational Therapeut Avg Time	3,79		
Occupational Therapeut pergroup	0	57	60
Physiotherapist N meetings	38		
Physiotherapist Avg Time	3,79		
Physiotherapist pergroup	0	57	60
Nurse N meetings	38		
Nurse Avg Time	3,79		
Nurse per group	0	57	60

Table 59. Time spent in multi-disciplinary team meetings

The composition of the multidisciplinary teams varies among the two Pilots. For FDG five different professionals are involved (i.e.: geriatrician, case manager, neuropsychologist,

psychologist, social worker) while for VGR four are the figures involved (i.e.: geriatrician, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, nurse). These figures in VGR are always involved in each multidisciplinary meeting thus in total they attended 38 meetings for more than 3 hours on average. In FDG not all the professional figures were involved in each meeting. In particular, geriatrician, case manager and neuropsychologist were involved mostly in meeting where GR2 patients were discussed, while psychologist and social worker were involved in the discussion on GR1 patients. Case manager and neuropsychologist participated in a higher number of meetings – respectively 28 and 21 – with an average time of 35 minutes the case manager and 45 minutes the neuropsychologist.

Conclusions

Considering the objectives of the analysis, results show that in FDG (Italy) through the use of the DECI platform the frequency of contacts between clinicians and patients increased and the response time of the various actors decreased. Thus, **responsiveness** is confirmed to increase for Intervention 2 group patients, with an average waiting time of 24 hours with respect to about 44 hours for Intervention 1 group patients. **Healthcare resources** and the **time spent by professionals** were affected by Intervention 2 group patients that needed more effort in terms of assistance (visits, calls, etc.). Also **planning** results as a residual activity for control group patients and intervention 1 group patients whereas it was a substantial part of the intervention for the second group of patients receiving DECI platform. Opposing results refer to the area of **collaboration**: in FDG (Italy) the effort spent to discuss patients during multidisciplinary meeting decrease for Interventions 2 group patients while in VGR it increases.

5.4.2 Cost-minimisation analysis

Willingness to pay

In total, 101 patients filled in the WTP questionnaire of which 48 in intervention group 1 and 53 in intervention group 2. Age and gender are evenly distributed among groups.

Patients		Intervention group 1 (n=48)	Intervention group 2 (n=53)
Gender	Male	20	24
	Female	28	29
Age		76.9	76.1

Table 60. Patient characteristics WTP questionnaire

For informal caregivers there were 37 in total, of which 16 in intervention group 1 and 21 in intervention group 2 who filled in the WTP questionnaire. Table 56 and 57 shows the characteristics of both groups. There were more female caregivers than male and most of the caregivers were a child of the patient (n=24) or a spouse (n=12). Most caregivers lived together with the patient (n=13) or within less than 20 minutes 'drive (n=18) and cared for their patient between 1-5 years.

Caregivers		Intervention group 1 (n=16)	Intervention group 2 (n=21)
Gender	Male	6	3
	Female	10	18
Age		20.4	24.5
Relation to patient	Child	15	9
	Spouse	3	9
	Sibling	-	1
Distance from patient	Living together with the patient	2	11
	Living within less than 20 minutes' drive	10	8
	Living within more than 20 minutes' drive	2	-
Time caring	Less than 1 year	-	1
	Between 1-5 years	10	13
	More than 5 years	4	5

Table 61. Caregiver characteristics WTP questionnaire

Most of the caregivers (61%) and patients (56%) would like to continue using DECI after the projects' end, showing they are quite positive about the DECI platform. In total, 23 caregivers (74%) were positive about DECI and recommend it to others, compared to 8 who did not. Especially, caregivers in group were highly positive regarding the recommendation to others. Italy was the pilot site who recruited the most caregivers next to the patients. In the other pilot sites, it is not that common to have informal caregiving for the patients.

In the patient group, similar results were found, 64% of the patients would recommend DECI to others. Patients in intervention group 2 were more positive to recommend DECI to others, compared to intervention group 1.

Would you recommend DECI to others?			
		Yes	No
Caregivers	Total	23	8
	Italy	20	7
	Sweden	-	-
	Spain	2	-
	Israel	1	1
	Intervention group 1	8	5
	Italy	7	5
	Sweden	-	-
	Spain	1	-
	Israel	-	-
	Intervention group 2	15	3
	Italy	13	2
	Sweden	-	-
	Spain	1	-
	Israel	1	1
Patients	Total	41	23
	Italy	18	10
	Sweden	13	7
	Spain	3	1
	Israel	7	5
	Intervention group 1	7	10
	Italy	4	7
	Sweden	-	-
	Spain	1	1
	Israel	2	2
	Intervention group 2	34	13
	Italy	14	3
	Sweden	13	7
	Spain	2	-
	Israel	5	3

Table 62: Recommendation of DECI

Most of the patients and caregivers were not willing to pay for DECI. In Italy and Israel, patients were willing to pay more each month compared to Sweden. Patients in the

intervention group 2 were much more willing to pay than patients in intervention group 1.

Would you be willing to pay for DECI?				
		Yes	How much? (euros)	No
Caregivers	Total	14		17
	Italy	13	€39,- (n=13)	14
	Sweden	-	-	-
	Spain	1	-	1
	Israel	-	-	2
	Intervention group 1	2		11
	Italy	2		10
	Sweden	-		-
	Spain	-		1
	Israel	-		-
	Intervention group 2	12		6
	Italy	11		4
	Sweden	-		-
	Spain	1		-
	Israel	-		2
	Patients	Total	19	
Italy		11	€53 (Italy) (n=14)	17
Sweden		4	€6 (Sweden) (n=3)	16
Spain		2	-	2
Israel		2	€55 (Israel) (n=3)	10
Intervention group 1		2		15
Italy		2		9
Sweden		-		-
Spain		-		2
Israel		-		4
Intervention group 2		17		30
Italy		9		8
Sweden		4		16
Spain		2		-
Israel	2		6	

Table 563: Willingness to pay

No correlations were found between different characteristics of the patient and/or caregiver and the willingness to pay. The only correlation found was between willingness to pay and recommendation to others for both patients (Pearson correlation .487) and for caregivers (Pearson correlation .559).

Cost-Analysis results in Italy

In total, there are 64 finished patients with data about the health care consumption. In total, 37 specialists were involved in the care of patients participating in the DECI study. We merged those specialists to 6 main specialists involved. Hours of care per patient increases in intervention group 1 and 2 compared to the control groups. Hours of the nurse are less in the intervention groups and there are no hours for the technician in intervention group 2 for the technician. However, hours for the case manager increases. When calculating costs for the different groups, these also increases for the intervention groups, with the highest amount of costs per patient in the intervention group 2.

Italy		Hours of care per patient			Costs of care per patient (euros)		
Specialist	Tariff	Control group (n=26)	Intervention group 1 (n=17)	Intervention group 2 (n=21)	Control group (n=26)	Intervention group 1 (n=17)	Intervention group 2 (n=21)
Doctor	37	2,19	2,69	4,53	81,03	99,68	167,53
Psychologist	25	0,32	0,77	1,30	8	19,12	32,41
Nurse	18	0,62	0,03	0,44	11,16	0,53	8
Physiotherapist	24	0,48	0	0,89	11,52	0	21,33
Technician	21	0,98	2,53	0	20,58	53,12	0
Case manager	22,5	0	0,66	1,35	0	14,89	30,42
Hours of care per patient		4,59	6,68	8,51			
Total costs per patient (euro)					€132,29	€187,34	€259,69

Table 64. Cost results in Italy

Cost-Analysis results in Sweden

In total, there are 49 finished patients with data about the health care consumption. In Sweden, four specialists are involved in the care of patients. The hours of a nurse are the highest in all groups. The hours of care per patient increases in the intervention groups, which is also shown in the average amount of costs per patient, being the highest in the intervention group 2.

Sweden		Hours of care per patient			Costs of care per patient (euros)		
Specialist	Tariffs	Control group (n=5)	Intervention group 1 (n=23)	Intervention group 2 (n=21)	Control group (n=5)	Intervention group 1 (n=23)	Intervention group 2 (n=21)
Assistant nurse/casemanager	26	0,5	0,5	0,5	13	13	13
Physician	61	2,5	2,15	2,41	152,5	131,28	146,69
Geriatrician	84	2	3	3	168	252	252
Nurse	34	4	4,65	4,91	136	158,17	166,76
Hours of care per patient		9	10.3	10.8			
Total costs per patient					€469,50	€555,90	€578,00

Table 65. Cost results in Sweden

Cost-Analysis results in Spain

In total, there are 12 finished patients with data about the health care consumption. In Spain, three specialists are involved in the care of patients. Hours of care from the geriatrician and the nurse increases in the intervention group 2, due to making the treatment plan for this group and teaching patients how to use it. Also, the costs per patient increases as such, with the highest costs in the intervention group 2.

Spain		Hours of care per patient			Costs of care per patient (euros)		
Specialist	Tariffs	Control group (n=5)	Intervention group 1 (n=4)	Intervention group 2 (n=3)	Control group (n=5)	Intervention group 1 (n=4)	Intervention group 2 (n=3)
Neuropsychologist	25	4	4	4	222	222	276.40
Geriatrician	21.28	2	2	4.65			
Nurse	13.37	-	1	1,5		13.37	20.05
Hours of care per patient							
Total costs per patient (euro)					€222,-	€235,37	€296,45

Table 66. Cost results in Spain

Cost-Analysis results in Israel

In total, there are 13 finished patients with data about the health care consumption. In Israel, a total amount of 21 specialists were involved in the care of patient. We merged them into 6 different specialists. The hours of a nurse and occupational therapists decreases in the intervention groups, but increases for the technician and the physiotherapist, especially in intervention group 2. The hours for a doctor decreases in intervention group 1 and increases for intervention group 2. Also, the costs per patient in intervention group 2 are the highest. However, number of patients in each group is very low.

Israel		Hours of care per patient			Costs of care per patient (euros)		
Specialist	Tariffs	Control group (n=1)	Group 1 (n=4)	Group 2 (n=8)	Control group (n=1)	Group 1 (n=4)	Group 2 (n=8)
Doctor	40	6,75	3,31	7,59	270	132,50	303,75
Nurse	18	1,75	0,25	0,97	31,5	4,5	17,44
Technician	21	0	0,25	0,5	0	5,25	10,5
Physiotherapist	35	0	0,19	1,09	0	6,56	38,28
Social worker	18	0	0	0,06	0	0	1,13
Occupational therapist	25	0,5	0,31	0,16	12,50	7,81	3,90
Hours of care per patient		9	4,31	10,38			
Total costs per patient (euro)					€314	€156,62	€374,99

Table 67. Cost results in Israel

Cross-case comparison

Healthcare consumption is differently organized in the different countries. This implies that there is no one size fits all implementation strategy for DECI, which should be taken into account. Also, the WTP is different between sites, as in Sweden patients are not used to paying for their health services as for Italy and Israel this might be more common.

Conclusion

Patients and caregivers were positive about DECI, but most of them were not willing to pay for it. This is important to take into consideration when developing the business case for DECI. Patients in intervention group 2 were more positive about DECI, as they probably felt like they received something in return from the platform. Health care consumption increases in the intervention groups. However, the number of finished patients is low which makes comparisons between groups and sites difficult.

6 Conclusions

This document outlined the assessment methodology and results of the DECI project. The described results will provide the informational basis for deliverables “D6.2 – A business case” and “D6.3 – Exploitation plan” that discusses transferability and exploitation potential of results and lessons learned.

Domain	Expected result	Summary of the results
Clinical perspective		
Quality of Life	For Intervention group 2, stable or increased perceived quality of life is expected. Group mean index value is expected to be higher than for Intervention group 1 and Control group. For Intervention group 1, stable or increased perceived quality of life is expected. Group mean index value is expected to be higher than for Control group. For Control group patients, no change in quality of life index value is expected.	Statistically significant better result in group 1 in comparison to control group. No statistically significant results for group 2.
Cognitive performance	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of MMSE score in terms of group mean is by 0-3 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, expected worse or stable performance. Mean decrease of group score by 0-4 points.	No effect on global cognition was found.
	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of score in terms of group mean is by 0-1 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.	
Autonomy	For all groups, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.	Group 2 present more stability in BADL over time. DECI could be a promising approach to delay BADL worsening in elderly people at the first stages of cognitive impairment.
	For Intervention group 2, stable or better performance is expected. Increase of score in terms of group mean is by 0-2 points from baseline to end of pilot. For Intervention group 1 and Control group, stable performance is expected. No change in mean group score.	

Patient satisfaction	Group 2 and group 1 patients will be satisfied with the received DECI care and will be willing to use DECI solution in the future.	Positive outlook to professionals who delivered care, appreciation for case manager and ICT solutions (especially cognitive and physical training programs). Patients expressed willingness to use DECI in the future.
Informal caregiver perspective		
Caregiver burden	Intervention group 2 caregivers are expected to report reduced burden in comparison to Intervention group 1 and Control group. Intervention group 1 caregivers are expected to report reduced or stable burden compared with Control group.	The expected result was satisfied in Spanish site with statistical significance.
Healthcare professional perspective		
Healthcare professional's satisfaction	Healthcare professionals will be satisfied with the provided care and will positively perceive the DECI business model and will be willing to use DECI solution in the future.	The overall perception in all countries was positive and professionals expressed willingness to use DECI in the future. However, workload increased in all sites.
Safety, ethical, legal and social aspects		
Safety	DECI solution will be safe for the studied population.	Physical training program might be less safe for older population. Activity monitoring sensor caused allergic reactions to few patients.
Ethical aspects	DECI solution and study does not violate ethical principles.	Activity monitoring sensor can create an image of a sick person. But patients appreciated being monitored.
Legal aspects	N/A	Discussed in WP2 and WP7 D7.1.
Social aspects	Patients in Group 2 and 1 will be more empowered using DECI solution. Healthcare professionals will be more empowered using DECI solution. Caregiver's burden will decrease for group 2 and group 1 patients.	Lesser caregiver's burden in Spain for the intervention groups compared to control group. More empowered patients and healthcare professionals.
Technology perspective		
System usage and stability	Good penetration of DECI solution will be achieved.	Good penetration of DECI solution was achieved in the group 2 and group 1. However, an overall sense of progression was slow. Stability of the system was ensured after the initial bugs of implementation and integration have been resolved.
Business perspective		

Process effectiveness perspective	<p>DECI solution will improve effectiveness, efficiency and governance within healthcare structures, from an organizational point of view, respectively by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving responsiveness of the contacts between clinicians and patients in case of need • Reducing unnecessary consumption of healthcare resources and better allocating assistance time on added value activities • Improving collaboration within healthcare providers <p>Supporting better planning of treatment care plan.</p>	<p>Increased responsiveness in group 2. More healthcare resources needed to assist patients. In Italy, time for collaboration decreased, while in Sweden increased.</p>
Cost-minimisation perspective	<p>We expect healthcare consumption to be organized differently in the different groups, with on the long-term lower health care costs in intervention group 1 and 2 compared to the control group.</p>	<p>Health care consumption increases in the intervention groups. Patients and caregivers were positive about DECI, but most of them were not willing to pay for it.</p>

In conclusion, we can say that a good level of ICT penetration was achieved or a digital solution in the intervention groups, though with an overall sense of slow progression. During 6 months of intervention, Group 2 patients demonstrated more stability in Basic activity of daily living (BADL), and the clinical responsiveness for the patient contact has increased. Moreover, the results related to cognitive performance and autonomy have been discussed in relation to other studies (see chapters 5.1.2.6 and 5.1.3.6). While some patients in Control group mentioned a lack of integration in the care system (Italy), Group 1 and 2 patients appreciated the case manager's role. Group 1 patients showed improved Quality of Life. Most of the studied patient groups demonstrated positive satisfaction with the care received. Most of the patients were willing to use DECI in the future. Similarly, all the healthcare professionals involved in DECI care have been highly positive about using DECI model in the future.

The results should be further explored with the full sample of the recruited patients in the DECI study.

7 References

Alzheimer's Association. (2016). 2016 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 12(4), 459-509.

American Psychiatric Association (2013). *DSM-5: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, 5th ed. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association.

Arrighi, H. M., Gélinas, I., McLaughlin, T. P., Buchanan, J., & Gauthier, S. (2013). Longitudinal changes in functional disability in Alzheimer's disease patients. *International Psychogeriatrics*, 25(6), 929-937.

Astell, A. J., Ellis, M. P., Bernardi, L., Alm, N., Dye, R., Gowans, G., & Campbell, J. (2010). Using a touch screen computer to support relationships between people with dementia and caregivers. *Interacting with Computers*, 22(4), 267-275.

Bahar-Fuchs, A., Clare, L., & Woods, B. (2013). Cognitive training and cognitive rehabilitation for mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 6. Art.No.: CD003260.

Baumgart, M., Snyder, H. M., Carrillo, M. C., Fazio, S., Kim, H., & Johns, H. (2015). Summary of the evidence on modifiable risk factors for cognitive decline and dementia: A population-based perspective. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 11(6), 718-726.

Ben-Sadoun G, Sacco G, Manera V, Bourgeois J, König A, Foulon P, et al. Physical and Cognitive Stimulation Using an Exergame in Subjects with Normal Aging, Mild and Moderate Cognitive Impairment. *J Alzheimer's Dis*. 2016;53(4):1299–314

Bernard, H. R. (2002). *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches* (3rd ed.). Walnut Creek, CA: Alta Mira Press.

Blankevoort, C. G., van Heuvelen, M. J., Boersma, F., Luning, H., de Jong, J., & Scherder, E. J. (2010). Review of effects of physical activity on strength, balance, mobility and ADL performance in elderly subjects with dementia. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 30(5), 392–402.

Brooke, J. (1996). "SUS: a "quick and dirty" usability scale". In P. W. Jordan, B. Thomas, B. A. Weerdmeester, & A. L. McClelland. *Usability Evaluation in Industry*. London: Taylor and Francis.

Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press, USA.

Collin, C., Wade, D. T., Davies, S., & Horne, V. (1988). The Barthel ADL Index: a reliability study. *International disability studies*, 10(2), 61-63.

Cornelis E, Gorus E, Beyer I, Bautmans I, De P. Early diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment and mild dementia through basic and instrumental activities of daily living: Development of a new evaluation tool. 2017;1–22.

Davis, F.D. 1989, "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology", *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 319-340.

Deeken, J.F., Taylor, K.I, Mangan, P et al (2003). Care for the Caregivers: A Review of Self – Report Instruments developed to measure the burden, needs and quality of Life of Informal Caregivers. *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*. 26(4): 922-953.

Di A, Baldereschi M, Lamassa M, Bovis F, Inzitari M. Daily Function as Predictor of Dementia in Cognitive Impairment , No Dementia (CIND) and Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI): An 8-Year Follow-Up in the ILSA Study. 2016;53:505–15.

Farquhar, M. (1995). Elderly people's definitions of quality of life. *Social science & medicine*, 41(10), 1439-1446.

Fleming R, Sum S. Empirical studies on the effectiveness of assistive technology in the care of people with dementia: a systematic review. *J Assist Technol [Internet]*. 2014;8(1):14–34.

Folstein, M. F., Folstein, S. E., &McHugh, P. R. (1975). "Mini-mental state": a practical method for grading the cognitive state of patients for the clinician. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 12(3), 189-198.

Garcia-Casal, J. A., Loizeau, A., Csipke, E., Franco-Martin, M., PereaBartolome, M. V., &Orrell, M. (2017). Computer-based cognitive interventions for people living with dementia: A systematic literature review and meta-analysis. *Aging & Mental Health*, 21(5), 454-467.

Garvin, D.A. 1987, *Competing on the eight dimensions of quality*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston.

Gates, N. J., & Sachdev, P. (2014). Is cognitive training an effective treatment for preclinical and early Alzheimer's disease?. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease*, 42(s4), S551-S559.

Group, T. E. (1990). EuroQol-a new facility for the measurement of health-related quality of life. *Health policy*, 16(3), 199-208.

Hibbard, J. H., Mahoney, E. R., Stockard, J., & Tusler, M. (2005). Development and testing of a short form of the patient activation measure. *Health services research*, 40(6p1), 1918-1930.

Jones, R. N., Marsiske, M., Ball, K., Rebok, G., Willis, S. L., Morris, J. N., & Tennstedt, S. L. (2013). The ACTIVE cognitive training interventions and trajectories of performance among older adults. *Journal of aging and health*, 25(8_suppl), 186S-208S.

Katz, S., Ford, A.B., Moskowitz, R.W., Jackson, B.A., & Jaffe, M.W. (1963). Studies of illness in the aged: The index of ADL: A standardized measure of biological and psychosocial function. *JAMA*, 185(12), 914-919.

Kerssens C, Kumar R, Adams AE, Knott CC, Matalenas L, Sanford J a., et al. Personalized Technology to Support Older Adults With and Without Cognitive Impairment Living at Home. *Am J Alzheimers Dis Other Demen* [Internet]. 2015;30(1):85–97.

Kidholm, K., Ekeland, A. G., Jensen, L. K., Rasmussen, J., Pedersen, C. D., Bowes, A., ... & Bech, M. (2012). A model for assessment of telemedicine applications: mast. *International journal of technology assessment in health care*, 28(01), 44-51.

Lautenschlager, N. T., & Cox, K. L. (2016). Physical activity interventions for mild and major neurocognitive disorders. *Physical Exercise Interventions for Mental Health*, 109.

Lampit, A., Valenzuela, M., & Gates, N. J. (2015). Computerized cognitive training is beneficial for older adults. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 63(12), 2610-2612.

Lawton, M. P., & Brody, E. M. (1969). Assessment of older people: self-maintaining and instrumental activities of daily living. *The gerontologist*, 9(3_Part_1), 179-186.

Li, J., Talaei-Khoei, A., Seale, H., Ray, P., & MacIntyre, C. R. (2013). Health care provider adoption of eHealth: systematic literature review. *Interactive journal of medical research*, 2(1), e7.

Marshall, G. A., Rentz, D. M., Frey, M. T., Locascio, J. J., Johnson, K. A., & Sperling, R. A. (2011). Executive function and instrumental activities of daily living in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & dementia: the journal of the Alzheimer's Association*, 7(3), 300-308.

McAllister, M., Dunn, G., Payne, K., Davies, L., & Todd, C. (2012). Patient empowerment: the need to consider it as a measurable patient-reported outcome for chronic conditions. *BMC health services research*, 12(1), 157.

McDermott, O., Charlesworth, G., Hogervorst, E., Stoner, C., Moniz-Cook, E., Spector, A., Csipke, E., & Orrell, M. (2018). Psychosocial interventions for people with dementia: a synthesis of systematic reviews. *Aging & mental health*, 1-11.

Mitseva, A., Peterson, C., Dafoulas, G., Efthymiou, A., Abildgaard, A., & Bellini, S. (2010). ISISEMD evaluation framework for impact assessment of ICT pilot services for elderly with mild dementia, living in the community and their relatives. *Proceedings of the ASTMA NAEC*, 123-148.

Mowles, C. (2014). Complex, but not quite complex enough: The turn to the complexity sciences in evaluation scholarship. *Evaluation*, 20(2), 160-175.

Murray, E., Burns, J. S. S. T., See, T. S., Lai, R., & Nazareth, I. (2005). Interactive Health Communication Applications for people with chronic disease. *Cochrane database syst rev*, 4.

Ngandu, T., Lehtisalo, J., Solomon, A., Levälähti, E., Ahtiluoto, S., Antikainen, R., ... & Lindström, J. (2015). A 2 year multidomain intervention of diet, exercise, cognitive training, and vascular risk monitoring versus control to prevent cognitive decline in at-risk elderly people (FINGER): a randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 385(9984), 2255-2263.

Norton S, Matthews FE, Barnes DE, Yaffe K, Brayne C. Potential for primary prevention of Alzheimer's disease: an analysis of population-based data. *Lancet Neurol* 2014; 13: 788–94.

Núñez-Naveira L, Alonso-Búa B, de Labra C, Gregersen R, Maibom K, Mojs E, et al. UnderstAID, an ICT Platform to Help Informal Caregivers of People with Dementia: A Pilot Randomized Controlled Study. *Biomed Res Int [Internet]*. 2016;2016:1–13.

Of M, Disorders M. DSM-5.

Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. John Wiley & Sons.

Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method

implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42(5), 533-544.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. & Berry, L.L. 1985, "A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research", *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 41-50.

Petersen, R.C. (2004). Mild cognitive impairment as a diagnostic entity. *Journal of Internal Medicine*, 256, 183-194

Pfeffer, R. I., Kurosaki, T. T., Harrah Jr, C. H., Chance, J. M., &Filos, S. (1982). Measurement of functional activities in older adults in the community. *Journal of gerontology*, 37(3), 323-329.

Pilotto A, D'Onofrio G, Benelli E, Zanesco A, Cabello A, Margelí MC, et al. Information and Communication Technology systems to improve quality of life and safety of Alzheimer's disease patients: A multicenter international survey. *J Alzheimer's Dis*. 2011;23(1):131-41.

Pinto-Bruno AC, García-Casal JA, Csipke E, Jenaro-Río C, Franco-Martín M. ICT-based applications to improve social health and social participation in older adults with dementia. A systematic literature review. 2016;7863(February):1-8.

Powell J, Chiu T, Eysenbach G. Supporting Carers of People With Dementia. 2016;154-6.

RAND, E. (2012). National Evaluation of the DH Integrated Care Pilots. *Rand health quarterly*, 2(1), 8.

Rao, A. K., Chou, A., Bursley, B., Smulofsky, J., &Jezequel, J. (2014). Systematic review of the effects of exercise on activities of daily living in people with Alzheimer's disease. *American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 68(1), 50-56.

Reed C, Belger M, Vellas B, Andrews JS, Argimon JM, Bruno G, et al. Identifying factors of activities of daily living important for cost and caregiver outcomes in Alzheimer ' s disease. 2016;247-59.

Reuzel, R. P. B., Van der Wilt, G. J., Ten Have, H. A. M. J., & de Vries Robbe, P. F. (2001). Interactive technology assessment and wide reflective equilibrium. *Journal of Medicine and Philosophy*, 26(3), 245-261.

Rogers, E.M. 2003, *Diffusion of innovations*, 5.th edn, Free press, New York.

Sacco G, Joumier VV, Darmon N, Dechamps A, Derreumaux A, Lee J-HH, et al. Detection of activities of daily living impairment in Alzheimer's disease and mild cognitive impairment using information and communication technology. *ClinInterv Aging* [Internet]. 2012;7:539-49.

Sheehan, B. (2012). Assessment scales in dementia. *Therapeutic advances in neurological disorders*, 5(6), 349-358.

Shulman, K. I. (2000). Clock-drawing: is it the ideal cognitive screening test?. *International journal of geriatric psychiatry*, 15(6), 548-561.

Smith, S. C., Lamping, D. L., Banerjee, S., Harwood, R., Foley, B., Smith, P., ... & Mann, A. (2005). Measurement of health-related quality of life for people with dementia: development of a new instrument (DEMQOL) and an evaluation of current methodology. *Health Technology Assessment (Winchester, England)*, 9(10), 1-93.

Spradley, J. (1979). *The Ethnographic Interview*. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston Inc.

Subramaniam P, Woods B. Digital life storybooks for people with dementia living in care homes: An evaluation. *ClinIntervAging*. 2016;11:1263-76.

Umidi, S., Trimarchi, P. D., Corsi, M., Luzzati, C., & Annoni, G. (2009). Clock drawing test (CDT) in the screening of mild cognitive impairment (MCI). *Archives of gerontology and geriatrics*, 49, 227-229.

Unverzagt, F. W., Kasten, L., Johnson, K. E., Rebok, G. W., Marsiske, M., Koepke, K. M., ... & Rexroth, D. F. (2007). Effect of memory impairment on training outcomes in ACTIVE. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 13(06), 953-960.

Van Mierlo LD, Meiland FJM, Van de Ven PM, Van Hout HPJ, Dröes R-M. Evaluation of DEM-DISC, customized e-advice on health and social support services for informal carers and case managers of people with dementia; a cluster randomized trial. *Int Psychogeriatr* [Internet]. 2015;27(8):1365-78.

Vijayavenkataraman, S., Lu, W. F., & Fuh, J. Y. H. (2016). 3D bioprinting—An Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (ELSA) framework. *Bioprinting*, 1, 11-21.

Woods, B., Aguirre, E., Spector, A. E., & Orrell, M. (2012). Cognitive stimulation to improve cognitive functioning in people with dementia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 2(2).

Yasini M, Marchand G. Adoption and use of a mobile health application in older adults for cognitive stimulation. *Stud Health Technol Inform*. 2016;221:13-7.